

**TOWARDS SUSTAINABILITY: THE ROLE OF SUPPLY CHAIN CAPABILITIES,
RESILIENCE, CIRCULAR ECONOMY, AND BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN
FOOD SUPPLY CHAINS**

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Declaration

I declare that this dissertation is entirely my own original work and has been composed solely by myself. It contains no material previously submitted, either in whole or in part, for any other degree, diploma, or qualification at any university or institution.

Amina Mehmood

11-01-2025

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RESEARCH OUTPUTS FROM THIS DISSERTATION

The research conducted for this dissertation has resulted in several publications, which were co-authored with members of the supervisory committee. These publications represent only a portion of the work contained in this thesis.

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ABSTRACT

In today's competitive landscape, sustainability has evolved from a trend to a strategic imperative, particularly challenging for the complex and waste-prone food supply chain. This study explores the synergistic effects of three critical pillars: resilience, circular economy (CE), and I4.0 technologies particularly Blockchain technology (BCT) on sustainable performance of food supply chains. While these elements independently contribute to sustainability, research on their combined effects has remained fragmented. This study bridges that gap by examining how these pillars interact with core supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) to enhance sustainability in food supply chain.

The research examines the relationship between supply chain capabilities, resilience, CE practices and BCT in achieving sustainable supply chain performance, drawing on a combination of Resource-Based View (RBV), Resource Dependence Theory (RDT), and Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT). To achieve its objectives, this study set out to collect primary data via a self-administered survey from 299 managerial-level employees in the dynamic UK food and drink manufacturing sector. Structural equation modelling (SEM) was used to test hypotheses. The results revealed that SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) play a significant role in strengthening SC resilience, which enhances an organization's ability to manage and recover from disruptions effectively. While collaboration and traceability were found to foster CE practices, agility's influence on CE practices was not statistically significant. Furthermore, collaboration did not directly influence sustainable supply chain performance in this study. Notably, supply chain resilience and circular economy practices both demonstrated statistically significant positive impacts on sustainable supply chain performance. The mediation analysis showed that SC resilience positively and significantly mediates the relationship between agility, traceability, and sustainable supply chain performance. However, collaboration's impact on sustainable performance was not mediated by SC resilience. Additionally, the study found that circular economy practices positively and significantly mediate the relationship between agility, collaboration, traceability, and sustainable supply chain performance. Moderation analysis suggests that Blockchain technology plays a complex moderating role. Specifically, it enhances the synergistic effects of agility and collaboration on supply chain resilience while showing no impact on traceability. Blockchain also strengthens the positive relationships between collaboration and traceability concerning circular economy practices, though it mitigates the negative influence of agility on these practices. Interestingly, Blockchain technology amplifies the positive effects of agility and collaboration on sustainable supply chain performance although it does not have a positive effect on traceability. The conceptual framework presented in this study offers a novel foundation for enhancing sustainability in supply chains by integrating supply chain resilience, circular economy (CE) practices, core supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), and Blockchain technology. By strategically harnessing these components, supply chain professionals can drive meaningful sustainability improvements throughout their supply chain performance.

Keywords: Supply chain capabilities, supply chain agility, supply chain collaboration, supply chain traceability, supply chain resilience, circular economy (CE), Blockchain technology, sustainability, sustainable performance, food supply chain

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TERMINOLOGIES

Term	Description
Food Supply Chain (FSC)	<i>“A series of processes in a "farm-to-fork" framework involves growing, producing, quality testing, packaging, storage, transportation, distribution, and marketing” (R. Sharma et al., 2020; Tsolakis et al., 2014).</i>
Supply Chain Resilience (SCRES)	<i>“SC refers to the ability of a supply chain to return to its original state or improve to a more favourable condition after experiencing a disruption” Christopher and Peck (2004).</i>
Circular Economy (CE)	<i>“A circular economy is a system designed to be regenerative by nature. It operates with two types of material flows: biological materials, which are designed to re-enter the biosphere safely, and technical materials, which are intended to circulate within the economy with minimal loss of quality” (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2013).</i>
Supply Chain Capabilities (SCCs)	<i>“SC capabilities refer to firm's ability to effectively manage and optimize various aspects of its supply chain operations. These capabilities encompass a range of skills, processes, and technologies that facilitate a firm to efficiently transfer goods and information from suppliers to end consumers” (F. Wu et al., 2006).</i>
Supply Chain Agility (Ag)	<i>“SC agility refers to an organization's ability to rapidly and efficiently adapt its supply chain operations in response to changes in market conditions, customer demands, and external pressures” (Gligor et al., 2020).</i>
Supply Chain Collaboration (Col)	<i>“Supply chain collaboration is defined as the partnership between two or more independent organizations working together to plan and execute supply chain operation” (Cao et al., 2010).</i>
Supply Chain Traceability (Tr)	<i>“SC traceability implies to the ability to track and trace the movement of products and their components throughout the entire supply chain, from raw materials to end consumers” (Skilton and Robinson, 2009).</i>
Industry 4.0 (I4.0)	<i>The term "Industry 4.0" stems from the concept of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, representing a new phase in industrial development that follows the first three industrial revolutions (L. Da Xu et al., 2018).</i>
Blockchain Technology (BCT)	<i>“Blockchain technology (BCT) is an advanced, decentralized, and distributed system that affirms the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of transactions and data. It consists of a chain of blocks, each containing a comprehensive record of transactions, much like a traditional public ledger” (Zheng et al., 2017).</i>
Sustainability	<i>“Sustainable development refers to the development that fulfils the needs of the current generation without limiting the capacity of future generations to satisfy their own needs.” (WCED, 1987).</i>
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)	<i>The sustainable performance of a supply chain refers to the outcomes achieved through the implementation of sustainable development practices (Nursimloo et al., 2020).</i>

CHAPTER 1 : INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

Food is absolutely essential to the continued existence of humans on our planet. To bring the food from farm to folk it passes through the complex network of operations and involve a wide range of stakeholders collectively known as the food supply chain (FSC). At a macro level, the primary links in the chain consist of agricultural operations, food production, distribution, and consumption. Nevertheless, at micro level, there are a variety of other actors, such as agrochemical and feedstock suppliers, machinery and equipment manufacturers and suppliers, farmers, marketers, and sellers, food processors, food additive suppliers, packaging companies, logistics firms, food retailers, consumers, and waste processors. Another important stakeholder is research organisations, both public and private, that work in the many agri-food business subsectors (R. Sharma et al., 2020; Tsolakis et al., 2014).

The expanding global interest in the concept of sustainability intensifies the demand for businesses to rethink their conventional approaches to the production, consumption, and disposal of goods. The agri-food sector has made significant strides in tackling important concerns including food safety, quality assurance, and carbon footprint reduction in the direction of more sustainable approaches (Anastasiadis et al., 2022). Yet, the total amount of waste generated throughout the global agri-food supply chain was roughly 1.3 billion tonnes (FAO, 2019). This waste can be attributed to the misuse of resources throughout both the pre- and post-harvest stages, as well as inefficient processes in the supply chain and unsustainable consumer consumption patterns. Additionally, the length of supply chain, perishability, seasonality, quality, safety, and varied production lead time made food supply chain more complicated and vulnerable to significant interruptions than the other supply chains (Behzadi et al., 2017; P. Kumar & Kumar Singh, 2021; R. Sharma et al., 2020).

The increasing frequency of unforeseen disruptions has propelled resilience to the forefront as a key competitive advantage in supply chain management. As businesses face an ever-growing array of challenges and uncertainties, the ability to withstand, adapt to, and quickly recover from disruptions has become a critical factor in maintaining operational continuity and market position (Carvalho et al., 2012). The significance of resilience in supply chains (SCs) has become more critical because of the worldwide unprecedented catastrophes, including strikes, terrorism and economic crisis and natural calamities such as floods, equipment failure and pandemics. These incidents have highlighted the vulnerability of supply chains to unexpected shocks. In response, resilience is regarded as one of the most important prerequisites for a supply chain (SC) to survive and grow in an uncertain and dynamic economic environment, as well as to operate better even after being disrupted (Christopher & Peck, 2004) Building resilience into supply chain strategies has evolved from a contingency measure to a fundamental aspect of business competitiveness and long-term success (Sheffi, 2005).

The circular economy (CE) has gained attention as a promising alternative to the conventional linear economic model of "take-make-waste," focusing on principles of regeneration, waste reduction, and pollution minimization (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015). This innovative approach to resource utilization offers organizations a fresh perspective on how to create and capture value throughout the product lifecycle. At its core, the circular economy emphasizes the recovery and regeneration of resources once a product has reached the end of its useful life (Mangla et al, 2018; Farooque et al, 2019). The integration of CE practices (CEP) in supply chain management offers compelling prospective in achieving the desired business performance, decreasing the consumption of raw materials, promoting the reuse and closed-loop flow of materials, preventing energy leakages, lowering emissions, preventing pollution, and overall decline of environmental impact (Bai et al. 2020; Lengyel, 2021). By adopting CE principles, organizations can create more sustainable supply chains that not only contribute to environmental preservation but also drive economic value, encouraging businesses to rethink their resource utilization strategies for a more sustainable future.

Supply chain capabilities (SCCs) are fundamental to an organization's ability to effectively manage its entire supply chain by identifying, utilizing, and integrating both internal and external resources and information (F. Wu et al., 2006). These capabilities are unique to each firm and represent their distinct strengths, making them difficult for competitors to replicate them (Wernerfelt, 1984). The literature distinguishes between ordinary (or operational/static) capabilities and dynamic capabilities. Ordinary or operational capabilities determine how a firm produces revenue, whereas dynamic capabilities drive change and improvement (Laaksonen & Peltoniemi, 2018). The objective of dynamic capabilities is to strategically reconfigure a company's resources and operational procedures in order to achieve substantial improvements (H. Aslam, Blome, et al., 2020; Cepeda & Vera, 2007). Researchers have suggested that the development of "dynamic capabilities" and the subsequent application of those capabilities can enable firms to identify and reduce vulnerabilities before they occur (Echefaj et al., 2022; W. Yu et al., 2019). The importance of supply chain capabilities has been emphasized by scholars, who have provided comprehensive lists of both static and dynamic logistics and supply chain capabilities (Defee & Fugate, 2010). This distinction underscores the need for organizations to not only focus on their day-to-day operational capabilities but also to cultivate dynamic capabilities that allow them to adapt and flourish in an ever-changing business environment.

Digital technologies have profoundly transformed the way societies communicate and exchange Information, revolutionizing interpersonal and business interactions (Nasiri, 2021). These technological innovations offer a multitude of benefits, including more efficient production processes, increased profit margins, cost reduction, enhanced reliability, and improved management control (H. Gupta et al., 2021). The concept of Industry 4.0 encompasses a wide array of emerging technologies that are reshaping the industrial landscape. These include big data analytics, simulation tools, additive manufacturing techniques, autonomous robots and vehicles, horizontal and vertical system integration, blockchain technology, robust cybersecurity measures, augmented and virtual reality applications, cloud

computing, fog and edge technologies, and the Internet of Things (IoT) etc. Together, these advancements are driving a new era of industrial capability, enabling exceptional degrees of automation, connection, and data-informed decision-making across many economic sectors (Katsaliaki et al., 2022).

Blockchain technology (BCT) has appeared as one of the most significant technologies of Industry 4.0, fundamentally transforming various sectors and industries (Saberli et al., 2019). This decentralized ledger technology utilizes peer-to-peer (P2P) networks for data sharing and verification, streamlining company operations and ensuring the integrity and authenticity of transactions within its ecosystem (Rejeb et al., 2023). As blockchain continues to mature and evolve, its influence is extending beyond its initial association with cryptocurrencies, promising to reshape industries and redefine how we approach digital transactions and information sharing (Berdik et al., 2021, Tseng et al., 2020). Furthermore, BCT offers the promise of reduced transaction costs, increased trust among industry participants, and the creation of a more secure and reliable medium for communication regarding complex supply chain processes (Chari et al., 2022). In the context of supply chains, blockchain technology has the ability to facilitate enhanced capabilities and guarantee data integrity for both upstream and downstream parties by increasing transparency across all stakeholders. The comprehensive impact of blockchain technology underscores its potential to reshape industries and redefine how businesses approach digital transactions and information sharing in the era of Industry 4.0.

Enhancing sustainability in food supply chains requires a holistic approach that combines resilience-building, circular economy practices, and the strategic use of technological innovations (Jones & Wynn, 2021). Although supply chain management (SCM) has shown varying levels of interest in the concepts of resilience, circular economy (CE), and Industry 4.0 (I4.0), research examining their combined effects and interactions remains scattered across various academic sources. This dispersion of knowledge underscores the need for a more unified understanding of how resilience, circular economy practices, and technological advancements can synergistically transform food supply chains to meet contemporary sustainability demands.

To bridge this gap, the present study offers an integrated examination of these key elements. Specifically, this research examines the intricate associations between supply chain capabilities, resilience, circular economy practices, and blockchain technology in fostering sustainable supply chain performance. Through investigating these interconnections, the study aims to provide a comprehensive framework that explains how these components work together to enhance the sustainable performance of food supply chains.

This holistic approach not only contributes to the academic understanding of sustainable supply chain management but also offers practical insights for food industry stakeholders. By examining the synergies between supply chain capabilities, resilience, circular economy practices, and emerging technologies like blockchain, the research seeks to illuminate pathways for creating more robust,

environmentally responsible, and technologically advanced food supply chains capable of meeting future challenges while promoting sustainability.

1.2 Research Problem and Knowledge Gaps

In a dynamic, technological advanced and high-demand market, resilience and circular economy combined with industry 4.0 in the framework of supply chain management (SCM) may contribute to greater competitive advantage for businesses (Chari et al., 2022). (Jones & Wynn, 2021) suggested that integration of resilience and CE principles along with I4.0 in SCs, will improve economic potential in green technology, raw material and energy reduction, and the creation of innovative routes for the recovery and re-use of waste material from virgin resources. Although, resilience and CE are two independent concepts but they both interlink with sustainability. Resilience can be viewed as a means of achieving sustainability in the face of disturbances within a system, emphasizing the ability to adapt and recover from unexpected changes while maintaining essential functions (Brassesco et al., 2022). On the other hand, the circular economy (CE) represents a new paradigm for attaining sustainability (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). This economic concept focuses on maximizing the value derived from goods, materials, and resources by extending their lifecycle as much as possible while minimizing waste generation. Together, resilience and the circular economy offer complementary approaches to addressing sustainability challenges, with resilience highlighting adaptability and recovery, and CE promoting resource efficiency and waste reduction (Jones and Wynn, 2021). To incorporate resilience and CE practices in supply chain management is not simple rather a complex process that demands organization's inherent capabilities (Castro-Lopez et al., 2023; Gunasekaran et al., 2015; Jones & Wynn, 2021; O. Khan et al., 2020). As a result, supply chain capabilities are fundamental in the development and maintenance of resilient and circular supply chains.

A burgeoning body of literature concentrated on the importance of resilience in sustainable supply chain (Ivanov, 2018; Jabbarzadeh et al., 2018; Raut et al., 2021; Zahiri et al., 2017; X. Zhu & Wu, 2022) and CE in sustainable supply chain (Bai et al., 2020; Del Giudice et al., 2020; Hussain & Malik, 2020; Kumar Mangla et al., 2021). There is a limited body of research that integrates the concepts of resilience and circular economy (CE) to facilitate the achievement of sustainable performance in supply chain management (Chari et al., 2022). Mostly, relevant research on the issue is primarily fragmented, with a focus on resilience and circular economy as two distinct subjects. To effectively integrate CE and resilience practices in SCM, SC capabilities can play a significant role (Nandi et al., 2021). Numerous studies have demonstrated the significant influence of SC capabilities on the development of resilient (Brusset & Teller, 2017; Echefaj et al., 2022; Kalubanga & Gudergan, 2022; Mandal et al., 2016; Parnell et al., 2015) and circular supply chains (Yu et al., 2021., Khan, Daddi and Iraldo, 2020, 2021, Ersoy et al., 2022, Rehman Khan et al., 2022).

Sustainability and industry 4.0 are prominent areas of focus in modern supply chains (de Sousa Jabbour et al., 2018). These areas can be strategically aligned to effectively address several of the United

Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Therefore, the mere possession of I4.0 technological resources by firms does not necessarily result in improvements in supply chain sustainable performance (Madhani, 2021). In contrast, it is imperative that firms utilise their technological resources to enable the development of capabilities at both the firm-level and supply chain-level (Liang et al., 2010; X. Zhang et al., 2011). These SC capabilities are unique to each firm and have a significant impact in achieving sustainable performance (Paulraj, 2011). One of the widely acknowledged Industry 4.0 promising technologies is the blockchain in the realm of supply chain management. Nonetheless, little attention is given to examine the relationship of BCT and supply chain capabilities.

Finally, despite the significance of resilience and CE in sustainability efforts overall, very little attention has been given to investigate them in the field of food supply chains.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

The primary aim of this study is to investigate the impact of supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability), supply chain resilience, CE practices and Blockchain technology on sustainable supply chain performance. To achieve the aim of this research the objectives are as follows:

- 1) To investigate the impact of supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on supply chain resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance.
- 2) To investigate the impact of supply chain resilience and CE practices on sustainable supply chain performance.
- 3) To examine the mediating role of supply chain resilience and CE practices between supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance.
- 4) To examine the moderating role of Blockchain technology on supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability), supply chain resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance.
- 5) To develop a comprehensive framework of supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), supply chain resilience, CE practices and Blockchain technology in achieving sustainable supply chain performance in food and drink manufacturing industry UK.

1.4 Research Questions

After reviewing the literature extensively, the following questions will be investigated in this study:

RQ1. *What is the impact of supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on supply chain resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance?*

RQ2. *What is the impact of supply chain resilience and CE practices on sustainable supply chain performance?*

RQ3. *Do supply chain resilience and CE practices play a mediating role between supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance?*

RQ4. Does Blockchain technology moderate the influence of supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability), on supply chain resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance?

1.5 Research Significance

The current dynamic and highly competitive nature of the business environment necessitates research that makes a significant and valuable contribution to both academic understanding and industrial practise. Therefore, the value of a study is determined by whether or not it allows for both practitioners and academics to take into account each other's perspectives in a holistic manner and collaborate closely towards analysing outcomes (Bashir, 2012).

The objective of this study is to provide a substantial contribution to the current body of research on supply chain management. This contribution will be made through the following ways:

1.5.1 Contribution to Academic Knowledge

The literature extensively examines the concepts of resilience and circular economy (CE) as potential solutions to sustainability challenges. Resilience pertains to the ability of a system to endure and recover from disruptions, serving as a crucial characteristic for organisations to achieve long-term sustainability within dynamic and intricate environments (Stone & Rahimifard, 2018; Tendall et al., 2015). Whereas the CE is commonly regarded as a prerequisite for achieving sustainability, with various scholarly works presenting it as either a mutually beneficial relationship or a potential trade-off (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). This study offers significant contributions to the field in multiple ways. Primarily, it addresses a critical gap in existing literature by integrating the concepts of SC resilience (SCRES) and circular economy (CE) practices. Current research tends to treat these topics as separate entities, resulting in a fragmented understanding of their relationship. This research uniquely focuses on the intersection of these concepts, exploring their interactions and mutual influences. By doing so, it will provide a more comprehensive and nuanced perspective on how resilience and circular economy principles can be synergistically applied in supply chain management.

Secondly, this study evaluates the SC capabilities and identifies three key capabilities: agility, traceability and collaboration in integration of SC resilience and CE. To the best of the authors' knowledge, it is one of the first efforts to investigate the SC capabilities (agility, traceability, and collaboration) to achieve resilient and circular supply chains.

Thirdly, since prior studies have mainly concentrated on the direct impact of BCT on sustainability, this study addresses the dearth of literature by examining the moderating role of blockchain technology (BCT) in influencing SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) to contribute to SC resilience, CE practices, and ultimately, sustainable supply chain performance.

Lastly, this research contributes to the existing body of knowledge by highlighting the synergistic value of the resource-based perspective, the resource-dependent theory, and the dynamic capability theory in

highlighting the crucial role of SC capabilities and BCT in building resilience and implementing CE practices in supply chains. Additionally, this study proposes a theoretical framework which integrates the SC capabilities, SC resilience, CE concepts leverage with BCT in supply chains (SCs) with the aim of improving the sustainable performance of supply chains.

1.5.2 Contribution to Industry / Practice

The agrifood system represents the largest manufacturing sector in numerous developed and developing nation. From a long-term perspective, it is continually struggling to fulfil the constantly changing customer and governmental food safety concerns along with a sustainable evolvement in business (Agnusdei & Coluccia, 2022; Genovese et al., 2017). Additionally, the challenges related to global food crises highlight the importance of the agrifood supply chain as a vital element in accomplishing the second Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), which aims to “end hunger, ensure food security, and promote sustainable agriculture” (UN, 2015). This research will help the management of Agri food sector in achieving sustainability in their supply chains by illuminating the contextual relationship between SC resilience and CE practices. This study can also assist supply chain managers in effectively using relevant capabilities, such as agility, traceability, and collaboration to accomplish sustainability. To attain sustainability, it is imperative for supply chain managers to consider the technologically driven environment across all stages of supply chain operations (J. Köhler et al., 2022). Therefore, this study will assist managers in identifying the well-recognised potential of blockchain technology within the context of sustainability in supply chain management. It will also help managers to understand that BCT implementation goes beyond direct sustainability enhancements, particularly at the supply chain level. It serves as a powerful enabler, amplifying key SC capabilities to foster SC resilience and implementation of circular economy practices. This integration will foster the target of sustainable performance of supply chain at all levels.

1.6 Scope and Limitation of the Study

The current study focuses exclusively on medium and large food and drink manufacturing firms in the UK that have initiated or adopted blockchain technology (BCT) and circular economy (CE) practices. Given that BCT is a recent innovation with significant implementation costs, the potential number of respondents may be limited. To address this constraint, the researcher plans to employ a multiple-response strategy, soliciting several responses from each participating firm to ensure a sufficient sample size. Furthermore, the study's scope is narrowed to target supply chain professionals (including those in operations, logistics, sales, production, purchasing, procurement, and distribution) and IT managers. These individuals are selected based on the assumption that they possess the most comprehensive understanding of their firms' supply chain operations and the associated innovative technologies. This targeted approach aims to gather insights from those most closely involved with and knowledgeable

about the implementation of BCT and CE practices within their organizations, ensuring the collection of relevant and informed data.

1.7 Thesis Structure

This dissertation is structured into the following six chapters:

Chapter 1: serves as an introduction to the dissertation, providing a comprehensive overview of the study. This chapter is carefully structured to familiarize the reader with the key topics of interest and establish the foundation for the research. It clearly articulates the research objectives, emphasizing the significance and relevance of the study.

Chapter 2: provides an in-depth examination of the literature related to the industry analysis of the UK agri-food sector, emphasizing several key areas of interest. This chapter aims to provide a clear foundation for understanding the key challenges in the food supply sector, along with the roles of its main actors.

Chapter 3: provides a comprehensive review of relevant literature pertaining to several key areas: supply chain capabilities, supply chain resilience, circular economy practices, blockchain technology, and sustainable supply chain performance. This chapter also presents the formulated hypotheses based on the literature, the theoretical underpinning the research, and culminates in the development of a conceptual framework.

Chapter 4: focuses on the research methodology employed in this study. It begins by exploring and explaining various research philosophies, providing a comprehensive overview of different epistemological and ontological approaches. Following this exploration, the chapter presents a detailed justification for the selection of positivism as the most suitable research paradigm for this particular study. This justification is grounded in the nature of the research questions, the objectives of the study, and the type of data required to address these objectives effectively.

Chapter 5: provides a comprehensive quantitative analysis of the collected data. It begins with a detailed presentation of descriptive statistics for demographic information, offering insights into the characteristics of the study participants. The chapter then focuses on preparing the dataset for structural equation modelling (SEM). This preparation includes data cleaning, handling of missing values, outlier detection, and normality checks.

Chapter 6: presents a comprehensive analysis of the data using structural equation modelling (SEM) techniques. This chapter provides an in-depth statistical examination of the research hypotheses and the proposed conceptual framework. It meticulously outlines the steps taken in the SEM process, including data preparation, model specification, estimation, and evaluation. The chapter offers a detailed interpretation of the results, focusing on key aspects such as model fit indices, path coefficients, and the significance of relationships between variables.

Chapter 7 & 8: encompasses comprehensive discussion of the findings, implications, conclusions, and limitations of the study. This chapter provides an in-depth analysis of the results, exploring their

significance and relevance to the research questions. It also highlights the practical implications of the findings for practitioners and policymakers in the field. Additionally, the chapter summarizes the key conclusions drawn from the research while acknowledging any limitations that may affect the interpretation of the results.

1.8 Chapter Summary

This chapter encompasses several key components essential for framing the research study. It begins with the background of the study, providing context and historical insights relevant to the topic. A brief introduction to the industry follows, highlighting its characteristics and significance. The problem statement clearly defines the specific issue the research aims to address, while the significance of the study is discussed from both theoretical and practical perspectives, illustrating its contributions to academic knowledge and real-world applications. The research questions guide the inquiry, supported by clearly defined research objectives that outline the study's goals. Finally, the scope of the study delineates its boundaries, clarifying what will be included and what will not, thereby setting a clear framework for the research that follows.

Figure 1.1 Thesis Structure

Aim	Research Objectives
To investigate the impact of SC capabilities, SC resilience, CE practices and Blockchain technology (BCT) on sustainable supply chain performance	1 To investigate the impact of supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on supply chain resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance
	2 To investigate the impact of supply chain resilience and CE practices on sustainable supply chain performance
	3 To examine the mediating role of supply chain resilience and CE practices between supply chain capabilities and sustainable supply chain performance
	4 To examine the moderating role of Blockchain technology on supply chain capabilities, supply chain resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance
	5 To develop a comprehensive framework of supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), supply chain resilience, CE practices and Blockchain technology in achieving sustainable supply chain performance in food and drink manufacturing industry UK

CHAPTER 2 : LITERATURE REVIEW (INDUSTRY OVERVIEW)

2.1 Brief Overview of UK Agri Food Sector

The agri-food sector in the United Kingdom plays a significant role in stimulating economic growth. It contributed £128.3 billion to national Gross Value Added (GVA) in 2021 (www.gov.uk). It is distinguished by its intricate nature, which encompasses a wide range of activities including food production, processing, retailing, consumption, and disposing. The food system is facilitated by various players and activities, which are backed by essential components such as transportation and market infrastructure, financial services, trade, and logistics, among others. They are governed by rules, laws, certifications, and policies that apply to a variety of industries and levels on the spatial, temporal, and jurisdictional scales. These driving forces influence the conduct and future course of the food system along with biophysical variables. The food system yields consequences pertaining to food and nutrition security, economic and social welfare, and environmental sustainability. The UK is ranked ninth out of 113 countries in the Economist Intelligence Unit's 2021 Global Food Security Index (Global Food Security Index 2022). In terms of food loss and waste, agricultural sustainability, and nutritional issues, it ranks 26th out of 67 countries in the Food Sustainability Index 2021. Just-in-time food supply systems, in which products in supply chains arrive precisely when needed, should be held partially responsible for the fragility and vulnerability of the UK food system. These systems are susceptible to even little disturbances, which have an impact that spreads and gets stronger over time.

The food and beverage sector is the largest manufacturing industry in the UK, surpassing both the automotive and aerospace sectors combined. In 2022, the Food and Drink sector in Great Britain (GB) employed 3.7 million individuals, which increases to 4.1 million when including agriculture, fishing, and self-employed farmers as shown in Fig 2.1 below.

Figure 2.1 Number of Employees (millions)

(Source: www.gov.uk)

In 2022, the food and drink manufacturing sector had around 8,285 small and medium enterprises (SMEs), including micro businesses, with a turnover just under £22 billion and employing 148,000 people. In contrast, there were approximately 260 large businesses in the sector, generating £76 billion in turnover and employing 294,000 people. SMEs made up 97% of businesses in this sector, contributed

22% to total turnover, and accounted for 33% of the employment (www.gov.uk). The number of SMEs and large businesses in different food businesses are provided in Fig 2.2.

Figure 2.2 Number of UK food and drink manufacturers in 2022

(Source: www.gov.uk)

The UK's food production to supply ratio, which serves as a measure of the capacity of UK agriculture to fulfil domestic consumer needs, was recorded at 74% for indigenous food items in 2021 (Agriculture in the UK Evidence Pack, 2022). The UK has historically been a major net importer of food. It is advantageous to have a diversified range of food supplies, including imports from a wide range of stable economies, to maintain a robust food chain. In 2022, 58% of domestic consumption was sourced from UK production (calculated based on the unprocessed value at the farmgate), while 23% originated from the EU and the remaining 19% came from other countries around the world (www.gov.uk) as shown in Fig 2.3.

Figure 2.3 Origins of Food

(Source: *Agriculture in the UK Evidence Pack, 2022*)

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The overall value of food and drink exports dropped to £20.2 billion in 2021, which is £4.7 billion lower than the record high of £24.9 billion reached in 2019. The category that experienced the largest decline in value was fruit and vegetables, which fell by £0.4 billion, or 32% (www.gov.uk) as represented in Fig 2.4.

Figure 2.4 Imports / Exports

(Source: Agriculture in the UK Evidence Pack, 2022)

2.2 Food Industry challenges

The role of the Food industry (retailer, manufacturer, and food services) has a substantial effect on social, economic, and environmental development in the world economy (Turi et al., 2014) as it is the key source of food supply to the world population. Due to globalization food supply chains FI is facing numerous challenges.

(a). Population and Income

The world population is expected to increase from 7.7 billion in 2019 to 8.5 billion in 2030, 9.7 billion in 2050 will have a significant impact on world demand for food (UN, 2019). As population is growing more people needs to be fed, this increase in food demand critically depends on the capacity of the world food supply (Cirera & Masset, 2010; Muhammad, et al., 2025). Income is an important factor of food demand, as income increases more disposable income of households is available for food consumption as given in Fig 2.5.

Figure 2.5 Population growth over years

(Source: United Nations, 2019)

(b). Urbanization and the Contraction of the Agricultural Sector

Urbanization leads to the contraction of the farmland to urban land use. It is estimated that by 2030 the urbanized land will expand by 1.2 million km² more globally (Seto et al., 2012; Wang, et al., 2025). Such land use conversion reduces the agricultural land and impact the agriculture production (Liu, et al., 2025; UNICEF 2021). It will imposing serious threats to world food supply and adversely effects the FI (Mohammed Bakoji et al., 2020). Furthermore, the increasing population and growing urbanization are also key factors driving organic waste generation (Voukkali, et al., 2024). This increase in waste is having a notable effect on the environment, economy, and society.

(c). Structural Changes in Diets

Technologies in our kitchen, media, mode of transportation, government and trade has changed the food choices dramatically around the world (FAO, 2015: Alam, et al., 2025) as shown in Fig 2.6. These transitions signify new challenge for FI to provide what consumer wants to buy where consumers are getting more conscious about the quality of the food and demanding more organic and safe food (with less use of chemicals) (Mahesh, 2025; Jamuni & Halijol, 2025). These nutrition transitions outpacing the consumer demand from simple starchy plant dominated diet to more diverse food inputs including fruits, vegetables, dairy products, and meat put pressure on agricultural resources (Godfray, 2011).

Figure 2.6 Food consumption, major commodities (kg/year)

(Source: Food and Agriculture Organization, 2015)

(d). Food waste

Food Industry is also facing huge food waste problem. According to the Food and Agriculture Organisation Food (FAO) waste is "wholesome edible material intended for human consumption, arising at any point in the food supply chain that is instead discarded, lost, or degraded," (Gustafsson et al., 2013). Food loss and waste have been identified as significant factors to the overall amount of waste generated at various stages of the food supply chain (Borrello et al., 2016; Mohammed et al., 2025; Adelodun, et al., 2025). FAO (2014) estimated 1.3 billion tonnes, or one-third, of the world's food production was lost or squandered (Gonçalves & Guiné, 2025). From agricultural production to ultimate family consumption, this issue arises along the whole food supply chain (Parfitt, Barthel, and MacNaughton, 2010a; Kummu et al., 2012; Thapa, et al., 2025)

(e). Perishability

The agri-food supply chain involves all phases from cultivation, harvesting, and packaging to processing, transportation, marketing, and ultimate consumption. It encounters not just overarching risks associated with social, political, cultural, and economic aspects but also distinct vulnerabilities stemming from perishability, seasonality, quality, and safety standards (Amamou, et al., 2025). These traits render the food industry more complex and distinct from other sectors. Ensuring the quality of food throughout the supply chain to meet consumer expectations has become a significant challenge for the food industry.

(f). Climate Change

The agriculture sector is the most important sector of the economy that is very susceptible to climate change (Alawode, 2025). Climate changes threaten the arable land, crop production and food availability globally (Ludena & Mejia, 2012; Heikonen et al., 2025). The global food industry either upstream or downstream is enduring unprecedented changes due to climate degradation including the impact of changing in temperature and rain fall on agricultural production, quality, and distribution (Ridoutt et al., 2016). Moreover, natural disasters due to climate change impact food supply and distribution networks (Ikedigwe, 2025).

(g). Technology

Food industry has a responsibility to provide safe and secure food to the customers. Disruption of food supply chains due to climate change and the worldwide pandemic has underscored the necessity of innovation to enhance resilience in these supply chains (Stone & Rahimifard, 2018). The latest technological revolution is the fourth industrial revolution commonly called Industry 4.0. The utilization of technological novelties of I4.0 such as real time data streaming and information sharing at each step of supply chain level can make FSC more efficient (Nagy et al., 2020). The advantages of implementation of industry 4.0 paradigms in food industry is unquestionable but there are many challenges associated with the implementation of these technologies. The digitization without properly assessing the full cost of their implementation as well as improper evaluation of its benefits are the most common challenges for food industry (Oltra-Mestre et al., 2021). The readiness of FI for smart production system is still at its infancy.

(h). Pandemic

The World Health Organization (WHO) declared the COVID-19 outbreak a pandemic on March 11, 2020. Governments have imposed aggressive restrictions, smart or full lockdown due to the risk of virus contamination and its spread with direct physical contact. To stop the spread of COVID_19 organizations underwent drastic changes in their operations. Some organizations have to temporarily stop their operations; some have limited operations. While some organizations started running remotely work from home on their full or nearly full operations and activities. The most affected sector by this pandemic was food industry (FI). Due to the lockdown, community quarantine and stay at home restrictions by government, a surge in food consumption and stocking was seen. To deal with rise in food demand with the limited operations and labour capacity was a huge challenge for food industry (FI) (Rizou et al., 2020). Moreover, food supply chain disruptions due to limited workforce, operation hours and transportation made tremendous effect on logistic of food industry (Loske, 2020).

FI is the forefront industry of the economy to provide food to the world population and directly related to the well-being of people. Current global trends in business environment pushing the FI to transform its management approach. The main reasons for this transformation are rising food demand, change of consumer consumption pattern, urbanization, climate change and pandemic. To make FI more resilient it is essential to focus on the application of innovative technologies (Joshi et al., 2023) and close loop supply chains (Esposito et al., 2020; Jreissat et al., 2024; Krishnan et al., 2024).

2.3 Food Supply Chains

(Beamon, 1998) outlined the supply chain as a process that includes three fundamental stages: the procurement of raw materials, the transformation of these raw materials into finished products, and the distribution of the final products to various points in the supply network. According to (Handfield et al., 2011), SCs is a set of organizations that link the upstream or downstream flow of material through sharing of information from the point of production to the end customer. This involves several

independent firms in the process of production of a good or services to the end user of supply chain. (Sanders, 2020) defines supply chain as a network of all the activities including the production and delivery of finished product to the final consumers. This interdependence of activities in supply chains can jeopardise the effectiveness of the supply chain as disturbance in one part of the activity can produce ripple effect throughout the entire SC (Stevens & Johnson, 2016).

Food supply chains are essential to human existence. The availability of food at the appropriate time, quantity, and quality is every country's top priority, whether it is local or worldwide. "We can save on energy and forgo many luxuries, but without sufficient food of the right quality, our population cannot survive" (Mellanby, 1975, pp.1) is a quotation that emphasises the significance of food. This statement, although originating from the post-World War II period when the United Kingdom faced significant food scarcity, remains pertinent in today's economic landscape. Modern economies continue to operate on the principle of allocating limited resources efficiently to maximize overall benefits. The FAO reckons that more than 60% of the world's population depends on agriculture for their livelihood, and that agriculture is the biggest employer in the world, providing living to 40% of the population.

Figure 2.7 A graphical view of Agri food supply chain

(Source: Akhtar et al. 2017)

The food supply chain is defined as a series of activities that encompass the entire 'farm-to-fork' process as depicted in Fig 2.7. This includes multiple stages, such as farming (land cultivation for crop production), production, testing, packaging, warehousing, transportation, distribution, and marketing (R. Sharma et al., 2020; Tsolakis et al., 2014). Food supply chains (FSCs) are inherently complex and particularly vulnerable to disruptions due to factors such as perishability, seasonality, quality and safety requirements, and variable production lead times (Van Der Vorst et al., 2000). Agriculture sector is directly expose to the climate and its SCs are particularly critical with regards to the environment as emission of greenhouse gases and food waste (Parfitt et al., 2010). Food supply chains are also facing several social and ethical pressure such as food safety and animal welfare (Hartmann, 2011). These

concerns have led to the redesign of the supply chain (Krishnan et al., 2020) and new concepts have emerged such as green supply chains, sustainable supply chains, short food supply chains, alternative food networks etc (Thomé et al., 2021).

2.3.1 Phases of FSC

There are three main characteristics of FSCs: farming and agri inputs, food processing, logistics and distribution. Based on the nature of the operations these stages are further segregated and into six phases where goods flow from farmers to processor to the retailers (R. Sharma et al., 2020) as shown in the figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8 Supply chain activities

(Source: Sharma et al. 2020)

2.3.2 Key players and their roles in the food supply chain

AFSC is a complex form of networks that link farm to fork functions. A wide range of stakeholders are involved in it. Fig 2.9 maps the conceptual configuration of a typical Agri food supply chain.

Figure 2.9 Agrifood supply chains system

(Source: Tsolakis et al., 2014)

(a). Farmers/Producers

It includes wide range of key players from large-scale agricultural business to small scale farmers and from landlords to tenants. In typical mainstream of supply chain farmers sell their primary products to an intermediary (processors or wholesalers) even they can sell directly to consumers at their local markets.

(b). Agricultural cooperatives

In Agri sector cooperatives play an important role in both developed and developing countries. It enables independent farmers to withstand the market power of local and international retailers. It allows the farmers to integrate their most or all the processing and marketing procedures in few steps and provide considerable savings to farmers on transaction and other intermediate costs.

(c). Manufacturer and Processor

Food manufacturers/processors collect produce from farmers and create packaged food products by adding chemicals and nutritional additives. It includes a wide range of businesses such as fruit and vegetables preparation and packing, dairies, abattoirs, meal manufacturing and warehousing etc. Market concentration provides great power to processors to stipulate food requirements.

(d). Food Wholesalers

Food wholesalers gather produce in bulk from producers and manufacturers and sell it to retailers. This sector includes a diverse array of private sector participants, such as food distributors, wholesalers, and cold storage facilities. Within the supply chain, food wholesalers primarily serve as distributors.

(e). Retailers

In the mainstream of FSC retailers sell both farm and processed food directly to the consumers in local stores. This segment of the supply chain includes a vast array of businesses, ranging from international retail supermarkets to small independent stores, as well as informal markets and street food vendors. Buying pattern of retailers affects the inventory planning throughout the SC.

(f). Consumer

Consumer is the central element of the FSC. To meet consumer demand, it is important to consider consumer viewpoint when developing food products and processes. The awareness of health and nutritional aspects of food vis digital/print media has put more pressure on SC stakeholders to cater safety concerns of consumers.

(g). Research Institutes

Research organization in AFSCs promote the modernization and diversification in food sector through scientific research and technological innovations. Research organization helps active stakeholders to ensure food safety and quality, enhance production efficiency and lead their way to more innovative products and processes.

(h). Logistics and Third-Party Logistic Partners

Logistics and transport are embedded in all stages of SCs. The fundamental objective of AFSC is to provide right product, to right place, at right time and at right cost. Due to globalization logistical and transportation requires more extensive and advanced system for bringing food to the end consumer. To meet consumer's demand globally the concept of third party logistic is getting considerable attention in SCM literature. Third party logistics refers to as logistic outsourcing (Marasco, 2008). Companies use 3-PL partners for managing all or part of their logistic operations (Marasco, 2008; Radzi et al., 2020).

(i). Peculiarities of Food supply chain management

Food supply chains function within a multifaceted context where product quality is essential. Six critical characteristics significantly influence the development of FSCs, distinguishing them from other supply chains and contributing to their complexity.

(j). Quality

The degree of comparison between consumer's expectations and their realization is called quality (Bourlakis & Weightman, 2008). To satisfy the expectations of suppliers, customers and workforce is managers' task. Price is the fundamental element to determine the demand of a product. Companies generally avoid any activity that adds into cost and soar up the price of the commodity which customers are not willing to pay (Christopher, 1999). In developed world consumers are generally more quality conscious. Quality and its assurance have become an important aspect of supply chain management specially in modern era. However, to keep the quality of food product at a certain standard throughout the supply chain processes is very difficult and challenging (Reardon & Barrett, 2000). Due to the globalization of the food sector, food can be produced, transported, and consumed anywhere in the world which increases the length of supply chains. This has lead food processing companies to develop quality management systems and standards which are based on HACCP and ISO series. Those who are failed to adapt the rigorous requirements of international standards become non-competitive.

(k). Technology

Technology is an intrinsic factor in today's modern world. The myriads of technological innovations and developments increases the productivity, efficiency, and integrity of food supply chains (Cappellesso & Thomé, 2019). This includes precise seeding, organic animal and crop production, controlled temperature, accurate weighing, pasteurization, artificial insemination, and bar coding etc. These advancements are some of many applications of research and development in genetics, biology, biochemistry, engineering, computer science and other disciplines of agriculture.

(l). Information Technology

In food supply chain the application of information technology supports the movement of products and information dissemination. The scanning and bar-coding technologies are used widely to transport and process information by electronic data interchange (EDI) system in retail warehouses to identify the location of the product. The electronic data interchange (EDI) and Enterprise resource planning (ERP) based on particular standard coordinate different members of SCs and provide rapid data collection and

processing information in various SC operations (ko & Kincade, 1997). Internet has appeared as another EDI system and its use in food supply chain is largely favoured by food suppliers, processors and retailers. Internet allows the members of supply chain to exchange not only information it also reduces the excessive paperwork and made each supply chain process more visible.

(m). The Regulatory Framework

The regulatory framework established by both domestic and international legislation has a significant impact on food supply chains. The main aim of the food regulation is to address consumers concerns about food safety and quality (Aruoma, 2006). At national level through legislations food safety standards have been enforced and firms also have introduced various private standards. Public legislation of improving the food safety includes standards related to the attributes of the product, traceability within the food supply chains, production practices and legal accountability of the supply chain (Hammoudi et al., 2009). The public regulations are accompanied with many private standards which stipulates more stringent requirements than required. At International level the focus of discussion is primarily the legitimacy and harmonization of the standards (De Frahan & Vancauteran, 2006).

CHAPTER 3 : LITERATURE REVIEW (DEVELOPMENT OF HYPOTHESES AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK)

3.1 Supply Chain Management

More than thirty years have passed since the term "supply chain management" first appeared in published works (Oliver & Webber, 1982) and has become popular paradigm among academia and practitioners. While arriving at this overreaching definition still stands in a considerable muddle. One school of thought views functionality-based perspective (including management and control of all the flow of material and information) of SCM definition. Whereas other school of thought defines the term SCM as an integration of business practices from consumer through supplier (Gibson et al., 2005). According to the Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals (CSCMP), supply chain management is the most comprehensive method, including the planning and oversight of all sourcing and procurement-related activities, conversion procedures, and logistics management operations. It emphasises how crucial it is to work together and coordinate with different channel partners, including suppliers, middlemen, third-party service providers, and customers. In the end, supply chain management combines demand and supply management within and across enterprises, demonstrating its function as an integrated discipline that monitors the whole product flow (Gibson, Mentzer, and Cook, 2005).

3.2 Supply Chain Capabilities

Capabilities are crucial for the success of organizations involved in supply chain management (SCM). Over the past thirty years, research has consistently shown that (i) SCM is a key component of corporate strategy (Ellram & Carr, 1994) and (ii) capabilities are fundamental to supply chain strategy (Liao et al., 2017; Morash, 2001). Research across multiple disciplines, including supply chain management (SCM), information systems, management, and marketing, consistently emphasizes the significance of various capabilities for effective SCM and firm performance. Researchers in the field of supply chain management have thoroughly investigated various categories of SCM capabilities and their critical role in organizational success. This extensive body of work, as evidenced by studies from scholars such as (Krause, 1999; Lynch et al., 2000; Morash et al., 1996; Scheer et al., 2010; Weigelt, 2013) underscores the significance of these capabilities for companies operating in diverse supply chain environments. Aligning with capabilities-focused research in adjacent business disciplines, studies in supply chain management have repeatedly shown robust positive relationships between diverse capability types and organizational performance (Krause, 1999; Liao et al., 2017; Rajaguru & Matanda, 2019; X. Tang & Rai, 2012).

Initially, the terms "resources" and "capabilities" were often used interchangeably (Barney, 1991). Nonetheless, subsequent research refined the concept of resources to distinguish them more clearly from capabilities, while still acknowledging that capabilities can be considered a specific type of

resource (Kozlenkova et al., 2014). However, the research on capabilities is fragmented and encountered difficulties in establishing clear and consistent definitions. For example, (Amit & Schoemaker, 1993) conceptualized capability as an organization's capacity to utilize its resources. On the other hand, (Sanchez & Heene, 1996) offered a more comprehensive definition of capabilities, describing it as an organization's ability to maintain coordinated resource deployment to achieve its objectives. Despite these varying definitions, (Madhavaram & Hunt, 2008), followed the (Day, 1994) work and concluded that the terms "capabilities" and "competences" are fundamentally interchangeable due to their conceptual similarities.

As academic interest in capabilities expanded, different researchers categorize SC capabilities differently. (Teece et al., 1997) introduced dynamic capabilities to address the lack of scholarly focus on developing resources and capabilities in rapidly changing environments. Subsequently, (Winter, 2003) and (Zollo and Winter, 2002) distinguished between dynamic and operational capabilities. Specifically, (Zollo & Winter, 2002) noted that (Teece et al., 1997) overlooked the origins of dynamic capabilities and suggested that a dynamic capability involves a systematic pattern of activities that allows the organization to evolve and improve its routines over time, ultimately leading to better performance and adaptability in changing environments. Overall, research on dynamic capabilities (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece, 2007; Zahra et al., 2006) emphasizes the effect of dynamic capabilities on company performance through the enhancement of operational capabilities.

Teece et al. (1997) introduced the concept of dynamic capabilities, defining it as “the firm’s ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments” (p. 516). Building on this work, Teece (2007) further classified dynamic capabilities into three categories: sensing, seizing, and transforming. Sensing capabilities refer to a set of activities such as scanning, learning, and interpreting to identify new opportunities and threats. These activities encompass market orientation (monitoring and scanning), information sharing, traceability, visibility, trust and transparency, data immutability, customer identification, and supplier-customer integration (Beske et al., 2014; Chari et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2022a; Queiroz et al., 2021; Paul et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2020; De Giovanni, 2022; Chang et al., 2019). Seizing capabilities involve the processes of mobilising internal and external resources and competencies to pursue identified opportunities (Teece, 2007). Specific examples of seizing capabilities include agility, joint planning, resource allocation, collaboration, technology upgrading, standardisation, and resource sharing (Gebhardt et al., 2022; O. Khan et al., 2020; Nandi et al., 2021b; Patel & Sambasivan, 2022; Quayson et al., 2023). Transforming capabilities reflect a firm’s capacity to recombine and reconfigure its resources in response to recognised opportunities, thereby sustaining competitive advantage (Khan et al., 2020). Examples of transforming capabilities include auditing, internal restructuring, and organisational flexibility (H. Aslam, Blome, et al., 2020; Bag & Rahman, 2023; Beske, 2012; O. Khan et al., 2021; Kittipanya-ngam & Tan, 2020; Nandi et al., 2021b; Quayson et al., 2023).

(Day, 2014) presented the concept of adaptive capabilities, describing it as a firm's ability to enhance and expand its dynamic capabilities by adopting an outside-in approach. This, in turn, allows the firm to respond more swiftly to rapidly changing markets. (Morash, 2001) stated seven major SC capabilities as core competences including customer service, quality, information systems support, distribution flexibility, low logistic cost, productivity, delivery speed. According to Wu et al. (2006), supply chain capabilities are a higher-order construct. These higher-order constructs refer to organizational capabilities that are firm-specific and difficult to replicate across organizations, comprising four essential components: supply chain responsiveness, coordination, information sharing, and interfirm activity integration. According to (Amit & Schoemaker, 1993), Collis (1994), and Bharadwaj (2000), SC capabilities are the ability of an organisation to recognise, use, and integrate information and resources from both internal and external sources in order to support all supply chain operations. In this research, the researcher investigates three SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and their relationships with SC resilience, CE practices, and sustainable supply chain performance. Additionally, the researcher investigates how blockchain technology (BCT) influences these relationships. To address the research objectives, the investigator conceptualised supply chain (SC) capabilities as a higher-order construct, following the approach of Wu et al. (2006), and focused on these key capabilities which were chosen due to their significant role in fostering SC resilience, supporting CE practices, and enhancing sustainable performance within supply chains. Each of these three capabilities embodies the ability to execute both cross-functional and interorganizational activities essential for effective supply chain management. Additionally, they symbolise the supply chain's dynamic character, which enables a company to absorb knowledge and adjust to changes in the environment (Amit & Schoemaker, 1993; Teece et al., 1997).

3.2.1 Supply Chain Agility

SC agility is a strategic capability that allows organizations to quickly adjust their strategies and operations in response to fluctuations in the external business landscape (Gligor et al., 2020). This agility enables companies to enhance flexibility in their supply chain activities, swiftly modify their approaches, foresee external changes, and empower customers (Gligor et al., 2020). It helps organizations achieve a competitive edge in an unstable business environment (Blome et al., 2013; Brusset, 2016; Ngai et al., 2011; Swafford et al., 2006, 2008; Yusuf et al., 2014). The notion of agility was first introduced by the Iacocca Institute (Iacocca Institute, 1991) and further developed by Yusuf et al. in 1991. (Christopher, 2000) identified several characteristics that define a truly agile firm, including market sensitivity, a network-based approach (relying on shared information across all supply chain partners), and process integration. Additionally, the agility of suppliers is crucial for effectively implementing changes in a competitive global environment (Al Humdan et al., 2020). Supply chain agility capabilities have the potential to enhance supply chain efficiency, effectiveness, and return on investment (Cantele et al., 2023; Gligor et al., 2020).

3.2.2 Supply Chain Collaboration

Supply chain collaboration refers to the ability of two or more independent companies to work together efficiently, jointly planning and executing supply chain operations to achieve shared objectives (Cao et al., 2010). Supply chain collaboration serves as a catalyst for creating synergistic relationships among partners, facilitating joint planning initiatives, and promoting the sharing of real-time information. As Whipple and Russell (2007) point out, this collaborative approach enhances the overall effectiveness of the supply chain by encouraging partners to work together more closely. Many authors highlight mutual benefit, rewards, and risk-sharing, along with information exchange, as the foundation of collaboration (Barratt & Oke, 2007). For example, (Daugherty et al., 2006) emphasize that collaboration involves information sharing, joint strategic planning, and synchronized operations. Similarly, (Nyaga et al., 2010) point to information sharing, joint relationship efforts, and dedicated investments. (Simatupang & Sridharan, 2008) also outline supply chain collaboration activities, including information sharing, decision synchronization, and incentive alignment. Collaboration, as a sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) practice, is fundamentally connected to dynamic capabilities, representing the central theoretical contribution (Beske et al., 2014). This perspective suggests that the ability to collaborate effectively in supply chains is not just an operational necessity, but a strategic capability that can enhance an organization's ability to adapt and thrive in changing environments, which is at the heart of the dynamic capabilities' framework. Supply chain collaboration fosters trust among members, encouraging them to act in the best interest of the partnership. This integration allows each member to focus on their unique core competencies, thereby enhancing their competitive positions. Supply chain collaboration is a business process where members work together as partners to achieve shared goals (Cao & Zhang, 2011). According to (Liao & Kuo, 2014) supply chain collaboration is a business operation built on communication and interactions across the supply chain and with all stakeholders.

3.2.3 Supply Chain Traceability

The monitoring of supply chain activities has been relatively underexplored in the literature (Faucheux & Nicolai, 2011; Jenkin et al., 2011; Pennekamp et al., 2024; Setterstrom, 2008; L. Wang et al., 2011; G. Zheng & Brintrup, 2025). However, monitoring serves as a crucial risk management tool to mitigate information asymmetry (Tachizawa et al., 2015). A particular method for implementing monitoring is through the application of traceability systems (Wowak et al., 2016). Traceability can be broadly understood as the capability to identify and authenticate the various components and the sequence of events along the entire supply chain (Skilton & Robinson, 2009). Traceability encompasses two key aspects: tracking, which involves determining a product's origin and specific attributes, and tracing, which entails gathering information about a product's historical journey and movements throughout the supply chain (Bechini et al., 2008). For instance, traceability includes identifying the sources of raw materials, understanding the chemicals or elements in purchased products, monitoring the environmental performance across the supply chain, tracking the processes involved in product

manufacturing, and tracing the origins of purchased products throughout the supply chain (Dabbene et al., 2014). In fact, traceability is not confined to a single company's capabilities but rather depends on the intricate interactions within a network of companies. This includes intra- and inter-organizational supply chain expertise (Wowak et al., 2016), which are difficult for competitors to replicate (Skilton & Robinson, 2009). Specifically, the ability to track and trace products and activities helps to reduce information asymmetry and encourages supply chain partners to act opportunistically.

3.3 Supply Chain Resilience

3.3.1 Resilience

The notion of the word “resilience” is the Latin verb “resilio” meaning to return or to bounce back (Rose, 2009). The general concept of resilience was first introduced by (Holling, 1973) to understand the capacity of ecosystem to persist to original state after disturbance. Since then, it has been used or reinvented in a variety of disciplines. (B. Walker et al., 2004) defined the term resilience as “the ability of a system to absorb and withstand disturbances, reorganize itself while undergoing change, and maintain its core function, structure, identity, and feedback mechanisms”.

3.3.2 SC Resilience

Resilience is a and multidimensional phenomenon. Specific concept of SC resilience has emerged from these diverse perspectives of resilience. The broad notion of the resilience literature has led to lack of unified definition of SC resilience (Mensah & Merkurjev, 2014; Spiegler et al., 2012). Different studies highlighted different elements of SCRES, and various definitions can be identified from the literature. The first wide speared definition of SCRES is based on (Christopher and Peck, 2004) they asserted SC resilience as “the ability of a supply chain to return to its original state or move to a new, more desirable state after a disturbance”. (S. Y. Ponomarov & Holcomb, 2009), defines SCRES as “the ability of a supply chain to adapt and respond effectively to disruptions, ensuring operational continuity”. Several definitions identified from the literature are summarized in the table 3.1 based on their contribution to expanding SC resilience knowledge. Most of the studies address the recovery aspect of SC resilience from unanticipated disruptive events (Ambulkar et al., 2015; Blackhurst et al., 2011; Datta, 2017; Gunasekaran, Childe, et al., 2019; Gunasekaran et al., 2015; Hohenstein et al., 2015; Kamalahmadi & Parast, 2016; S. Y. Ponomarov & Holcomb, 2009; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015). However, few studies emphasised the time, cost, and speed of recovery features of the SCRES (Datta, 2017; Hohenstein et al., 2015).

Table 3-1 Existing definitions of SCRES from the literature

Source/Author	Scope	Definition
(Rice & Caniato, 2003)	SC resilience	Resilience refers to a firm's ability to effectively respond to and recover from unexpected disruptions, which can include extreme events such as terrorist attacks or natural disasters, as well as more routine business challenges.
	SC resilience – adaptive aspects	A system's resilience refers to its capacity to recover and adapt after experiencing a disruption.
(Sheffi & Rice, 2005)	SC resilience capability	Resilience is the capacity to recover from a disruption.
(S. Y. Ponomarov & Holcomb, 2009)	SC resilience – adaptive aspects	Supply chain resilience refers to the ability of the supply chain to adapt by preparing for unforeseen events, responding to disruptions, and recovering from them while maintaining operational continuity at the desired level of connectivity and control over its structure and functions.
(Pettit et al., 2010)	The value of resilience concept	The capacity of an enterprise to survive, adapt, and thrive amid turbulent change is referred to as its resilience.
(Jüttner & Maklan, 2011)	SC resilience capability	The ability of enterprises to endure, adapt, and expand in response to turbulent change is known as resilience.
(Wieland & Wallenburg, 2013)	SC resilience	The ability of [the] supply chain to cope with change”
(Ambulkar et al., 2015)	Firm resilience	The capability of the firm to remain vigilant, adapt to, and respond swiftly to changes caused by supply chain disruptions.
(Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015)	SC resilience – adaptive and reactive aspects	The adaptive ability of a SC encompasses its ability to prepare for and respond to disruptions, achieve a timely and cost-effective recovery, and advance to a post-disruption operational state that ideally surpasses the condition before the disruption.
(Scholten & Schilder, 2015)	SC resilience – response and recovery aspect	Resilience allows a supply chain to prepare for potential events, minimize the impact of disruptions, and enhances the ability to recover swiftly by ensuring continuity of operations while maintaining the desired level of connectedness and control over its structure and functions.
(M. M. H. Chowdhury & Quaddus, 2017)	SC resilience – adaptive, reactive and reactive aspects	The ability of a supply chain to prevent disruptions and reduce their impact entails establishing an appropriate level of preparedness, along with the capacity to respond swiftly and recover efficiently.
(Datta, 2017)	SC resilience – dynamic process	A dynamic process of guiding actions helps keep the organization out of the danger zone. When a disruptive or uncertain event arises, resilience involves launching a rapid and effective response to mitigate the impact while maintaining or restoring stability. This stability enables the organization to adapt its operations to the requirements of the changed environment more swiftly than its competitors, ensuring long-term success.
(Dubey, Gunasekaran, Childe, et al., 2019; Gunasekaran et al., 2015)	SC resilience	The characteristic of a supply chain that enables it to return to its normal operating performance within an acceptable timeframe after disruptive forces have been eliminated or ceased is referred to as recovery capability.

The chronological order of the SC resilience definitions show that they all consider SC resilience as a capability of SC to response and recovery to disruption. A disruption is defined as “an anticipated or unanticipated event which directly affect the operation of supply chain’ (Kamalahmadi & Parast, 2016).

Definition proposed by (Rice & Caniato, 2003) argues on the ability of a system to response and reinstate of operations. (Christopher & Peck, 2004) included the adaptability aspect as system's ability to return and move on new state. Similarly, (Sheffi & Rice, 2005) emphasised on the bouncing back ability of system from shock. (Priya Datta et al., 2007) not only included ability to maintain control but also adaptation and response. Over time, the element of anticipation as preparing plans to disruption added in the definition of SC resilience. (S. Y. Ponomarov & Holcomb, 2009) introduces the anticipation element first time in the SC resilience definition followed by (Ponis & Koronis, 2012) and (Day, 2014). Based on the aforementioned definitions of supply chain resilience, this research adopts the definition proposed by Ponomarov and Holcomb (2009).

3.3.3 Phases of SC Resilience

Company's performance can be affected by any significant disruption in an atypical profile. On the bases of above definitions, the nature of the disruption and company's response can be categorised into four major phases: Anticipation, Resistance, Recovery and Response and Growth (I. Ali et al., 2017; Kamalahmadi & Parast, 2016; Sheffi & Rice, 2005) as shown in the fig 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Phases of SC resilience

(Source: Author self)

(a). Anticipation

Anticipation phase refers to how supply chain stakeholders anticipate the occurrence of disruptive event and prepare their supply chains from any disturbance. The impact of unexpected event should be completely comprehended, and the probability of their occurrence must be curtailed (I. Ali et al., 2017; Kamalahmadi & Parast, 2016). In case of any emergency, a contingency plan should be on board.

(b). Resistance

This phase refers to confronting and deactivating the disturbance. As soon as any anticipated or unanticipated event is detected, the supply chain should resist and deactivate the perturbation and maintain its control over its structure and core functions (Kamalahmadi & Parast, 2016; Sheffi & Rice, 2005).

(c). Recovery and Response

This phase refers to supply chain's ability to respond quickly to mitigate the disruption and return to normal or stronger position (Pettit et al., 2013; Wieland & Wallenburg, 2013). A well-prepared response not only repositioned the firm to its pre-disruption position but can restore firm's status to a higher level (Kamalahmadi & Parast, 2016). A firm's ability to respond in shortest period is a unique source of competitive advantage (M. M. H. Chowdhury & Quaddus, 2017).

(d). Growth

The element of growth included in the definition of SC resilience over period (A. Ali et al., 2017). The opportunities after post-disruption phase emerges the idea of seeking growth. Growth is the most favourable state after an event to gain competitive advantage (I. Ali et al., 2017; Pettit et al., 2010; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015).

3.3.4 Complementary Aspects of Resilience in Food Supply Chains

Covid-19 has dramatically changed the current business environment and posed serious threats for food supply chains. Food supply chain is inefficient to cope with disruptions which caused abundant pre- and post-harvest food lost issues (Borrello et al., 2017; Managa et al., 2018). These disruptions could be internal or external, structural, or cyclic, sudden, or gradual can induce natural, political, economic, or social impacts on food supply chains. Additionally, population growth, urbanization, and growing demand for organic food further burgeoning pressure on agriculture sector. The complex interactions and consequences of disruptions on food supply chains has increase the importance of resilient in food system.

Resilience is a multidisciplinary and multidimensional concept. Food system is more complex than other systems and when we explore the role of resilience in food system it shows unique dimensions of resilience. Three major dimensions of food system resilience has been discussed in the literature: Sustainability, Food security and Food safety. The below sections will discuss each dimension of Food system resilience in context to FSCs as Food supply chains are an integral part of food system that provide food from farm to table.

(a). Sustainability

The notion sustainability originated from United Nations Work Commission on Environment and Development, and they define sustainability as "meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs". The concept of sustainability has gained more attention in recent years due to incorporation of sustainability in the key agendas of sustainable development goals (SDG) launched in 2015. Conceptualization, measurement, and evaluation of sustainability is still seen as a "wicked problem" (John J. Green et al., 2020). The sustainability of Agri food system is often defined in a static and normative way in reference to three classical pillars of sustainability such as environment, economic and social. Whereas resilience is defined in more dynamic perspective in terms of capability of a system to cope with disruption and stress. (Tendall et al., 2015)

stated sustainability as the capacity of a system to perform and resilience implies the capacity of system to continue during time of disruption. Consequently, resilience and sustainability are complementary concepts. Inversely resilience concerned short term ability of a system to withstand to disruption which is a key attribute of any organization to accomplish long term sustainability in ever changing complex environment, thus an organization cannot be sustainable without the refence of resilience (Stone & Rahimifard, 2018).

Mostly sustainability has been studied from environmental and strategic viewpoint only limited studies has been done from system resilience perspective (Murino et al., 2011). (John J. Green et al., 2020) developed sustainability/ resilience index for local food system, they measured the association of sustainable and resilient local food system through eight different dimensions as connectivity, local self-organization, innovation, accumulation, maintenance, transformation, diversity, and ecology integrity. Some studies emphasised the need to consider entire agri-food system to analyse sustainability and resilience of food system (Lamine, 2015; Tendall et al., 2015). (Himanen et al., 2016) used adaptive capacity model to analyse the relationship between food system actors and concluded that adaptive capacity can increase food system resilience but there is more empirical research is needed. Sustainable food supply chain needs to be resilient and agile. Therefore, resilience is an essential component for continuity of food supply chains and a key component of sustainable food supply chains.

(b). Food Security

Food security is described as the condition in which all individuals, at all times, had physical and economic access to adequate, safe, and nutritious food that satisfies their dietary requirements and preferences for an active and healthy lifestyle (FAO, 2019). The definition of food security emphasised on four dimensions of food security: 'Availability', 'Accessibility', 'Utilization' and 'Stability' (FAO 2022). Availability means in terms of quantity, quality, and safety to meet the physiological needs, by accessibility means physically and economically assessable and utilization underlines the ability of human body to digest it, utilization is only discussed from biological perspective. Stability is the fourth dimension of FS which is linked with the functional goal of food system resilience (Tendall et al., 2015) (FAO, 2024). (Stone & Rahimifard, 2018) linked the food related resilience by incorporating the stability fourth pillar of FS. Food system resilience is a dynamic concept and provision of food security over time is its aim. (Tendall et al., 2015) broke down food system resilience in to four different components; Robustness or capacity to withstand before any food security lost, Redundancy as capacity of system to absorb the disturbance and avoid food insecurity as much as possible, Flexibility in terms of ability of food system to recover from any food security loss, Adaptability and resourcefulness determines the amount of food security recovered after perturbations as shown in the fig 3.2. Improving food security requires improving resilience in food system. Food security is an essential element for the welfare of nations (Mwangi et al., 2022; Soussana, 2014) (Jaba Tkemaladze., 2025; Mona Haji, 2024)

(Source: Tendall et al, 2015)

Compared to other supply chains, food supply chains are particularly susceptible to high levels of uncertainty due to factors such as short product shelf life, natural disasters, climate change impacts, and food price volatility (Aziz et al., 2025; Shekarabi & Mozdgir, 2025). This situation is further aggravated by the outbreak of covid pandemic which shut down the whole world and increased the vulnerability of food supply chains. The repercussions of covid outbreak are enormous particularly in terms of food security. Hence the resilience in each stage of food supply chain from producer, processor, wholesaler, and retailer is vital in ensuring food security in terms of physically available, accessible (consumer can access it) and safe and reliable food for consumption (Stone & Rahimifard, 2018; Suweis et al., 2015).

(c). Food Safety

Provision of safe food to society has been a key subject on the agenda of researchers, food industry and policy makers. Presence of any kind of chemicals residues, viruses, bacteria, or parasite in food can cause food safety risks to human health. Due to consumption of contaminated food 600 million people (1 in every 10 persons) every year become sick (WHO., 2020). The complexity of global food supply chains, climate change and urbanization results in emergence of food safety hazards (Leat & Revoredo-Giha, 2013). The notion of resilience in the context of food safety is at its infancy. (W. Mu et al., 2021) defined resilience in the context of food safety is as "the food supply chain's ability to recover and adapt to shocks to food safety and enable the delivery of safe food over a reasonable lead time" and they highlight the building and maintaining resilience at each stage of food supply chain. Safety hazard at farm stage can produce safety shock at the later stages of supply chain. Therefore it is necessary to incorporate resilience in the full supply chain (Scherer et al., 2008). Food SC resilience to food safety shocks can be quantified by three factors: 1) time, 2) degree of impact and 3) degree of recovery as shown in the fig 3.3 (W. Mu et al., 2021).

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Figure 3.3 Resilience factors for quantifying of food SC resilience to food safety shocks

(Source: Nakov et al., 2019)

Time is the first factor to measuring resilience which further divided into three types i.e. incubation, detection, and recovery time. Incubation time is the period between emergence and the start of impact caused by food safety shock. The incubation time for plant/animal can be between infection and the moment clinical symptoms have appeared. At retailer level the period of incubation is between the arrival of unsafe food at retailer entry point and the safe supply capacity of retailer starts to decline. In this case if retailer can detect unsafe food with the help of detection technology upon their arrival, he can immediately replace the unsafe food with either from its own stocks or get new supply batch from supplier. Detection time refers to the duration between the occurrence of a food safety shock and its identification. At the retail level, this is the time between the arrival of an unsafe food product and its detection. Recovery time is defined as the period during which the shock is present, or the time taken to return to a pre-shock or new equilibrium state. For plants or animals, recovery time is the interval from infection to recovery. In contrast, at the retail level, recovery time is the duration between the onset of the shock and the point at which the business's supply capacity returns to normal.

The second factor for determining resilience is the degree of impact caused by shock. It can be range from symptom at animal level to the quantity food products removed from market at retail level. The third factor for measuring resilience is degree of recovery. Degree of recovery reflects the capacity to recover back to a stable state that can be lower equal or even better form pre shocked situation.

3.4 Circular Economy

Circular economy (CE) has garnered significant interest from academics, practitioners, and policymakers as a viable solution to the social, environmental, and economic challenges posed by today's competitive business environment (Govindan & Hasanagic, 2018; Jawahir & Bradley, 2016). The conventional linear economic model is facing serious difficulties from the changing socio-economic and regulatory landscape, resource price volatility, growing regulatory demands related to waste and greenhouse gas emissions, and the effects of climate change. In contrast, the circular economy (CE) maintains resources within a closed-loop supply chain. It transforms the conventional linear

economy of "take-make-consume-dispose" into a circular system that incorporates maintenance, reduction, reuse, remanufacturing, recycling, and recovery to ensure minimal or zero waste generation, as illustrated in Figure 3.4. This principle operates at all levels of the economy: the micro level (including products, companies, and consumers), the meso level (such as eco-industrial parks), and the macro level (encompassing cities, states, and countries) (Bernon et al., 2018) with the main goals of recycling and resource preservation.

Figure 3.4 Circular Economy

(Source: Khompatraporn 2020)

While the circular economy (CE) has attracted substantial interest as a strategy for achieving sustainable development and addressing the limitations of the linear “take-make-dispose” model (Govindan & Hasanagic, 2018; Jawahir & Bradley, 2016), the literature reveals significant complexities and criticisms surrounding its practical implementation. One key issue is the conceptual ambiguity of CE itself. Kirchherr et al. (2017), in a comprehensive review, found over 100 distinct definitions of CE, leading to inconsistent interpretations and applications across industries and regions. This lack of conceptual clarity creates difficulties in translating CE principles into measurable and actionable business strategies (Korhonen et al., 2018). Additionally, scholars highlight several practical and economic challenges (Chakraborty & Dey., 2025). For instance, implementing circular business models often requires high upfront investments, radical redesigns of products and supply chains, and significant organizational change, which many firms particularly small and medium-sized enterprises struggle to afford or manage (Merli et al., 2018; Ranta et al., 2018; Boskovic and Cullen., 2025); There are also technological and infrastructural barriers (Pittri et al., 2025; Rani et al., 2025), especially in emerging economies, where the lack of advanced recycling, remanufacturing, and reverse logistics capabilities limits the feasibility of closing resource loops (Kalmykova et al., 2018).

A further critical concern is the rebound effect, whereby efficiency improvements or circular initiatives lower costs or increase resource availability, paradoxically encouraging higher overall consumption and thus undermining the environmental benefits (Zink & Geyer, 2017) . This calls into question whether CE can truly achieve absolute decoupling of economic growth from environmental degradation, particularly given the pressures of global consumption trends (Korhonen et al., 2018). Moreover, some scholars argue that CE's focus on material loops can overlook broader sustainability dimensions, such as social equity and systemic environmental impacts beyond resource efficiency (Korhonen et al., 2018; Murray et al., 2017). There is also the challenge of measuring CE performance reliably and consistently (Pakuła et al., 2025). Although various metrics and assessment tools have been proposed, there is still no universally accepted framework for evaluating the environmental, economic, and social impacts of circular practices (Sassanelli et al., 2019).

3.4.1 CE Principles

The following five basic principles which form the foundation of the circular economy are explained:

(a). Design Out Waste

The principle of designing out waste emphasizes proactive planning to minimize environmental impact throughout a product's lifecycle. This approach advocates for intentional design, creating products with their end-of-life stage in mind. It involves ensuring that product parts align with either technical or biological cycles for easier processing post-use. The principle encourages incorporating biodegradable materials that can be safely composted without harmful effects, while also designing technical components (e.g., metals, alloys, and other man-made inputs) for efficient recycling with minimal energy use and maximum quality retention. By adopting this strategy, manufacturers can significantly reduce waste and improve the sustainability of their products, contributing to a more circular economy.

(b). Build Resilience Through Diversity

This principle draws a parallel between natural ecosystems and man-made systems, emphasizing the importance of diversity in creating resilient and durable structures. It suggests that systems with multiple connections and balanced components are better equipped to handle unexpected challenges compared to single-purpose systems. Natural systems demonstrate adaptability through a blend of diversity, consistency, and complexity, which enhances their resilience. (Braungart, 2019) endorses this view, highlighting how natural systems adapt to their environment through a continuous mix of these elements. The principle proposes that we can learn from and apply these natural models to improve our industrial and global systems, making them more robust and sustainable. By embracing diversity and complexity in our approach to the emerging industrial revolution and globalization, we can create more successful and enduring systems that mimic the resilience found in nature.

(c). Rely On Energy from Renewable Sources

The energy sources used in production processes play a crucial role in advancing the circular economy. Many industry leaders recognize the significance of renewable energy in fostering circularity. Vestas, a prominent wind energy company, emphasizes that prioritizing renewable energy in production

processes is fundamental to establishing a circular economy. This approach aligns with the circular economy's core principles of reducing waste and minimizing the consumption of finite resources. By focusing on renewable energy sources, companies can significantly contribute to the development of more sustainable and circular production systems, thereby reducing their environmental impact and promoting long-term resource efficiency.

(d). Think in 'Systems'

Systems thinking involves a holistic approach to understanding complex structures, focusing on the interrelationships between individual components and their collective behaviour. This perspective emphasizes that a system is more than just the sum of its parts; it's defined by the intricate web of connections and dependencies among its elements. The impact of each component on others, as well as the relationship between the whole system and its constituent parts, is crucial in comprehending the system's broader context. Systems are often characterized by their complexity and non-linear nature, where small changes in initial conditions, combined with feedback loops, can lead to unexpected and sometimes chaotic outcomes that may be disproportionate to the input. Rather than isolating individual components, systems thinking encourages a broader view that encompasses the flow of information, energy, or materials, and the long-term connectivity within the system. This approach provides a more comprehensive understanding of how systems function, evolve, and respond to changes over time.

(e). Waste is Food

In a circular economy, waste is viewed as an input for the next cycle or process, which is a fundamental concept on the biological input side and is relatively straightforward and well-established. However, on the technical side, maintaining the quality and managing the toxicity of waste presents challenges, though it is not impossible. This process is referred to as upcycling.

The idea of utilizing such inputs, which can be easily and feasibly reintroduced into the process after extracting valuable feedstock, embodies the core principles of a restorative circular economy.

3.4.2 Circular Economy Practices

Circular economy (CE) model implemented through specific actions and practices (Schroeder et al., 2019). These Circular Economy Practices (CEP) are typically conceptualized using "R" frameworks, ranging from the 3R model (reduce, reuse, and recycle) (Cui et al., 2024), to the 4R model (reduce, reuse, recycle, and recover) (Gebhardt et al., 2022), and even extending to a 9R framework (Potting et al., 2017).

The circular economy practices are implemented at three distinct levels, ranging from narrow to broad scope. Individual enterprise level: This is the most focused application, involving a single company or a small group of closely related enterprises. At this level, individual businesses implement circular economy practices within their own operations. Supply chain level: This broader application involves most businesses within a specific supply chain. At this level, companies collaborate and share resources to enhance collective efficiency. This approach allows for a more comprehensive implementation of circular economy principles across interconnected businesses. Macro or policy level: This is the

broadest application, involving government policies and regulations. At this level, circular economy practices are integrated into national or regional economic strategies, influencing entire industries and sectors. Government policies play a crucial role in shaping and promoting circular economy initiatives on a large scale (Mathews & Tan, 2011). CEP is believed to enhance sustainability by increasing the circulation of resources within supply chain systems, reducing the use of virgin materials, addressing resource scarcity issues, and extending product lifecycles (Velenturf & Purnell, 2021).

The literature highlights a connection between the constructs of Circular Economy (CE) practices and green supply chain management practices, both of which contribute to enhancing ecological sustainability (Genovese et al., 2017). Circular Economy (CE) is advocated at the organizational policy level to boost economic performance by tackling environmental and resource issues. In contrast, green supply chain management primarily focuses on improving environmental performance rather than financial performance (Belhadi et al., 2020). However, there is a strong correlation between the measures employed for Circular Economy (CE) practices and green supply chain management practices (Belhadi et al., 2020; Genovese et al., 2017). The initial measures for CE practices at the organizational level were established by (Q. Zhu et al., 2010). These measures have since been adopted and adapted in subsequent studies (Sousa-Zomer et al., 2018). (Edwin Cheng et al., 2022) used the measure developed by (Q. Zhu et al., 2010) and categorize them into three categories: management support (six items), eco-design (six items), and investment recovery (five items). (Govindan & Hasanagic, 2018) present a comprehensive framework for internal Circular Economy (CE) practices. They categorize these practices into six clusters based on their similarities and context. This includes Governance initiatives: implementing CE policies and establishing performance indicators. Economic initiatives: these aim to separate economic growth from environmental impact. Cleaner production: practices focused on increasing eco-efficiency. Product development: this involves designing for durability or reuse. Management support: refers to top management's endorsement and promotion of CE principles and Knowledge that encompasses CE education, training, and fostering creativity within the organization which was adopted by (Riggs et al., 2023). (T. T. Le et al., 2022) adopted a comprehensive scale originally developed by (Kuzma et al., 2021), (Hazen et al., 2020) and (Pizzi et al., 2022) to measure CE practices (CEP). The implemented practices exemplify typical Circular Economy (CE) strategies, such as transforming waste into production inputs, sharing resources, conserving energy, encouraging sourcing from the circular economy, adding value to products and materials, and generating valuable inputs for business partners within the supply chain.

3.5 Industry 4.0 Overview

Massive technological developments in history have played a vital role in triggering industrial revolutions. Mechanization of processes marked the first industrial revolution, the introduction of electrically powered mass production based on the division of labour marked the second revolution and automation of processes by incorporating electronics and computers marked the third revolution (Rijwani et al., 2025). The term "Industry 4.0" originated from the concept of the Fourth Industrial

Revolution, marking a new era in industrial development following the previous three industrial revolutions. It aims to create "smart factories" where physical production systems are connected to digital networks, enabling real-time data exchange and autonomous decision-making (Hossin et al., 2025; Malik et al., 2024; L. Da Xu et al., 2018). This integration allows for increased efficiency, flexibility, and customization in manufacturing processes. These revolutions have made manufacturing processes more complicate, automatic and sustainable by enabling a transformation of water and steam powered machines to fully automated production (Lass & Gronau, 2020; Vaidya et al., 2018). The implementation of Industry 4.0 principles is expected to lead to significant improvements in productivity, quality, and sustainability across various industrial sectors (Ghobakhloo, 2018; Hossin et al., 2025). However, it also presents challenges in terms of workforce adaptation, data security, and initial investment costs. Despite these challenges, Industry 4.0 is widely recognized as a crucial step in the evolution of industrial production, with the potential to revolutionize how goods are manufactured, and services are delivered (Rauch et al., 2019; Raut et al., 2019).

Figure 3.5 The Evolution from Industry 1.0 to Industry 4.0

(Source: Xu, 2018)

3.5.1 Overview of Basic Technologies of Industry 4.0

Industry 4.0 represents a comprehensive integration of advanced technologies, each with specific business applications that are transforming the industrial landscape (Erboz, 2017). The core technologies of Industry 4.0 are explained below:

Big Data Analytics: Big Data and Analytics play a crucial role in Industry 4.0 by enabling the collection, storage, and evaluation of massive amounts of data to support real-time decision-making in manufacturing and industrial processes (da Silva & Sehnem, 2025). This technology allows organizations to harness the power of vast data volumes to significantly enhance efficiency and productivity (Wamba et al., 2017). By leveraging advanced analytical tools and techniques, businesses can extract valuable insights from diverse data sources, including production equipment, supply chain operations, and customer interactions (Nneka Adaobi Ochuba et al., 2024). These insights drive

informed decision-making, allowing for rapid adjustments to production processes, predictive maintenance, and optimized resource allocation. The real-time nature of this data analysis enables manufacturers to respond swiftly to changing market conditions, identify potential issues before they escalate, and capitalize on emerging opportunities (Anjum et al., 2025). Ultimately, Big Data and Analytics in Industry 4.0 transform raw data into actionable intelligence, fostering agility, innovation, and competitive advantage in the modern industrial landscape (Ghobakhloo, 2018; Gilchrist, 2016; X.-Y. Wu et al., 2023).

Autonomous Robots: Robotics technology has become increasingly prevalent across a wide spectrum of industries, revolutionizing various sectors with its versatility and efficiency (Demetriou, 2011; Ming et al., 2025). In manufacturing, advanced robotic systems automate repetitive tasks, enhance precision, and increase productivity, enabling companies to stay competitive in a rapidly evolving market. The logistics and e-commerce industries have also embraced robotics, streamlining warehouse operations, improving inventory management, and accelerating order fulfilment processes (Rainer et al., 2025). Moreover, robotics is making inroads into the education sector, where interactive robots are used as teaching aids, engaging students and enhancing the learning experience. These examples underscore the transformative impact of robotics technology, which continues to expand its reach and applications, driving innovation and progress in diverse fields.

Cloud Technology: Cloud systems serve as remote storage repositories for massive volumes of data gathered from a wide array of business systems, devices, equipment, and sensors (Gharibvand et al., 2024). These cloud-based platforms offer a crucial advantage in the modern data-driven landscape: they enable instantaneous access to and retrieval of substantial data sets (Ghadge et al., 2020). This capability is particularly valuable in today's fast-paced business environment, where real-time information can be the key to making informed decisions and maintaining a competitive edge. By leveraging cloud technology, organizations can efficiently manage, process, and analyse vast amounts of information without the need for extensive on-site infrastructure (Vadisetty, 2024). This not only enhances operational flexibility but also facilitates seamless data sharing across different departments or geographical locations, fostering improved collaboration and decision-making processes throughout the organization (Oztemel & Gursev, 2020).

Internet of Things (IOT): In Industry 4.0, the Internet of Things (IoT) platform serves as a central nervous system, orchestrating communication and interaction among diverse equipment and systems (Aouedi et al., 2025; Thilakarathne et al., 2025). This sophisticated network acts as a hub, facilitating seamless data exchange and coordination across the entire industrial ecosystem (Gunasekaran et al., 2015). One of the key advantages of IoT is its ability to provide real-time traceability and tracking capabilities, offering unprecedented visibility into operations at every stage. Moreover, the IoT architecture supports decentralized analytics and decision-making processes, allowing for rapid, data-driven responses at the point of need (Hosny et al., 2025; X. Mu & Antwi-Afari, 2024). This distributed intelligence enables more agile and efficient operations, as decisions can be made autonomously by

smart devices and systems based on local conditions and predefined parameters. By combining centralized control with decentralized execution, IoT empowers industries to achieve higher levels of productivity, flexibility, and responsiveness in their operations (Manavalan & Jayakrishna, 2019).

Additive Manufacturing and 3D Printing: Additive Manufacturing, also known as 3D Printing, refers to the production of customised goods tailored to the specific requirements of customers (Erboz, 2017). As Industry 4.0 continues to evolve, these innovative manufacturing methods are expected to become increasingly prevalent, particularly in the production of small-batch, customized items (L. Zhou et al., 2024). This shift enables manufacturers to offer tailor-made products that cater to specific customer needs or niche markets (Ghadge et al., 2020; Hossain et al., 2025).

Augmented Reality/ Virtual reality (VR)/ Extended reality (XR): Augmented reality is an interactive technology that blends digital elements with the real world, allowing users to experience virtual content as part of their physical environment (Erboz, 2017). A range of services can be facilitated through augmented-reality-based systems, including designing layouts for warehouses or production lines and transmitting repair instructions via mobile or other remote-control devices (Vaidya et al., 2018). Virtual reality (VR) and virtual environments (VE) are terms frequently used synonymously to refer to computer-generated spaces that allow users to interact via different interfaces (Bayro & Jeong, 2025). Extended reality (XR) encompasses the fusion of real and virtual environments, enabling human-machine interaction through computer-generated experiences supported by technology and hardware (Doolani et al., 2020).

Artificial Intelligence: Artificial intelligence (AI) are terms used to describe a machine's capacity for intelligent learning and behaviour (Jiang et al., 2022). These technologies can make decisions, perform tasks, and even predict future outcomes based on insights gained from data. AI involves applying algorithms to data to solve problems, identify patterns, determine subsequent actions, and potentially forecast future results (S. A. R. Khan et al., 2021; C. Zhang & Lu, 2021; Y. Zhang et al., 2025). A key aspect of this process is the ability to learn from data, improving the interpretation of that data over time. This is where machine learning, a subfield of AI, comes into play (Messeri & Crockett, 2024).

Most modern devices are equipped with multiple communication interfaces, such as 4G, 5G, 6G, and WiFi. They typically use one or more of these available options for data transmission (Islam et al., 2025). 5G communication technologies provide various essential advantages, such as ultra-high system capacity, ultra-low latency, improved security, extensive device connection, reduced energy consumption, and superior quality of experience (Qiao et al., 2021; Salahdine et al., 2023). The introduction of the 6G communication system is expected to occur between 2027 and 2030 (M. Z. Chowdhury et al., 2020). This new will arise from an unprecedented wave of innovative applications and technological trends that will influence its performance goals and significantly transform standard 5G services.

Blockchain: Blockchain represents one of the key advanced technologies within Industry 4.0. Further details are provided in the following sections.

Among the various Industry 4.0 technologies introduced earlier, this research chooses to focus specifically on blockchain technology. The reason for selecting blockchain is closely tied to the main goals of the study. The research question seeks to understand how certain supply chain capabilities specifically agility, collaboration, and traceability contribute to important outcomes such as supply chain resilience, circular economy practices, and ultimately sustainable supply chain performance. An overview of blockchain technology will be provided first, followed by a detailed discussion of the rationale in relation to each of these variables in the subsequent sections.

3.5.2 Blockchain Technology (BCT) Overview

Blockchain is an advanced, decentralized, and distributed technology that guarantees the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of all transactions and data/information (Vazquez Melendez et al., 2024). It operates as a shared, transparent, and distributed ledger that facilitates the storage and recording of data/information and transactions, supported by cryptographic value (Choi & Siqin, 2022) across a peer-to-peer network (Chang, Chen Lu, 2019; Choi & Siqin, 2022).

Blockchain technology offers an innovative method for managing digital records. Fundamentally, it functions as a decentralized and distributed ledger, designed to be resistant to changes and to quickly identify any attempts at tampering (Rajasekaran et al., 2022). Unlike traditional systems, blockchains typically operate without a central controlling entity, such as a financial institution, corporation, or governmental body (Yaga et al., 2019).

The primary goal of blockchain is to enable participants to collaboratively maintain a common record of transactions. The system is designed to ensure that, under normal conditions, the recorded data/information remains permanent. After a transaction is added, it becomes nearly impossible to alter or delete, preserving both the integrity and transparency of the ledger (Yaga et al., 2019).

Blockchains can be informally defined as:

Blockchain technology is built on distributed ledgers that store cryptographically signed transactions, arranged in blocks (Rajasekaran et al., 2022). Each block is connected to the previous one, making any tampering immediately noticeable. After consensus validation, new blocks are added, and older blocks become increasingly difficult to change, enhancing resistance to tampering. These blocks are replicated throughout the network, with discrepancies resolved automatically through pre-defined rules (Z. Zheng et al., 2017). Key attributes of blockchain technology by (Habib et al., 2022; Rajasekaran et al., 2022; Ressi et al., 2024; Sarmah, 2018; Tripathi et al., 2023; Yaga et al., 2019) explained below:

- **Ledger** – The technology employs an append-only ledger to keep a complete record of all transactions. Unlike traditional databases, blockchain adds new transactions without overwriting existing data/Information, preserving the full history.
- **Secure** – blockchains are cryptographically secure, the ledger's contents are protected from tampering and can be verified, ensuring data integrity.
- **Shared** – The ledger is shared among multiple participants, allowing for open visibility across the network.

- **Decentralization** – By distributing the blockchain across many nodes, the system becomes more resilient to attacks and manipulation
- **Smart contracts:** Business rules and conditions can be embedded directly into the blockchain, automating transactions.
- **Consensus mechanisms:** Relevant users validate transactions, ensuring data/information immutability and traceability.

3.5.2.1 Blockchain Categorization

Blockchain systems can be classified based on their access control model, which defines who has the authority to manage and maintain the network. There are two main categories of blockchains based on this criterion permissionless and permissioned (Habib et al., 2022; Sarmah, 2018; Zheng et al., 2017).

(a). Permissionless

Open blockchain networks, also known as permissionless blockchains, are distributed ledger systems that allow any participant to add blocks without requiring approval from a central authority. These platforms are typically built on open-source software, which is freely accessible to everyone who wants to download and use it.

(b). Permissioned

permissioned blockchain networks operate under a controlled access model where users must obtain authorization from a governing body before publishing blocks. This controlled environment allows for greater flexibility in managing access rights. Network administrators can implement restrictions on both read access and transaction submission. As a result, permissioned blockchains can be configured in various ways: they may allow public read access while restricting block creation, limit both read access and block creation to authorized participants only, permit anyone to submit transactions but restrict who can add them to the blockchain, or confine all aspects - reading, transacting, and block creation - to a select group of authorized users. This approach offers more control over the network's operations and participant activities compared to permissionless systems.

3.5.2.2 Blockchain Elements

Blockchain technology may appear complex, it can be made more understandable by breaking it down into its individual components (Sheth & Dattani, 2019.; Komalavalli et al., 2020; Sarmah, 2018; Trivedi et al., 2024) .

(a). Cryptographic Hash Functions

Hashing is a technique that employs a cryptographic hash function to transform data/information into a unique output referred to as a message digest (or just a digest), applicable to inputs of virtually any size, including files, text, or images.

(b). Transactions

The engagement of two or more parties is denoted by the term "*transaction*." Although the data/information that is contained in a transaction may differ from one blockchain implementation to another, the method that is used to execute transactions is, for the most part, constant across all

blockchain implementations. When a participant in the blockchain network submits data/information it may encompass the sender's address (or another relevant identity), the sender's public key, a digital signature, along with the inputs and outputs of the transaction.

(c). Asymmetric-Key Cryptography

Cryptography that uses asymmetric keys employs a pair of keys—specifically, a public key and a private key that are mathematically linked to each other. While the private key must be kept secret to preserve the cryptographic protection of the data/Information, the public key can be freely distributed without jeopardising the integrity of the system's security.

- As a summary, the following is an explanation of how asymmetric-key cryptography is utilised in different blockchain networks:
- To digitally signing transactions, private keys are utilised.
- To generate addresses, public keys are utilised.
- The use of public keys allows for the verification of signatures that were generated using private keys.
- Asymmetric-key cryptography enables the verification that the individual transferring value possesses the private key necessary to sign the transaction.

(d). Addresses and Address Derivation

An *address* is a compact sequence of alphanumeric characters derived from a user's public key using a cryptographic hash function. Additionally, certain blockchain networks utilize an address, which is accompanied by some extra information (such as a version number and checksums). In comparison to public keys, addresses are more concise and do not conceal any information. Creating a public key, using a cryptographic hash function to it, and then turning resultant hash into text is one method for generating an address. Another method includes transforming the hash into text:

Public key → Cryptographic hash function → Address

Addresses act as the public identifier for users in a blockchain network and are often converted into a QR code (Quick Response Code), a two-dimensional barcode that can store various types of data, making it more convenient for use with mobile devices.

Figure 3.6 A QR code example

(e). Ledgers

A *ledger* is a record of transactions that have been recorded. Throughout the course of human history, ledgers made of pen and paper have been utilised to record the transactions of commodities and services. Today, ledgers are often maintained digitally in large databases managed by a centralized, trusted third party (typically the ledger owner) for the benefit of a user community. In order to organise these centralised ledgers, they may be organised in either a centralised fashion (by utilising a single server) or in a dispersed manner (by utilising a cluster of computers that coordinates activities).

(f). Blocks

Blockchain network users rely on various software tools, such as desktop applications, mobile apps, digital wallets, and online services, to submit candidate transactions to the network. Transactions are added to the blockchain whenever a publishing node creates and broadcasts a block. Each block consists of two main parts: the block header and the block data/information. It is essential to keep in mind that every blockchain implementation has the ability to create its own data/information fields; nonetheless, the majority of blockchains now employ fields that are quite similar to one another, such as following:

Block Header

- The block number, often referred to as block height in certain blockchain networks.
- The hash value of the previous block header.
- A hash representation of the block data, which can be generated using different methods, such as creating a Merkle tree and storing the root hash, or by hashing all the combined block data.
- A timestamp indicating when the block was created.
- The block size.
- The nonce value. In blockchain networks that make use of mining, this is a number that is modified by the publishing node in order to solve the hash problem. When it comes to blockchain networks, other networks might or might not contain a nonce, or they might utilise it for purposes apart from addressing a hash problem.

Block Data

- A list of transactions and ledger events contained within the block.
- Additional data/information may also be included.

(g). Chaining Blocks

Blocks are linked by incorporating the hash digest of the preceding block's header into each new block, thus creating the blockchain. Any modification to a previously published block will produce a different hash. This alteration will subsequently impact all subsequent blocks since they depend on the hash of the preceding block.

(Source: Trivedi et al. 2024)

3.5.3 Blockchain Technology and Supply Chains

The supply chain is a complex network made up of multiple organisational processes and interrelationships (Pettit et al., 2013), where each entity interacts with its business partners through distinct channels (Lambert & Enz, 2017; Madhani, 2021). Blockchain can be leveraged for the benefit of the entire network, fostering greater trust, transparency, traceability, collaboration, agility, security, decartelization, and coordination among stakeholders (S. E. Chang et al., 2019; Pattanayak et al., 2024; Surucu-Balci et al., 2024; Vázquez Meléndez et al., 2025; Younis et al., 2024). The agricultural SC developed today is extremely complex with many stakeholders involved and hence needs to be digitized and improved with blockchain. The current traceability system in place has the risks of data tampering. Blockchain implemented on a double chain structure helps increase openness and security of transactions, privacy of enterprise information and can achieve proper resource allocation among all stakeholders in the agriculture sector. It also enhances the overall efficiency of the system, eases business expansion, increases throughput and credibility of the related platforms. Blockchain and IoT based solutions are being used to deal with the trust issues that customers are having in the organic product SCs (Y. Zhang et al., 2025). Along with efficiency and product tracking, it also helps to maintain a fair relationship between the small farmers and big buyers and democratize the supply process (Kshetri, 2018; Mondal & Chakraborty, 2025). Food suffers from adulteration and tampering on a large scale. Using blockchain can solve this problem by facilitating the end-to-end traceability (Behnke & Janssen, 2020). An enterprise level smart contract helps to resolve the sensitive information disclosure, data tampering, transfer of trust and need of trusted intermediary issue with the help of proven authenticity and identity (Salah et al., 2019). Furthermore, to reduce the problem of data explosion, a collaborative approach of “on chain and off chain” management of data/information is utilized so that a single node is not overloaded with data/information. Blockchain DLT technique can be used to securely link all the actors of the entire food SC from the source to the consumers which can help eliminate food adulteration, ensure high resolution of food safety issues, improve management of quality issues and reduce the social chaos caused by uncoordinated issues thereby increasing the sustainability (Bumblauskas et al., 2020; S. Kamble et al., 2019; S. S. Kamble et al., 2020; Kshetri, 2018).

Blockchain technology is revolutionizing food supply chain operations by enhancing traceability, transparency, and efficiency. Major companies are leveraging this technology to improve their processes. For instance, Nestlé has partnered with IBM Food Trust to trace products like Mousline purée and Zoégas coffee (Daley, S, 2023). This initiative allows consumers to scan QR codes to access detailed information about the products' journeys from farm to store, including the origins of coffee beans sourced from South America, certified by The Rainforest Alliance. Walmart has also made significant strides in food traceability through its use of the Hyperledger Fabric platform (Bolale & Laourou, 2025; Rejeb & Rejeb, 2020). This system enables Walmart to trace the origin of over 25 products from five different suppliers (Kamath, 2018). Notably, the company can now trace U.S. mangoes in just 2.2 seconds, a remarkable improvement from the previous seven-day process. Additionally, Walmart is expanding its blockchain requirements to all suppliers of fresh leafy greens, further enhancing food safety measures (Collart & Canales, 2022; Zara, 2025). Other companies are following suit; for example, Kezzler's traceability platform integrates with blockchain to share product information across the supply chain. Ripe.io employs blockchain-backed IoT and AI technologies to automate farming and provide real-time food tracking. Furthermore, Bumblebee Foods and Kraft Heinz utilize blockchain for product traceability, while retailers like Carrefour, JD.com, Albert Heijn, and Auchan track items such as meat, dairy, fruits, and beverages (Haskell, S, 2022; Rijmenam, M.V, 2019). This widespread adoption of blockchain not only ensures transparency but also helps deter fraud within the food supply chain.

3.5.4 Block Chain Technology and Supply Chain Resilience

BCT in the SC can be seen as an instrument capable of providing SCRES, or SC resilience (Petit et al., 2019). Regarding supply chain resilience, a common mitigation strategy is to create redundancy in the supply chain structure (Ivanov, 2018; Scholten & Schilder, 2015; Tan, 2002) but this is often a costly decision (Chunsheng et al., 2019). This condition could be mitigated in a food supply chain through the use of blockchain technology (BCT), which can enhance visibility and coordination and reduce the need for physical redundancy (Saber et al., 2018; Vern et al., 2025). The presence of risks, or even the perception of instability within the supply chain, can create uncertain conditions and undermine decision-making processes. Shared visibility among supply chain actors offers valuable support in managing such risks by enabling timely and informed responses. The high degree of interconnection within food supply chains (FSCs) makes them particularly vulnerable to cascading disruptions if any individual link is unable to cope with a crisis (A. Chang et al., 2022). In this context, blockchain-enabled food supply chains (BCT-FSC) provide enhanced visibility that allows supply chain agents to proactively identify and mitigate potential disruptions, failures, or risks associated with specific trading partners (Chiaraluce et al., 2024; Min, 2019; Pakseresht et al., 2024). However, this visibility is primarily limited to commercial transactions and supply flows within the FSC and does not typically extend to external events such as natural disasters, regulatory interventions, or legal challenges.

Managing unexpected interruptions in food supply chains (FSCs) presents significant challenges; however, it is possible to reduce the impact of such disruptions through proactive strategies (Ivanov et al., 2015). Enhancing supply chain resilience (SCRES) can be achieved by unifying suppliers through strategic alliances, reducing delivery times, and systematising information to provide visibility of inventory levels for all supply chain (Shashi et al., 2020). These capabilities can be supported and facilitated by blockchain technology (BCT), which offers enhanced transparency and real-time information sharing among stakeholders (Fiore & Mongiello, 2023). For instance, BCT enables supply chain agents to gain visibility into critical operational data (Ordoñez et al., 2024; Peng et al., 2023). During crises, having insight into changes in demand is crucial for effective management, as greater volatility in the post-disruption period can significantly affect operational performance and disrupt inventory dynamics (Peng et al., 2023).

The increased visibility in the FSC helps the members of the SC to collaborate, as it favours the exchange of information and greater transparency, generating reliability (Peng et al., 2023). Clarity is achieved through existing connectivity (N. Kumar et al., 2019). Connectivity is related to the behaviour of people being united in times of crisis. Greater unification and better connectivity allow members of the SC to have the relevant information on critical aspects of the chain. This is because the more connected the SC members are, the more effectively the SC will be able to respond to the changes that arise (Bevilacqua et al., 2019; Y. K. Sharma et al., 2019). FSC connectivity depends on the quality of information sharing; it can be understood as a technological resource that facilitates information sharing. On the other hand, information sharing can be seen as organisational capital, a resource derived from the flow of information. In this sense, by investing in technological resources capable of innovating and improving its capacities, the organisation increases its ability to manage its risks (Wong et al., 2011).

Food products can be tracked and traced with the help of real-time information throughout the system that enhances the SC resilience (Pakseresht et al., 2024; Stone & Rahimifard, 2018; Tendall et al., 2015). Velocity is closely linked to flexibility, as the speed at which a supply chain can adapt to disruptions is a critical factor in maintaining operational continuity. Blockchain technology (BCT) can significantly enhance this velocity by accelerating the detection and response to supply chain disruptions (Sultan, 2025). Agility is highly influenced by collaboration, integration, and communication through BCT (Li et al., 2022; Pattanayak et al., 2024). The relationship between disruption and risks during pandemic and adoption of resilient FSCs facilitated by BC-T is exhibited.

3.5.5 Block Chain Technology and Circular Economy

Blockchain and the circular economy (CE) are two emerging concepts whose interconnections offer significant potential benefits (Bhatia & Gangwani, 2025; Bhatti & Nawaz, 2020; J. L. Schmidt et al., 2024). The CE focuses on minimising negative externalities generated by organisations, which arise from the processes of producing, using, and disposing of goods and materials throughout their life cycles (Fernandez de Arroyabe et al., 2021). In this context, blockchain technology, as a decentralised protocol

that enables the secure sharing and updating of information across distributed ledgers or databases, can play a pivotal role in supporting the formalisation and implementation of the CE's regenerative and restorative principles (Mukherjee et al., 2025) .

Therefore, that the adoption of blockchain technology can serve as a significant catalyst in accelerating organisational transitions towards the circular economy (CE). By reducing transaction costs and enabling optimal levels of operational performance and communication, blockchain technology addresses crucial needs across complex supply chains (T. Zhang et al., 2025) . It empowers each link in the supply chain by providing access to detailed, verifiable information regarding materials, emissions, and other sustainability indicators, while simultaneously enhancing data/information confidentiality and contributing to a reduction in the overall carbon footprint (Rodrigues et al., 2021) . While comprehensive recording of supply chain information is indispensable for vendors and manufacturers, blockchain's significance for consumers is equally critical (Vázquez Meléndez et al., 2025) . Today's consumers, increasingly driven by sustainability considerations, demand transparency and verification of sustainable practices to inform and justify their purchasing decisions (Duong et al., 2025). Transparent and clearly defined sustainability policies, supported by blockchain's immutable records, can thus serve as powerful incentives for responsible consumption. In this context, blockchain technology facilitates communication of the precise origin of materials and provides consumers with assurance that products have been produced in accordance with parameters defined under circular economy principles and broader environmental standards (Vazquez Melendez et al., 2024) .

Blockchain offers a promising framework to support the core objectives of the CE (R. Sharma et al., 2025) , contributing not only to resource efficiency and waste reduction but also to enhanced traceability and accountability throughout the value chain. Its inherent characteristics of decentralisation, immutability, and transparency can promote a new paradigm of ethical and socially responsible business practices. Consequently, blockchain technology has the potential to foster a transformative shift towards more sustainable and ethically grounded supply chains, reinforcing both environmental objectives and societal trust in the integrity of organisational practices (Giganti et al., 2024) .

3.5.6 Block Chain Technology and Supply Chain Sustainability

Today, the need to transform production systems toward sustainability is increasingly driven by institutional forces, such as the European Green Deal (Giganti et al., 2024) and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations, 2015). These initiatives advocate for sustainability through comprehensive frameworks and regulations designed to balance economic, environmental, and social dimensions. This growing emphasis on sustainable production has significantly reshaped managerial approaches to sustainability. Unlike earlier views that treated sustainability efforts purely as costs, recent research points to a major paradigm shift, framing sustainability as a strategic advantage rather than a financial burden (Hermundsdottir & Aspelund, 2022) .

Blockchain technology (BT) is recognised as a major disruptive force capable of fundamentally reshaping visibility, integration, and sustainability (Korpela et al., 2017). Blockchain technology (BT) can greatly enhance supply chain (SC) sustainability. One approach involves visualising data/information and closely examining detailed processes to identify and eliminate waste. Data security is also crucial in this context. Since information on the blockchain cannot be modified without the approval of SC participants, BT helps prevent unethical actions by governments, organisations, or associations attempting to unjustly control individuals' resources. Moreover, BT can deter corrupt actors and hold dishonest individuals accountable for social and personal misconduct (Elias Mota et al., 2020; S. A. Khan et al., 2022; M. Mubarik et al., 2021; Saberi et al., 2018). Blockchain has the potential to significantly improve operational efficiency, streamline resource allocation, and release resources that can help mitigate fluctuations in supply chain demand and supply (J. L. Schmidt et al., 2024). Blockchain's ability to provide costless verification offers advantages to all participants in the supply chain by reducing or eliminating expenses linked to product and ingredient certification (dos Santos et al., 2019). Consequently, supply chain partners can achieve substantial cost savings related to enforcement activities, including labour costs, legal fees, taxes, and court expenses, thereby contributing to economic sustainability (Rejeb & Rejeb, 2020). Blockchain technology serves as a crucial basis for fostering cooperative and collaborative relationships within supply chains. It builds trust through ensuring data integrity, security, and protection against fraud, violations, and cyberattacks (Modic et al., 2019). As a result, blockchain supports the development of a new ecosystem characterised by shared goals and policies, robust regulations and control systems, reputation-building, and strong relationships all of which contribute to enhancing a firm's social capital, particularly trust, thereby promoting social sustainability (Rejeb et al., 2020). Blockchain contributes to environmental sustainability by promoting more efficient and sustainable energy use and supporting the production of eco-friendly products. Its transparency allows verification that products labeled as green genuinely meet environmental standards (Saberi et al., 2019).

3.6 Sustainable Supply Chain Management

Sustainability is a multifaceted concept with diverse and broad applications across various fields and contexts. (Faber et al., 2005; Saruchera, 2025; Leone, 2024) discovered a wide range of sustainability definitions in academic literature spanning several decades of research. The idea of sustainability dates back to 1972 when Schumacher introduced the idea of "permanence". According to Schumacher, economic viability is contingent upon long-term feasibility without leading to logical inconsistencies or impracticalities. The World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) established a seminal definition of sustainability in their 1987 report, "Our Common Future," also known as the Brundtland Report. Based on this definition, sustainability refers to development that fulfils current needs without jeopardizing the capacity of future generations to satisfy their own requirements.

(Elkington & Fennell, 1998) triple bottom line concept brings sustainability down to the microeconomic level, providing a framework for organizations to address economic, environmental,

and social issues in their operations. This approach allows businesses to evaluate their performance and impact across these three interconnected dimensions, moving beyond a sole focus on financial metrics. It integrates three key dimensions: social, environmental, and economic concerns. This holistic approach, is referred to as the "triple bottom line" or "three pillars of sustainability," recognizes that true sustainable development must balance and address issues across all these areas simultaneously. This expanded understanding of sustainability acknowledges that long-term progress requires not just economic viability but as well as social equity and environmental stewardship (Sala, 2020). It emphasizes the interconnectedness of these factors and the need for integrated solutions that consider the complex relationships between human societies, economic systems, and the natural environment (Nogueira, 2022).

The growing emphasis on sustainable practices is driven by two main factors: increasingly stringent regulations and heightened public awareness. As a result, the pursuit of sustainable development has become an imperative for businesses rather than an optional strategy (Fabbe-Costes et al., 2014). (Linton et al., 2007; Mahajan, et al., 2024; Falcone & Tutore, 2025) stated that supply chain management covers the complete lifecycle of a product, starting from its inception ("cradle") to its eventual disposal ("grave"). This comprehensive perspective to supply chain management presents a significant opportunity for advancing sustainability efforts. According to (Gimenez et al., 2012; Mahmood, et al., 2024) in the context of supply chain management economic sustainability pertains to the costs associated with production or manufacturing. Environmental sustainability focuses on minimizing waste, pollution, energy consumption, emissions, and the use of hazardous or toxic materials, as well as reducing the frequency of environmental incidents (Akano, et al., 2024). Social sustainability encompasses both internal stakeholders, such as employees, and external parties (Muralidhar, et al., 2024). It aims to ensure fair opportunities, embrace diversity, promote independence throughout the supply chain, enhance quality of life, foster a democratic environment, and establish trustworthy organizational structures. (Teuteberg & Wittstruck, 2010) introduced the concept of the "House of Sustainable Supply Chain," which is founded on the three core pillars of the Triple Bottom Line framework. These dimensions economic, environmental, and social are considered the fundamental pillars of sustainable supply chain management. This model visualizes sustainable supply chain management as a structure, with the Triple Bottom Line dimensions forming the essential foundation. Using the metaphor of the "House of Sustainable Supply Chain Management" (see Fig. 3-8), (Teuteberg & Wittstruck, 2010) illustrated how sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) is structured around the triple bottom line, consisting of economic, environmental, and social dimensions. These three dimensions are depicted as pillars that support the house, symbolising their essential role in maintaining balance and stability within the supply chain system. The foundation of the house represents risk and compliance management, highlighting the importance of identifying and mitigating risks, as well as adhering to laws, guidelines, and standards. This structure reflects how the

interconnected and interdependent elements work together to achieve long-term sustainability and profitability in supply chains.

Figure 3.8 House of SSCM

(Source: Adopted from Teuteberg and Wittstruck, 2010)

Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM) is recognized as an emerging and evolving branch within the broader field of Supply Chain Management (SCM) (Ashby et al., 2012; Rajeev, et al., 2017). (Seuring & Müller, 2008) offered a comprehensive definition of SSCM: SSCM encompasses the overseeing of material, Information, and capital flows, along with inter-company collaboration throughout the supply chain. It incorporates objectives from all three aspects of sustainable development economic, environmental, and social based on the needs of customers and stakeholders. Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM) involves the bilateral flow of both tangible and intangible resources and incorporates the three dimensions of sustainability. This approach evaluates all stakeholders within an organization and addresses environmental complexities for corporations (Beske, 2012; Petrescu, et al., 2025). In sustainable supply chain management (SSCM), social performance focuses on non-environmental aspects, emphasizing consumers, stakeholders, and employees. Economic performance pertains to the financial profitability of the supply chain, while environmental performance involves compliance with regulatory standards (Ji et al., 2014; Roffé & González, 2024).

According to (S. Gupta & Palsule-Desai, 2011; Alqahtani, et al., 2025; Ahmad & Khokhar, 2024), SSCM includes a range of management practices that require taking environmental impacts into account. These practices guide the supply chain process based on the value chain of commodities and a multi-dimensional perspective that influences the product life cycle. (Tsai et al., 2021) asserted that a truly sustainable supply chain should be comprehensively considered, encompassing all inputs from suppliers to production centres to customers, while driving social and environmental improvements throughout the entire chain. Historically, the focus was primarily on production and logistics systems, tracing the flow from raw materials to end consumers. However, the contemporary approach has

evolved to incorporate environmental considerations to address sustainability challenges (Zailani et al., 2012; Roffé & González, 2024).

3.6.1 Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

The sustainable performance of a supply chain refers to the outcomes achieved through the implementation of sustainable development practices (Lebas, 1995). This concept emphasizes that the general effectiveness of a supply chain should be evaluated not only in terms of traditional metrics such as cost and efficiency but also considering its sustainability impacts. (Mangla et al., 2020) argued that the assessment of supply chain performance has evolved beyond the conventional metrics of efficiency, effectiveness, and economy. This perspective suggests a more comprehensive approach to evaluating supply chain performance, one that incorporates additional dimensions beyond these traditional measures. In response to increasing demands from both governmental bodies and various stakeholders, supply chains are now compelled to embrace a more holistic approach to performance evaluation. This approach necessitates the simultaneous coordination of ecological, economic, and social sustainability metrics (Mangla et al., 2020). (Govindan et al., 2013) introduced an innovative approach to assessing supply chain sustainability performance using a fuzzy multi-criteria methodology. Their study focused on assessing performance from the perspective of the triple bottom line (TBL) framework, that encompasses the social, economic, and environmental dimensions of business operations. (Slaper & Hall, 2011) defined the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) as an expanded accounting framework that goes beyond traditional financial measures to include social and environmental dimensions of performance. Companies can enhance their overall supply chain efficiency, responsiveness, and sustainability, leading to improved competitive advantage in the long run by implementing appropriate performance measures. Thus, it is crucial for performance measurement systems to encompass all three dimensions of sustainability economic, social, and environmental—without focusing on economic performance rather than social and environmental impacts (Pagell & Shevchenko, 2014). Environmental sustainability performance involves minimizing the consumption of natural resources, including materials, water, energy, and atmospheric elements, among others. Whereas, minimizing the supply chain's carbon footprint is a significant concern, it is important to recognize that suppliers' decisions have broader implications for resource use in general. Furthermore, assessing the effects of human and economic activities on raw material sources across the entire supply chain is vital. (Yusuf et al., 2013) referred to this concept as the preservation of limited resources needed to meet human needs. Additionally, waste, including external waste, imposes internal costs (Sarkis et al., 2011). Even without legal obligations, the inefficient use of materials, water, and energy, along with the disregard for greenhouse gas emissions, not only harms the environment but also contributes to climate change. The shifting climate is expected to heighten the susceptibility of global supply chains, compelling manufacturers to decrease their greenhouse gas emissions. There is widespread consensus that the climate is changing, and additional adjustments are unavoidable unless there are significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions. This includes gases such as hydrofluorocarbons, perfluorocarbons, sulfur

hexafluoride, carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide. The many repercussions of a warming climate have increased attention on environmental performance. This encompasses several factors, including reduced air emissions, less material consumption, improved energy efficiency, decreased release of solid and hazardous waste, and diminished consumption of natural resources, among others (Paulraj et al., 2017; Q. Zhu et al., 2008, 2013; Q. Zhu & Sarkis, 2004).

The literature has emphasized the importance of social sustainability performance (Beske-Janssen et al., 2015; P. H. Walker et al., 2014). Social performance acts as a means to achieve both environmental and economic sustainability goal (Yusuf et al., 2013). (Chen et al., 2017) Social performance can be divided into two main categories: social capital and human capital. Social capital emphasizes honouring the rights of communities where resources are located, enhancing individuals' quality of life without harming the environment, and avoiding the overexploitation of resources (Chin et al., 2015; Yusuf et al., 2013). This also includes guaranteeing humane working conditions at supplier facilities, treating customers fairly (which encompasses product and process safety), and making social investments in the communities where suppliers operate (Krause et al., 2009; Sarkis et al., 2010). Conversely, human capital emphasizes the importance of providing humane working conditions at suppliers' facilities, ensuring fair treatment of customers (including product and process safety), and investing socially in the communities (Carter & Rogers, 2008; Jennings, 2013; Krause et al., 2009; Porter & Kramer, 2006). Economic performance emphasizes on expansion of sales and improving profit margins. An important element of this is understanding how social and environmental initiatives can affect sales volume and enhance consumer contentment. Research shows a positive relationship between sustainability factors and sales growth (Sarkis, Zhu, and Lai, 2011). For example, Paulraj, Chen, and Blome (2017) illustrate that sustainable supply chain practices can enhance economic performance indicators, including profit margins, return on assets, and market share. These improvements often stem from resource efficiency, where products are designed to use fewer materials and less energy.

3.7 Effect of SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on SC Resilience

In supply chain management domain planning and carrying out various management operations is a difficult endeavour that necessitates good coordination of material, social, financial, and informational flows across organisational boundaries. Each of the business processes carries its own set of vulnerabilities and risks (Mentzer et al., 2008). They are commonly expressed as supply chain disruptions, which can take many forms, such transportation delays, port shutdowns, accidents and natural catastrophes, quality and operational concerns, and acts of terrorism, among others (Blackhurst et al., 2005; Mitroff & Alpaslan, 2003). Due to widespread disruptions, supply chain managers must be proactive in terms of event readiness and disruption susceptibility (Christopher & Peck, 2004; Jüttner & Maklan, 2011; Pettit et al., 2013). To deal with the complexities and avoid the vulnerabilities in the current dynamic business climate, SC resilience has gained greater significance in supply chain management. According to (M. M. H. Chowdhury & Quaddus, 2017) SC resilience is defined “*the*

capability of a supply chain to prevent disruptions and to reduce the impact of disruptions through developing required level of readiness, quick response, and recovery ability”.

Supply chains are undertaking efforts to strengthen SC resilience through the development of capabilities including redundancy, multi-sourcing, transparency and traceability, agility, collaboration, velocity and inventory and flexibility etc (Gunasekaran et al., 2015; Leat & Revoredo-Giha, 2013; Meidute-Kavaliauskiene et al., 2021; Razak et al., 2023). The current study focuses on only three critical capabilities in supply chain management: supply chain agility, collaboration, and traceability. This research seeks to offer a thorough understanding of how these interrelated elements enhance overall supply chain resilience. Supply chain agility is key element for resilient supply chain (Christopher & Holweg, 2011). Supply chain agility refers to the capacity of a supply chain to identify short-term, transient variations in the supply chain and market environment and to adapt swiftly and flexibly to these changes. (Dubey, Gunasekaran, & Childe, 2019). (Singh et al., 2019) identified that supply chain agility enhances the resilience of a supply chain. Additionally, (P. Kumar & Kumar Singh, 2021) mentioned that agility is one of the critical aspects of supply chains responsiveness in the wake of disruption. (Y. Kazancoglu et al., 2018) identified supply chain agility as a key determinant in the responsiveness of global supply chains. (Hussain & Malik, 2022) offered important insights into the interaction between different supply chain capabilities and resilience. In particular, the study's results indicated that supply chain agility serves as a vital mediating factor in the relationship between seizing capabilities, transformation capabilities, and supply chain resilience.

Collaboration is a fundamental concept in supply chain management. (Blome et al., 2013) demonstrated that supply chain collaboration, which includes cooperation, shared understanding and collaborative efforts, influences an organization's success in the market regarding sustainable performance. Collaboration in SSCM mainly constitute on relationships between upstream and downstream partners (Hussain & Malik, 2020), facilitates joint planning (Whipple & Russell, 2007), information-sharing, co-developing strategic plans and harmonizing operations (Daugherty et al., 2006). Supply chain collaboration helps to respond to disruption in both upstream and downstream supply chains (Scholten & Schilder, 2015). Literature emphasizes the significance of collaboration in fostering SC resilience (Christopher & Peck, 2004; Jüttner, 2005; Pettit et al., 2013) and describe it as the adhesive that unites supply chains during crises. Collaboration in supply chain management entails the process of closely collaborating with various stakeholders, including partners, suppliers, and customers, to develop a more integrated and agile supply chain network. This collaborative approach enhances coordination across the entire supply chain, leading to a more adaptable and resilient system capable of better withstanding and recovering from disturbances (Baah et al., 2022; Gani et al., 2023; Song et al., 2022).

Traceability systems, which can collect, update, and transmit information in real time with minimal delays and errors, are crucial tools for enhancing SC performance in relation to SC risk management (Razak et al., 2023). Enhancing transparency throughout the supply chain is another function of traceability systems. A transparent supply chain ensures end-to-end visibility, order processing,

inventory status, transportation, and distribution using actual data instead of projections, hence reducing complexity (Gunasekaran et al., 2015). Organizations can benefit from supply chain traceability strategies that lead them to the right level of disclosure, encourage more in-depth internal and external audits, and improve stakeholders' impressions of the firm's openness (Montecchi et al., 2021). Supply chain traceability facilitates the achievement of SCR by facilitating in the early detection of deviations or disturbances, thereby alerting all stakeholders to potential disruptions, and allowing them to adopt ways to prevent it, which is essential in assisting a company to overcome any supply chain disruption (Bowen et al., 2001; Cousins et al., 2019). Thus, the current study postulates the below hypothesis.

H1: SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) have a direct and positive impact on SC resilience

H1a: Agility has a direct and positive impact on SC resilience

H1b: Collaboration has a direct and positive impact on SC resilience

H1c: Traceability has a direct and positive impact on SC resilience

3.8 Effect of SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on CE Practices

The CE paradigm advocates for the transformation of linear resource utilisation into a closed-loop circular model of production and consumption (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). Within a CE framework, waste outputs and unwanted products may be reprocessed as inputs in energy resources and material loops (Kouhizadeh et al., 2021). CE is predicated on the notion of "reduce, reuse, and recycle," which can be implemented through five key areas of actions: take, make, distribute, use, and recover (Ormazabal et al., 2016). Take is associated to the mechanism by which industry acquires raw resources for their system. Make involves the act of converting raw materials into final products. The expression "distributes" denotes the act of making finished products accessible to customers. Use enables customers to derive advantages from the products' usefulness, which in turn satisfies their purchasing needs. Recover makes it easier to handle the product's end-of-life situation by encouraging its subsequent reuse and recycling.

Integration of CE into SCM has the potential to yield benefits from a sustainability point of view (Genovese et al., 2017; Nasiri et al., 2018). Consequently, there is a growing enthusiasm in supply chain management for CE (Govindan & Hasanagic, 2018; Howard et al., 2019; Y. Kazancoglu et al., 2018; J. Liu et al., 2018). Nevertheless, Research in SCM is still in its early stages regarding how to improve supply chain theories and methods to achieve the vision and potential of a CE (Farooque et al., 2019). In current study, researcher evaluate how supply chain capabilities, including supply chain agility, collaboration and traceability can facilitate the incorporation of CE thinking in SCM.

Agile supply chains can swiftly respond to changes in market demands, regulations, or consumer preferences. This adaptability enables organizations to rapidly adopt circular economy practices, such as incorporating recycled materials, implementing remanufacturing processes, or launching product-as-a-service models (Nandi et al., 2021a). In a circular economy, effective reverse logistics is crucial for collecting, refurbishing, and recycling used products and materials. An agile supply chain optimizes

reverse logistics processes (Soosay & Hyland, 2015; Wanganoo, 2020), ensuring seamless flow and handling of end-of-life goods back into the circular system (Sadeghi et al., 2023). Agility is required in CE for the identification, production, and delivery of by-products formerly considered as waste for new applications and customers (Nandi et al., 2021b).

Collaboration between product designers, manufacturers, and suppliers allows for the incorporation of circular design principles right from the beginning (Calicchio Berardi & Peregrino de Brito, 2021). Collaborative efforts can focus on creating products that are easily repairable, upgradable, and recyclable, contributing to a circular product lifecycle (Bloise, 2020). Collaboration streamlines close loop processes, making it easier to handle product returns, repairs, and recycling. By working together, supply chain partners can efficiently manage the flow of used products and materials back into the circular system. (Hussain & Malik, 2020) also argued that the expansion of upstream and downstream collaborative interactions outside the traditional industrial limits of a supply chain enables a shift to circular economy.

Traceable system capable of identifying each unit produced and supplied from the farm to the fork. A traceability system allows for the synchronisation of information in circular supply chains, which in turn benefits all stakeholders engaged in the supply chain by allowing for better, more well-informed decision-making (Centobelli et al., 2021; J. Xu et al., 2021). Thus, traceability systems that monitor every movement of materials both upstream and downstream in the supply chain, collect items in manageable quantities, and share information with consumers and SC stakeholders may be essential for implementing CE practices in SCM (Anastasiadis et al., 2022). According to the literature, traceability systems contribute to the sustainability of the agri-food SC (Epelbaum & Martinez, 2014; Garcia-Torres et al., 2019) and are crucial for the implementation of CE practises (Anastasiadis et al., 2022; Garcia-Torres et al., 2019).

The aforementioned literature is used to examine the following hypotheses.

H2: SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) have a direct and positive impact on CE Practices

H2a: Agility has a direct and positive impact on CE Practices

H2b: Collaboration has a direct and positive impact on CE Practices

H2c: Traceability has a direct and positive impact on CE Practices

3.9 Effect of SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)

SC capabilities (SCCs) refer to the abilities to coordinate the supply chain and everyday operational activities using internal and external resources (F. Wu et al., 2006). Researchers have identified SC capabilities as a critical component of SC strategy and a source of competitive advantage (Morash & Lynch, 2002). Prior studies also provided evidence in support of the idea that SC capabilities contribute to enhance supply chain performance. According to the analysis performed by (Liao & Kuo, 2014) on

the relationship between supply chain (SC) capability and organisational performance, it was concluded that the presence of SC capability positively impacts overall performance of an organization. (Asamoah et al., 2021) emphasised that the SC's quick response capability assisted in controlling inventory and orders, lowering liability and delivery costs through effectively overseeing the distribution of items, which in turn improves operational performance. (Hartono et al., 2010) claimed that extensive information sharing results in improved operational performance. The literature articulate several SCCs, including supply chain agility (Geyi et al., 2020; Teece, 2007; Q. Zhang et al., 2002), Collaboration (Scholten & Schilder, 2015; Shan et al., 2023; Weber & Heidenreich, 2018), supply chain integration (Flynn et al., 2010; Huo, 2012), supply chain flexibility (Edwin Cheng et al., 2022) information exchange (W. Yu et al., 2018), and traceability (Razak et al., 2023; Roy, 2021) etc have a positive link with supply chain performance.

A sustainable supply chain prioritizes minimizing its environmental impact, fostering social responsibility, and maintaining economic viability. Firms need capabilities to combine sets of interdependent resources on a regular basis to establish performance-enhancing patterns if they want to achieve sustainable performance (Morash, 2001; J. Schmidt & Keil, 2013; Sirmon et al., 2011). Supply chain agility allows businesses to enhance adaptability in their operations, respond quickly to changes, anticipate environmental shifts, and empower customers (Gligor et al., 2019). Businesses require supply chain agility to respond rapidly and effectively to the sustainable demands of their industry (Al Humdan et al., 2020; Geyi et al., 2020; Nath & Agrawal, 2020). According to (Ciccullo et al., 2018), supply chain agility and SSCM can work together to form a complementary and synergistic new paradigm. Additionally, the adoption of SSCM can be facilitated by cultivating supply chain agility practises, which in turn can assist in the evolution and long-term viability of sustainability initiatives and practises (Nath & Agrawal, 2020). (Geyi et al., 2020) argue that agile capabilities are essential for optimising the results of implementing sustainable practises. (Cantele et al., 2023) stated that high sustainability performance can be accomplished through various approaches, involving varying degrees of supply chain agility and values for each proposed sustainability endeavour.

For businesses to meet their economic, social, and environmental sustainability goals, supply chain collaboration has emerged as a key factor (Chen et al., 2017). According to (Soylu et al., 2006) supply chain collaboration is a common approach for businesses to share Information, forge partnerships for enhanced performance, and reduce costs and inventory. The aim of collaboration in a supply chain is to enhance a company's competitive advantage. (Cao & Zhang, 2011; Soylu et al., 2006). (Cao et al., 2010) stated that supply chain collaboration can help reduce risks such as conflicts and uncertainty by strengthening relationships between all parties involved, and that it can also be seen from a learning and knowledge perspective, wherein mutual information inception enhances innovation and expands resources. Supply chain collaboration helps organisations in having complete knowledge across all SSCM dimensions. (Cao & Zhang, 2011) highlighted the beneficial effects of supply chain collaboration on financial metrics and (Chin et al., 2015) investigated the effects of collaboration on

sustainable supply chain performances from the viewpoint of an environmental approach. Supply chain collaboration and SSCP have been found to be positively correlated by several studies (Billah et al., 2023; Mehdikhani & Valmohammadi, 2019; Shahid et al., 2020).

When it comes to managing supply chains, traceability is crucial for ensuring that the correct product is delivered at the right time and in the right amount (Ma et al., 2023). The implementation of traceability enhances the transparency, security, control, and auditability of product information among various stakeholders. Traceability has been regarded as a "good practise" for risk management (Lupien, 2005), a competitive advantage (Canavari et al., 2010), a unique resource embedded in firms' routines (Epelbaum & Martinez, 2014), and valuable knowledge resources related to value (Engelseth et al., 2014) for businesses, serving as a means of product safety monitoring. The necessity of traceability has become essential to enhance the vulnerabilities present in various aspects of business operations (Dandage et al., 2017). (Epelbaum & Martinez, 2014; Ma et al., 2023; X. Zhou et al., 2022) has investigated the relationship between supply chain traceability and sustainable supply chain performance.

The following hypothesis is stated based on the above considerations.

H3: SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) have a direct and positive impact on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

H3a: Agility has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance

H3b: Collaboration has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance

H3c: Traceability has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance

3.10 Effect of SC Resilience on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)

SC resilience is defined as the capacity of a supply chain to endure and adapt to disruptions while continuing to fulfil its essential functions and meet customer demands (Fiksel, 2006). It involves the ability to foresee, prepare for, respond to, and recover from a range of risks and unforeseen events that may affect the operations and performance of the supply chain (Pettit et al., 2010). A resilient supply chain identifies potential risks and vulnerabilities throughout its network, including risks related to suppliers, logistics, natural disasters, geopolitical factors, economic fluctuations, and other uncertainties. Resilient supply networks are the result of concerted efforts by all parties involved to anticipate and guard against disruptions (Faruquee et al., 2021). (S. Y. Ponomarov & Holcomb, 2009) break SCR down into three phases: readiness, response, and restoration/recovery. (Shan et al., 2023) stated that resilience is a proactive technique that involves activism, vigilance, and dynamism. (Wieland & Wallenburg, 2012) listed the active and passive approaches of resilience.

Sustainability is associated with the "triple bottom line" approach which includes economic, social, and environmental factors (Elkington & Rowlands, 1999; Savitz, 2013; Touboulic & Walker, 2015). The triple bottom line enables businesses to more effectively meet the needs of their shareholders as well as other stakeholders (Carter & Rogers, 2008). According to (Carter & Rogers, 2008), the concept of a

sustainable supply chain involves the strategic and transparent integration of an organization's social, environmental, and economic objectives. This integration is accomplished through the coordinated management of key inter-organizational business processes. The aim is to improve the long-term economic performance of both the individual organization and its associated supply chains. Researchers have employed various approaches to tackle the challenge of achieving sustainable supply chain performance. (Uysal, 2012) lays out the framework for the SSCP measuring system, which considers the four performance characteristics of sustainable economic, social, environmental, and resource performance. (Gong et al., 2019) highlight customer awareness as the fundamental drive behind pursuing SSCP. (Bag et al., 2020) suggests that both innovation and learning performance will significantly influence SSCP. (Shan et al., 2023) assesses the sustainable supply chain performance (SSCP) through the examination of three key indicators: economic accountability, environmental liability, and social equality. (Edwin Cheng et al., 2022) discussed the role of DBA capabilities on SSCP.

SC resilience develops when businesses can withstand, adjust to, and recover from disturbances and, as a result, can meet consumer needs and guarantee the performance of that supply chain for achieving sustainability. Organizations today are under unprecedented pressure from a variety of stakeholders to conduct their business operations sustainably (Wolf, 2014). According to (Cui et al., 2023) findings, businesses looking to boost their sustainability performance should develop the capabilities necessary to be ready for unforeseen changes as well as to react and adjust after a disruption occur. The reactive and proactive SC resilience significantly impact three dimensions of sustainable performance (Cui et al., 2023). (Thaiprayoon et al., 2019) proposed that SC resilience has significant effect on sustainability performance. (Piprani et al., 2023) examine the SSCP under the lens of dynamic data analytics capability, innovation capability and SC resilience.

In the light of these evidence researchers proposed the following hypothesis.

H4: SC resilience has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance

3.11 Effect of CE Practices on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)

The term "circular economy" (CE) refers to a new economic and business model that emphasises reusing and recycling materials rather than simply disposing of them once a product has served its purpose (de Sousa Jabbour et al., 2018). As a substitute for the current linear model of resource consumption, the logic of circularity uses the concepts of regeneration and restoration for the most efficient use of resources (Korhonen et al., 2018; Sauvé et al., 2016). A CE requires innovation in terms of both products and processes to deviate from the conventional linear production and consumption systems (Adams et al., 2017; F. Preston, 2012; Ritzén & Sandström, 2017). CE practises enable businesses to achieve their CE-targeted performance goals by reducing the reliance on virgin materials, promoting reuse and closed-loop material flow, minimizing energy losses, lowering emissions, and preventing and mitigating pollution (Bai et al., 2020; Edwin Cheng et al., 2022).

The growing awareness of the need of sustainable supply chains has spawned new standards for supply chain management from a circular economy perspective, in which materials that have served their purpose in a product's life cycle are recycled and reintroduced to the value chain (Centobelli et al., 2021). A circular economy (CE) can assist businesses in overcoming some of the biggest environmental problems, such as climate change, waste and pollution, and biodiversity loss (Bag & Rahman, 2023). Therefore, the circular economy model has given enterprises working in the same supply network (and beyond) a framework for engaging in sustainability initiatives, allowing best practises to be adopted (Genovese et al., 2017). As part of its sustainability initiative, a company like Philips has established a strategic alliance with the Ellen MacArthur foundation to move towards CE (Bag & Rahman, 2023). (Dey et al., 2020) also revealed the correlation between CE field of action and sustainability performance. (Edwin Cheng et al., 2022) examine the linkage between DBA capabilities, CE practices, sustainable supply chain flexibility and sustainable supply chain (SSC) performance and found that CE practices are significantly mediating variables between the BDA capabilities and SSC performance. (T. T. Le et al., 2022) investigated how the implementation of circular economy principles and entrepreneurial initiatives within the circular economy framework contribute to enhancing sustainable supply chain practices and boosting overall sustainability performance for small and medium-sized businesses operating in the food industry supply chain of developing economies. As per the aforementioned arguments, the following hypothesis is proposed.

H5: CE Practices has a direct and positive impact on m sustainable supply chain performance

3.12 Mediating Effect of SC Resilience between SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)

The literature pertaining to the SCRES, and the Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT) highlights the necessity for a company working within a highly dynamic context to effectively manage its resource allocation, integration, consolidation, and adaptation to the evolving business landscape (Gunasekaran et al., 2015). As noted by (P. Kumar & Kumar Singh, 2021), agility plays a vital role in improving the responsiveness of supply chains during disruptions. According to (Lohmer et al., 2020), there is a perception that supply chains exhibit a collaborative nature to improve their resilience. Collaboration encompasses various elements such as the exchange of Information, coordination of decisions, consolidation of resources, collective communication among participants, and the harmonisation of objectives (P. Kumar & Kumar Singh, 2021). Implementing traceability measures enhances the overall visibility of the supply chain, hence enhancing its resistance to disruptions (Razak et al., 2023).

Resilience is frequently employed alongside concepts of sustainability. Resilience pertains to a system's ability to effectively adjust and withstand ongoing stressors or severe disruptions. In contrast, the concept of sustainability places emphasis on the welfare of both present and future generations, taking into consideration several aspects such as social, economic, and environmental considerations (Jesse et al., 2019). According to (Marchese et al., 2018), the examination of resilience is an essential

requirement to attain sustainability. Therefore, the use of SCR will enhance sustainable performance by facilitating a rapid response to environmental disruptions via adjustments to products and procedures. (Bahrami & Shokouhyar, 2022) demonstrated the partial mediating role of SC resilience between DBA capabilities and firm's performance. (Haq & Aslam, 2023) stated the positive mediating effect of SCR between entrepreneurial leadership capability and supply chain performance. (Piprani et al., 2023) proposed the mediation effect of SCR between supply chain integration and supply chain performance. The study conducted by (Rezaei et al., 2022) examined the mediating effects of SC resilience and organisational flexibility on the association between data analytics capabilities and competitive advantage. The existing body of scholarly literature has firmly established a discernible association of SC resilience as mediator with capabilities and performance. Therefore, drawing from the evidence, the researcher posited the following hypothesis.

H6: SC resilience mediates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

H6a: SC resilience mediates the relationship between agility, and sustainable supply chain performance

H6b: SC resilience mediates the relationship between collaboration, and sustainable supply chain performance

H6c: SC resilience mediates the relationship between traceability, and sustainable supply chain performance

3.13 Mediating Effect of CE Practices between SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

CE is implemented through concrete steps and practises with the end goal of replacing traditional, linear production and consumption structures with circular models (Schroeder et al., 2019). The idea of Circular Economy Practices (CEP) is frequently discussed within the context of many frameworks, such as the 3R framework (reduce, reuse, and recycle) as proposed by (Cui et al., 2024), the 4R framework (reduce, reuse, recycle, and recover) as suggested by (Gebhardt et al., 2022), and even the 9R framework as outlined by (Potting et al., 2017). In the context of the circular economy, it is imperative for supply chains and organisations to adhere to the concepts of material, resource, and energy cycling, thereby aligning their operations with the operation of natural systems (Geng et al., 2013, 2016). The study conducted by (Stumpf et al., 2023) examined the resources and capabilities necessary for enhancing the circularity performance across the entire supply chain. A blend of the RT Delphi method and Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was employed to recognize and prioritize resources and capabilities (RCs) in accordance with the Resource-Based View (RBV). The study revealed that the collaboration capability between upstream and downstream actors as well as the design capabilities were the significant factors to facilitate the creation of simpler and more recyclable products. (Calicchio Berardi & Peregrino de Brito, 2021) undertook a comprehensive analysis of existing literature to explore the elements that facilitate to the successful transition to a Circular Economy (CE). Their findings highlight the

significance of social and governance capabilities, along with the importance of supply chain collaboration capability in facilitating this shift.

In the meantime, implementing CEP can help businesses become more sustainable (Barros et al., 2021). In terms of conceptualization, the implementation of cleaner industrial practises and the adoption of circular product development strategies yield economic advantages. These advantages manifest through the reduction of costs and the creation of new revenue streams, ultimately enhancing competitive advantage (Rosa et al., 2019). The practical manifestation of the environmental impacts of CEP is readily apparent. An illustration of this may be seen in the implementation of recycling and remanufacturing practises within the framework of cleaner production and circular product development. These activities contribute to a more sustainable utilisation of natural resources, simultaneously mitigating the presence of pollutants and dangerous substances (S. A. R. Khan et al., 2022). In term of social impact, circular economy practises (CEP) have the potential to facilitate novel modes of business collaboration among small and medium-sized firms. This collaboration may be leveraged to effectively utilise by-products, thereby encouraging knowledge co-creation, and enhancing social welfare (Howard et al., 2022).

Various studies investigated the mediation role of CE practices in different context; the researcher proposes the mediation role of CE practices between SC capabilities and SSC performance and postulate the below mentioned hypothesis.

H7: CE Practices mediates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

H7a: CE Practices mediates the relationship between agility and sustainable supply chain performance

H7b: CE Practices mediates the relationship between collaboration and sustainable supply chain performance

H7c: CE Practices mediates the relationship between traceability and sustainable supply chain performance

3.14 Moderating Role of Blockchain Technology

Block chain technology (BCT) is one of the most significant technologies of I4.0 that fundamentally transforms industries, including business and supply chains (Saber et al., 2018). As a rapidly developing technology, block chain has the potential to boost businesses' competitiveness through the introduction of new, ground-breaking platform-based business models (Berdik et al., 2021; L. Tseng et al., 2020). This technology, which is progressively gaining popularity, uses a peer-to-peer (P2P) network for data/information sharing and verification to streamline company operations. To validate online transactions and protect against cybersecurity risks, block chain technology uses public key encryption (Jahankhani et al., 2012; Maleh et al., 2020). It is a representation of a distributed transaction system in which all transactions are recorded and accessible by all users (Cole et al., 2019; Khalid et al., 2020). Bitcoin's block chain technology is thought to be the key to solving the problem of achieving full transparency of all transactions.

Supply chains are typically multi-tiered, complicated networks that are dispersed geographically (M. H. Ali et al., 2021; Ivanov & Dolgui, 2020; M. Mubarik & Mohd Rasi, 2019). Because of SC networks' inherent complexity, companies begin to lose visibility over the topology of their supply chain networks. The gravity of this challenge was brought to light by Achilles (2013) who mentioned in his research that "40% of companies who procured only in the UK and over 20% who sourced globally had no supply chain information beyond their primary suppliers. The lack of visibility in supply networks significantly impairs an organization's capacity to respond to disruptions in the supply chain (Agrawal et al., 2024; Ooi et al., 2025; Swink et al., 2024). Therefore, companies' supply chains are working extremely hard to deal with COVID-19 consequences and are doing everything in their power to ensure the availability of raw materials to keep their supply chains operational (T. Y. Choi et al., 2020; M. S. Mubarik et al., 2019).

Bayramova et al. (2021) highlight that blockchain technology (BCT) plays a crucial role in enhancing supply chain resilience (SCR), particularly in areas such as visibility, information sharing, risk management, and integration. Visibility is notably improved when BCT is applied in traceability systems (Gonczol et al., 2022), while information exchange and collaboration are strengthened through the distributed ledger features of BCT (Gonczol et al., 2022; Toufaily et al., 2021). BCT is especially effective in tracking and tracing orders from production to delivery, allowing for prompt adjustments as needed (Chang et al., 2019). By improving visibility and enabling real-time data/information sharing across the supply chain network, BCT supports SCR strategies by minimizing the number of stakeholders affected by disruptions (Lohmer, 2020). Additionally, BCT enables supply chain leaders to leverage data to manage current disruptions and build resilience for the future (Rajab, 2020; Nagariya, 2023). It also allows organizations to enhance their supply chain capabilities, fostering increased competitiveness (Madhwal & Panfilov, 2017; Rejeb & Rejeb, 2020; Sheel & Nath, 2019, as cited in Iranmanesh, 2023).

Growing concerns about food standards and contamination concerns have refocused attention on the need for improved supply chain traceability (Aung & Chang, 2014; Bosona & Gebresenbet, 2013). Monitoring the progress of agricultural products and effectively managing the logistics of the food and agricultural supply chain is crucial to ensuring the safety of the final product (Salah et al., 2019). To ensure that items in the agricultural supply chain can be traced, it is necessary to gather, share, and manage vital data that locates their origin. The existing traceability strategy in the agricultural supply chain suffers greatly from data fragmentation and centralised controls, which make the data vulnerable to management. The use of blockchain technology in recent technological advancements can offer a useful and viable solution for guaranteeing the traceability of agricultural products and remove the need for a reliable centralised authority. Blockchain has high hopes due to its innovative features, such as real-time information exchange, enhanced security, accountability, immutability, and transparency (J. Aslam et al., 2021). Through a sequence of verifiable blocks, the blockchain ensures both transparency and reliability. These applications of block chain make it possible to keep track on products, verify and

authorise them throughout a transaction's entirety, and conduct comprehensive audits depending on who has access to what data (Dutta et al., 2020).

Block chain improves the level of confidence between traders by making their transactions transparent and makes it possible for trading partners to exchange documents, designs quality documents, and share transaction data more quickly, accurately, and reliably (Sheel & Nath, 2019). By exchanging data and Information, demand forecasting, inventory control, backup will all be improved (Sheel & Nath, 2019) and enterprises can gain a flexible environment to adapt to internal and external changes which can augment the agility of the supply chains (Li et al., 2022). Accurate market predictions allow businesses to react and alter production plans promptly, guaranteeing the agility of SCs (Li et al., 2022). In the context of supply chain collaboration, trust and data collaboration are foundational elements of collaborative environments which are two significant inter-relational characteristics with a direct connection to information technology (Lohmer et al., 2020). BCT could serve as an appropriate intermediary for business ties between companies that haven't yet been established because of a lack of trust (Crosby et al., 2016; Swan, 2015).

For businesses to meet their economic, social, and environmental sustainability goals, supply chain collaboration has emerged as a key factor (Chen et al., 2017). According to (Soylu et al., 2006) supply chain collaboration is a common approach for businesses to share Information, forge partnerships for enhanced performance, and reduce costs and inventory. The aim of collaboration in a supply chain is to enhance a company's competitive advantage. (Soylu et al., 2006, Cao and Zhang, 2011). (Cao et al., 2010) stated that supply chain collaboration can help reduce risks such as conflicts and uncertainty by strengthening relationships between all parties involved, and that it can also be seen from a learning and knowledge perspective, wherein mutual information inception enhances innovation and expands resources. Supply chain collaboration helps organisations in having complete knowledge across all SSCM dimensions. (Cao and Zhang, 2011) highlighted the beneficial effects of supply chain collaboration on financial metrics and (Chin, Tat and Sulaiman, 2015) investigated the effects of collaboration on sustainable supply chain performances from the viewpoint of an environmental approach. Supply chain collaboration and SSCP have been found to be positively correlated by several studies (Mehdikhani and Valmohammadi, 2019, Shahid et al., 2020, Billah et al., 2023).

When it comes to managing supply chains, traceability is crucial for ensuring that the correct product is delivered at the right time and in the right amount (Ma, Shi and Kang, 2023). The implementation of traceability enhances the transparency, security, control, and auditability of product information among various stakeholders. Traceability has been regarded as a "good practise" for risk management (Lupien, 2005), a competitive advantage (Canavari et al., 2010), a unique resource embedded in firms' routines (Epelbaum and Martinez, 2014), and valuable knowledge resources related to value (Engelseth, Wongthatsanekorn and Charoensiriwath, 2014) for businesses, serving as a means of product safety monitoring. The necessity of traceability has become essential to enhance the vulnerabilities present in

various aspects of business operations (Dandage, Badia-Melis and Ruiz-García, 2017). (Epelbaum and Martinez, 2014, Zhou, Pullman and Xu, 2022, Ma, Shi and Kang, 2023) has investigated the relationship between supply chain traceability and sustainable supply chain performance. The following hypothesis is stated based on the above considerations.

Since successful disruption management is linked to traceability and both are possibly enhanced in the digitalization era by BCT. Hence, BCT-enabled traceability is a key factor in ensuring the resilience of the supply chains (Razak et al., 2023). During the COVID-19 crisis, the vulnerabilities in the global supply chain were on full display due to restrictions placed at borders, shutdowns, and a general lack of control that might result in nonlinear and transformative changes. Circular economy has emerged as an alternative to linear supply chains in the contemporary environment. In conjunction with BCT, SC capabilities have the ability to enhance CE thinking.

Based on the aforementioned literature, the following hypotheses will be evaluated.

H8: BCT moderates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and SC resilience

H8a: BCT moderates the relationship between agility and SC resilience

H8b: BCT moderates the relationship between collaboration and SC resilience

H8c: BCT moderates the relationship between traceability and SC resilience

H9: BCT moderates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and CE practices

H9a: BCT moderates the relationship between agility and CE practices

H9b: BCT moderates the relationship between collaboration and CE practices

H9c: BCT moderates the relationship between traceability and CE practices

H10: BCT moderates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

H10a: BCT moderates the relationship between agility and sustainable supply chain performance

H10b: BCT moderates the relationship between collaboration and sustainable supply chain performance

H10c: BCT moderates the relationship between traceability and sustainable supply chain performance

3.15 Theoretical Lenses

In the context of research, grounding the study in established theoretical frameworks is essential to validate the key variables under investigation. This study focuses on understanding how supply chain (SC) capabilities, SC resilience, circular economy (CE) practices, and blockchain technology (BCT) collectively impact sustainable supply chain performance. Numerous theories have been applied within the supply chain management domain to explain these constructs, including the Resource-Based View

(RBV), Organisational Information Processing (OIP), Resource Dependence Theory (RDT), Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Network Theory (NT), Institutional Theory (IT), and Complex Adaptive Systems (CAS) theory (Adobor & McMullen, 2018; Ahmed & MacCarthy, 2022; Davis, 1989; El Baz & Ruel, 2021; Gunasekaran et al., 2015; Tashman, 2021).

This research focused primarily on RBV, RDT, and DCT, which together provide a comprehensive lens to explore how internal resources, external relationships, and dynamic adaptations drive resilience and circular economy practices in supply chains. Following the frameworks of Nandi et al. (2021b) and Tashman (2021), RBV and RDT are seen as complementary perspectives: RBV emphasizes leveraging internal resources and capabilities, while RDT highlights securing critical resources through external collaborations to build resilience and CE practices. Given the rapidly evolving and competitive business environment, digitization plays a crucial role in supply chain management (Lambourdiere & Corbin, 2020). Thus, to examine the moderating role of blockchain technology on SC capabilities in fostering resilience and circular economy initiatives, the researcher incorporated Dynamic Capability Theory, which addresses how organizations adapt and reconfigure resources in dynamic contexts (Lambourdiere & Corbin, 2020; Meier et al., 2023).

In summary, RBV underscores the importance of an organization's existing and potential resources and capabilities to achieve sustainable competitive advantage. RDT focuses on how firms rely on their external environment to access vital resources, and DCT explains how firms proactively create or modify practices to reconfigure resources in response to change (Teece et al., 1997). The following sections discuss these selected theoretical approaches in detail.

3.15.1 Resource Based View (RBV) and Resource Dependant Theory (RDT)

The resource-based view (RBV) emerged as an alternative to the dominant industrial organization (IO) view articulated by (Bain, 1968). RBV explicitly focusses on an organization's internal resources and capabilities for sustainable competitive advantage (SCA) (Nandi et al., 2021b; S. Ponomarov, 2012). (Barney, 1991) stated in his initial study that a firm's resources and capabilities may be used to gain a sustained competitive advantage. It has been established that these resources are distinctive, valuable, and irreplaceable. Additionally, these resources can be seen as collections of both tangible and intangible resources that comprise a company's managerial abilities, organisational procedures, and the knowledge and information it possesses and controls (Barney et al., 2001). Resources refer to "what a firm has access to or possesses, not what a firm is capable of" (Pham, 2019). They may be developed within the company or purchased from the market. Therefore, it is crucial that businesses manage their resources well. Whereas capabilities can be described as "businesses' capacity to deploy resources" (Amit & Schoemaker, 1993). Capabilities can also be thought of in terms of higher-level routines or bundle of routines to accomplish desired results (Helfat et al., 2009). This viewpoint is similar to that of (Sirmon et al., 2008), who argue that capacities are developed through the bundling of resources. The term bundling describes the practice of aggregating resources to enhance overall capability (Sirmon et

al., 2008). Businesses need to bundle their resources in order to develop distinctive skills that provide them sustainable competitive advantage.

Alternatively, (Selznick, 2011) proposed the idea of focusing on interactions across organisations to gain a competitive edge, rather than intra-organisational relationships. This idea called resource dependant theory (RDT) that operates on the premise that an organization's performance is shaped by its environment. It places an emphasis on collaboration between entities in order to stabilise resources and lessen the impact of environmental uncertainty (Nandi et al., 2021a; Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003; Tashman, 2021). According to (Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003), the organisation is especially vulnerable to the influence of the outside interest groups (social players), who have access to resources that are vital for the organisation (Pfeffer, 1987). In accordance with the resource dependence theory, one reason organizations strive to build relationships with stakeholders is to obtain resources that those stakeholders control (Mitchell et al., 1997).

Within the realm of SC resilience, RBV highlights the significance of identifying and leveraging key resources that enable organizations to withstand disruptions and uncertainties (Edwin Cheng et al., 2022). For instance, companies that invest in advanced technologies for real-time tracking and monitoring of their supply chains have a better chance of responding effectively to unexpected events and mitigating disruptions. In the circular economy context, RBV is relevant when organizations adopt circular business practices that promote resource efficiency and closed-loop systems (Nandi et al., 2021b). Companies that focus on reducing waste, reusing materials, and designing products for durability can derive competitive advantage by accessing a continuous flow of resources from their existing products. While the RDT perspective would identify effective control mechanisms of external assets such as coalitions, joint purchasing agreements, and various strategic partnerships, which can aid in fostering resilience and CE in SCs. Some studies have concurrently employed RBV and RDT to study the dominating organisational resources and capabilities (Frączkiewicz-Wronka & Szymaniec, 2012; Nandi et al., 2021b; Tehseen & Sajilan, 2016). Using earlier research as a guide, the researcher emphasised the complimentary significance of RBV and RDT lenses in highlighting the crucial role of BCT in building resilience and CE in supply chains.

3.15.2 Dynamic Capability Theory

Dynamic capabilities view, developed by (Teece et al., 1997), to solve the problem of resource-based approach, which does not take into account how to develop and retain organizations' competitive advantages over time. This problem is of the utmost importance because of the difficulties in preserving competitive advantages in dynamic environments, which requires constant resource restructuring by a firm in order to rapidly respond to changing market conditions (Schumpeter, 2013). Dynamic capabilities are therefore change-oriented and represent organisational and managerial processes that adapt, integrate, and restructure resources to meet changing needs. These capabilities can help businesses not only adapt their resources to shifting market conditions but also change their business environment through innovation and cooperation with key partners (Teece, 2007).

According to (Teece, 2014) there are two categories of capabilities, ordinary and dynamic. Ordinary capabilities are actions taken by businesses to produce and distribute their goods and services using their resources. Most of these improvements are made in the areas of administration, operations, and governance by including factors like (1) trained employees and contractors, (2) infrastructure, (3) procedures and practises, and (4) administrative coordination. However, in a market with weak competition, it is possible to achieve a competitive advantage with ordinary capabilities alone, as these qualities can be purchased or replicated.

On the other hand, dynamic capabilities make it easier to develop unique products and services that respond to or even drive changes in the market. According to (Helfat et al., 2009), dynamic capabilities are "an organization's ability to proactively generate, expand, or adjust its resource base". Strong dynamic capabilities are crucial to anticipate the needs of current and prospective customers, as well as gather, arrange, and reorganise the necessary resources to develop innovation in response to those needs. Dynamic capabilities are therefore path-dependent and challenging for competitors to copy.

Dynamic capabilities consist of three fundamental abilities: to sense, to seize, and to reconfigure (Teece, 2007). To "sense" is to "scan," "detect," and "understand" market signals in order to "evaluate" business opportunities and risks in a dynamic market. Businesses would benefit from the insight gained through sensing processes, since the data they collect would be transformed into valuable knowledge and intelligence. The ability to "seize" an opportunity or avoid a threat is essential for businesses to create value (Teece, 2007). To maximize the chances of success, it is also vital to choose the right technology and resources, as well as a business strategy that can seize and take advantage of new opportunities. The capacity to reconfigure entails the ongoing alignment and realignment of operating practises (Teece, 2007). To achieve this goal, businesses need to be highly decentralised and equipped with open innovation strategies that promote agility and flexibility.

The digitalization process is fundamentally dynamic, therefore dynamic capability theory is helpful in explaining how blockchain technology (BCT) can influence and support the achievement of resilience and circular economy thinking in supply chains (Meier et al., 2023; Mohamed et al., 2023; Pattanayak et al., 2023). Dynamic capability theory provides a framework to understand how organizations can develop and deploy capabilities that enable them to efficiently react to and recuperate from disruptions (Kalubanga & Gudergan, 2022). Once disruptions are detected, dynamic capability theory focuses on seizing opportunities to enhance resilience. This involves the ability to quickly assess the impact of disruptions and develop strategies to mitigate their effects. Dynamic capability theory also provides insights into how organizations can develop and deploy capabilities to effectively implement circular economy practices (Köhler & Pizzol, 2020; Scarpellini et al., 2020). Organizations need to develop the capability to sense and seize opportunities for circular economy practices, such as designing products for durability, facilitating recycling processes, and exploring new markets for secondary materials, redesigning products and promote resource efficiency (Marrucci et al., 2022). Dynamic capability theory provides insights into how organizations can develop and deploy capabilities to effectively

leverage blockchain technology to gain competitive advantages and drive innovation (Ahmed & MacCarthy, 2022; Choi & Siqin, 2022). Dynamic capability views also relevant in the context of BCT, where organizations need to develop the capability to understand the advantages of blockchain in terms of transparency, traceability, security, collaboration, and trust, and identify areas in their operations or industry where blockchain could be a game-changer (Li et al., 2022).

3.16 Conceptual Framework

This section will outline the proposed conceptual model for this research, providing a detailed explanation of the various factors involved. The proposed model makes various simplifications to provide a more thorough explanation of the phenomenon being studied (Tarhini et al., 2017). The proposed model will illustrate how the explanatory variables influence the dependent variables (Mandell, 1992) and will assist the researcher in formulating hypotheses and testing the proposed relationships between the identified constructs to assess the validity of the theoretical model (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

Firms required capabilities and resources to perform day-to-day procedures within an organisation and considered as an important variable in accomplishing sustainable supply chain performance. SC resilience and circular economy practices are other two important variables in realizing sustainable supply chain performance. By integrating SC resilience with circular economy practices, organizations can foster sustainable supply chain performance, contributing to a more resilient, responsible, and environmentally friendly business ecosystem (Cherrafi et al., 2022). SC capabilities play a critical role in enabling and strengthening both SC resilience and circular economy practices (Cherrafi et al., 2022). Digital technologies can support the SC capabilities enable decision-making during disruptions and ensure seamless coordination among supply chain partners in implementing CE practices (Nandi et al., 2021a; Ralston & Blackhurst, 2020).

Five key variables are illustrated in the below conceptual framework, SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) as independent variable, SC resilience and circular economy practices as dependent variables. Blockchain technology serves as a moderator in the relationship between supply chain capabilities, supply chain resilience, and circular economy practices, with sustainable supply chain performance being the resulting outcome. Figure 3.9 provides a diagrammatic representation of the proposed conceptual framework.

Figure 3.9 Proposed Conceptual Framework

3.17 Summary

The present chapter provides an overview of the concepts, definitions, and theories pertaining to the variables recommended for examination in this study. This study provides an in-depth exploration of the independent variables, namely SC capabilities encompassing agility, collaboration, and traceability, as well as the dependent variables, SC resilience and circular economy practises. Furthermore, this study examines the mediating roles of SC resilience (SCR) and circular economy practises (CEP), as well as the moderating effects of blockchain technology (BCT). Ultimately, the chapter offers an exhaustive examination of the suggested hypothesis and theoretical framework of the research.

CHAPTER 4 : METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the research approach utilized in this study. The chapter begins with an insight of various research philosophies and methodologies available to conduct research and discusses the fundamental premises of chosen research strategy for this study. To address the research questions, this section provides a concise explanation and rationale for the chosen research philosophies, the research design, including sampling methods, sample size, instrument development, and the validity of the instrument. After providing a brief rationale for the general quantitative study design, the research methodology and research paradigm are outlined. Moreover, this chapter will elaborate the development of research framework to empirically test the proposed hypotheses in detail by concentrating on the data sources, data collection methods, sample procedures, description of analytical tools employed in data analysis and ethical consideration.

4.2 Research Design

This section outlines the research design employed in the study, adhering to the research onion framework proposed by Saunders et al. (2019) (see Figure 4.1). The process of selecting an appropriate research design is critical to ensuring the credibility, reliability, and applicability of research findings (Asenahabi, 2019). Saunders et al. (2019) proposed the Research Onion framework, which guides researchers through a structured, layered approach to methodological decision-making. While other frameworks, such as the Research Honeycomb by Wilson, J., (2014), offer valuable perspectives, the Research Onion was selected for its comprehensive coverage (Melnikovas, A., 2018) and suitability for this study's objectives, particularly in addressing the complex relationships between supply chain capabilities, resilience, circular economy practices, and sustainable performance. This model consists of six core layers: research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, time horizon, data collection methods, and techniques/procedures. Each layer influences the research process and contributes to the overall rigour and coherence of the study. The Research Onion is particularly useful in complex research environments, such as education or business, where aligning methodology with philosophical assumptions and practical constraints is essential (Deshpande & Magerko, 2024). For example, Shahid et al. (2023) utilised the Research Onion to guide their study on the quantification and benchmarking of construction waste and its impact on costs in Pakistan. (Z. Wu et al., 2025) employed the research onion framework to investigate how innovation and entrepreneurship employee training programs enhance organisational commitment from the perspective of industry education integration. Additionally, (Orth & Maçada, 2020) applied the Research Onion in their systematic literature review exploring corporate fraud and inter-organisational relationships. These diverse applications highlight the Research Onion's flexibility and effectiveness in structuring methodological choices, thereby justifying its adoption in the current study.

The core research problem is located at the centre of this diagram, and it will be necessary to "peel away" each layer before reaching at the central point. These layers encompass research philosophy, methodology, strategy, choices, time horizon, and data collection methods. Together, they establish a clear and comprehensive framework for the entire research process.

Figure 4.1 Saunder's Research Onion

(Source: Saunders et al. (2019, p. 130))

4.3 Research Philosophy

Amaratunga & Baldry (2001) stated that research is based on philosophical views as a human action. Saunders et al. (2009) defined research as a broader term that encompasses a system of beliefs and assumptions related to the nature and evolution of knowledge. According to Sekaran (2003), while adopting a research method, researchers should be mindful of the philosophical commitments they undertake, as these significantly influence their actions and shape how they interpret the rationale behind their investigation. The phrase "research onion" was coined by Saunders et al., (2015) to define the research philosophy (Figure 4.1: Research Onion) where they divided the research process into flowing layers: philosophies, methodologies, choices, strategies, techniques, time frames and procedures. The research onion is a visual representation of your data collection possibilities that can help you to develop a study plan and arguably gives clarity and comprehensiveness of the various difficulties involved in research technique.

4.3.1 Philosophical Assumptions

According to (Burrell and Morgan, 2016) at each step of the research process, researcher create assumptions about the data and findings, whether or not he/she is aware of it. These can include, but are not limited to, beliefs about the nature of the world (ontological assumptions), about human knowledge (epistemological assumptions), and the extent researcher give to his/her own personal values (axiological assumptions) in the course of work. Additionally, these assumptions are vital in guiding a researcher's decision-making process concerning the formulation of research questions the choice of suitable procedures, and the interpretation of research results (Crotty, 1998).

4.3.1.1 Ontology

Bryman & Bell (2011) defined ontology as "one's opinion of what is true," which is the beginning point for most philosophical arguments. Ontology consists of subjectivism and objectivism, emphasizes on the nature of reality. The term "subjectivism" refers to the idea that social phenomena are formed by social actors based on their perceptions and actions. This is frequently linked to constructionism, or social constructionism. On the other hand, objectivism implies that social objects exist external to social actors (Saunders, 2009). Normally, subjectivism is associated with interpretivism's epistemological viewpoint, while objectivism is associated with positivism's epistemological viewpoint. Two of the most popular and important concepts in social science - organisation and culture can be used to highlight their disparities (Bryman & Bell, 2011).

This research adopts an objectivist ontological perspective, which asserts that social realities exist independently of social actors (Saunders, 2014). The study examines the relationships between various social constructs, specifically investigating how supply chain capabilities (including agility, collaboration, and traceability) influence supply chain resilience, circular economy practices, and sustainable supply chain performance. Additionally, it explores the moderating role of blockchain technology in these relationships. In line with the objectivist stance, the researcher maintains a detached position from the study's objectives, allowing for an unbiased examination of these phenomena

(Saunders et al., 2007). This approach enables a systematic and impartial analysis of the complex interplay between these supply chain elements and their broader impacts.

4.3.1.2 Epistemology

Epistemology is concerned with identifying what types of knowledge are considered valid and acceptable within a specific discipline (Saunders et al., 2009). Positivism and interpretivism are the two primary principles of epistemology (Collis and Hussey, 2009). The most effective approach to achieving a positivist perspective is to design experiments for key components that are accurately measured to test established hypotheses (Easterby-Smith et al., 2002). Knowledge is obtained through the aggregation of data that underpins for laws, and scientific inquiry should be conducted in a value-neutral way (Easterby-Smith et al., 2002). In contrast, interpretivism does not suppose any pre-existing reality; instead, the researcher aims to understand how individuals construct frameworks to help them make sense of their surroundings (Easterby-Smith et al., 2002).

This research aligns with the positivist paradigm by proposing multiple hypotheses that will be systematically tested, analysed, and measured using empirical data. This approach enables the study to examine the relationships between various supply chain elements in a structured, quantifiable manner, potentially yielding generalizable insights into supply chain dynamics and performance.

4.3.1.3 Axiology

Finally, axiology is defined as "a branch of philosophy that explores judgments about values" (Saunders et al., 2007). Axiology investigates the importance of the researcher's values inside the research process and their potential impact on the research's credibility. (Saunders et al., 2007). Furthermore, Saunders et al. (2007) recommended that researchers employ a variety of sources, concentrate on the subject of investigation, and adopt methods that reduce bias. Positivists argue that science and the research process are value-neutral, believing that the objects of their investigation remain unaffected by their findings. They seek to identify causal relationships between variables. Conversely, interpretivists (or phenomenologists) recognise that researchers possess values, even if these are not overtly articulated. Interpretivists seek to attain a profound comprehension of a certain context. These values play a crucial role in shaping what is accepted as fact and in guiding the conclusions drawn from that information (Collis and Hussey, 2003).

4.3.2 Multi-dimensional Continua of Philosophical Assumptions

Research philosophies are distributed in a multidimensional spectrum, as discussed by Niglas (2010), encompassing two contrasting extremes: objectivist and subjectivist.

4.3.2.1 Objectivism

Objectivism includes the core principles of the natural sciences, claiming that the social reality being examined prevail independently of social actors (Saunders et al., 2019). This implies that, from an ontological standpoint, objectivism encompasses the philosophical position of realism. According to an objectivist perspective, social and physical phenomena possess an intrinsic existence that is independent of individuals' subjective interpretations. Furthermore, these phenomena exhibit a tendency to be

universally applicable and durable in nature (Saunders et al., 2019). From an epistemological standpoint, objectivists aim to uncover the truth regarding the social realm. They accomplish this by analysing observable and measurable facts, which form the foundation for creating generalizations related to the broader social reality. From an axiological standpoint, objectivists aim to maintain the neutrality of their research by omitting values that may bias their conclusions. This technique is built on the assertion that social entities and actors exist as autonomous entities. Consequently, researchers strive to uphold objectivity by separating their personal opinions and beliefs during the rigorous scientific research process.

4.3.2.2 Subjectivism

According to (Saunders et al., 2019), subjectivism comprises the fundamental tenets of the arts and humanities, advocating that the formation of social reality is contingent upon the perceptions and ensuing actions of social actors (individuals). From an ontological perspective, subjectivism is aligned with nominalism, which is occasionally referred to as conventionalism. In its most extreme version, nominalism holds that the language we use, the conceptual frameworks we use, the perceptions we hold, and the actions we take as a result are what generate the order and structures of the social phenomena we investigate. Discussing various realities is more logical than focussing on a single universal reality, as individual experiences and perceptions of reality vary significantly (Burrell and Morgan 2016). A moderate variant of this concept is social constructionism. This theory suggests that reality is created via social interactions, where individuals within a society collaboratively create meanings and realities that are only partially shared. Essentially, reality emerges from intersubjective processes (Saunders et al., 2019). A comparison of different philosophical assumption types is given in the table 4.1 below.

Table 4-1 Philosophical assumptions and the objectivism – subjectivism dimension (Saunders et al., 2019, pp. 144)

Assumption type	Questions	Continua with two sets of extremes	
		Objectivism	Subjectivism
Ontology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •What is the nature of reality? • What is the world like? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reality is real -Exists externally - There is one true reality (universalism) -Reality consists of discrete entities (granular) - There is inherent order 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reality is nominal and defined by social conventions -Reality is socially constructed - Multiple realities exist (relativism) -Reality is fluid (process-oriented) - There is inherent chaos
Epistemology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •How do we acquire knowledge? •What counts as acceptable knowledge? •What defines high-quality data? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Embraces the assumptions of natural sciences -Based on facts -Quantitative data - Focus on observable phenomena -Seeks law-like generalizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Aligns with the notions of the arts and humanities -Emphasizes opinions -Includes written, spoken, and visual narratives -Considers attributed meanings - Focuses on individuals and specific contexts

Axiology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •What types of contributions to knowledge can be made? • What is the significance of values in research? •Should we strive for moral neutrality in research, or should our values influence the research process? •What is the appropriate approach to managing the values of study participants? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strives for value-free research -Emphasizes detachment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recognizes that values are integral, and reflexive -Values shape the research process
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4.4 Research Approach

Research approach dictates three main perspectives, deductive, inductive, or abductive (Bryman & Bell, 2007; Saunders et al., 2009). The deductive approach, which is most closely connected with positivism, begins by developing a hypothesis based on available data or theories and then developing a suitable research strategy to test it (Creswell, 2009). Saunders et al., (2009) defined the deductive approach as having three distinct characteristics: first, the relationship between the various variables is clarified; second, data are collected and analysed quantitatively; and third, data can be generalised to a larger population based on the conducted results and the nature of their relationship. Additionally, Bryman & Bell, 2007) discussed the deductive approach's several characteristics, including measurement, causality, generalizability, and replication. Bryman & Bell (2007) also discussed some disadvantages of the deductive approach, including the following:

- The measurement process gives the false impression of precision and accuracy.
- The relationship between daily life and research is constrained by predetermined methodologies and instruments.
- The deductive approach is guided by theoretical principles and hence follows a strict design approach that is unconcerned with the nature of the phenomenon being investigated.
- The deductive approach generates a statistical representation of social life based on the correlations between existent variables.

Contrary to the deductive technique, the inductive approach is defined as “the study in which theory is developed from the observation of social reality” (Collis & Hussey, 2013, p.43). Usually, data is collected in this type of research in the form of observations, interviews (structured or semi-structured), focus groups, and other methods, and then a new theory is derived after careful examination of the obtained data.

Unlike the deductive technique, which uses more rigid statistical criteria for data gathering and analysis, the inductive approach allows the researcher to gather data, engage with respondents, use various tools, and interpret the results in a social context. According to Saunders et al., (2009), the inductive technique is more flexible. The primary advantage of the inductive approach is that it enables the researcher to comprehend and acquire thorough understanding of the topic, as well as reveal potential participant traits in a social environment (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012). The biggest drawback of the inductive

technique is the researcher's bias, which might manifest as opinion during data gathering or interpretation during analysis (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012).

The abductive approach, like inductive, begins with real-life observations. The abductive approach is defined by Levin-Rozalis (2003) as a two-sided logic which incorporates basics of both deductive and inductive approaches. This integrated research approach is commonly used to mitigate the disadvantages of the two primary research approaches and is based on the idea that truth is co-constructed by the researcher and the subject of the inquiry (Saunders, et al., 2016). This signifies that an abduction analysis starts with the outcome, namely an observed occurrence, subsequently formulates a rule, and utilises a case to assess the outcome's dependability and validity (Kovács & Spens, 2005). A brief synopsis of the research approaches is provided in table 4.2.

Table 4-2 Deductive, Inductive and Abductive approaches (Saunders et al., 2019)

	Deductive	Inductive	Abductive
Logic	In deductive reasoning, if the premises are true, the conclusion must also be true.	In inductive reasoning, established premises lead to untested conclusions.	In abductive reasoning, known premises lead to testable conclusions.
Generalisability	Generalizes from the general to the specific.	Generalizes from the specific to the general.	Generalizes from the interactions between the specific and the general.
Use of data	Data collection is used to assess propositions or hypotheses related to an existing theory.	Data collection explores a phenomenon, identifies themes and patterns, and creates a conceptual framework.	Data collection explores a phenomenon, identifies themes and patterns, situates them within a conceptual framework, and tests this through subsequent data collection.
Theory	Focuses on theory falsification or verification	Aims at theory generation and development.	Involves theory generation or modification, incorporating existing theories where suitable to develop new theories or refine existing ones.
Philosophical underpinning	Associated with positivism (and pragmatism)	Linked to interpretivism, critical realism, postmodernism, and pragmatism.	Aligned with interpretivism, critical realism, postmodernism, and pragmatism.

4.5 Research Choice

Selecting an appropriate research method largely depends on the nature and objectives of the research questions (Hair et al., 2003). (Creswell et al., 2003) identifies three primary research approaches: quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods. However, these three approaches are not as distinct or

separate as they may initially appear. Quantitative and qualitative methods should not be viewed as rigid, mutually exclusive categories or polar opposites. Instead, they represent different points along a continuum (Newman & Benz, 1998). A study may lean more towards qualitative or quantitative methods depending on its aims, while mixed methods research occupies a position in the middle of this continuum, integrating elements from both traditions.

According to (Creswell, 2013) the distinction between qualitative and quantitative research is often described in terms of using words (qualitative) rather than numbers (quantitative), or in terms of employing open-ended questions (qualitative) versus closed-ended questions (quantitative). However, a more comprehensive way to understand the differences between these approaches is to consider the underlying philosophical assumptions guiding the research, the research strategies employed (such as quantitative experiments or qualitative case studies), and the specific methods used to implement those strategies (for example, collecting numerical data via instruments versus gathering qualitative data through observations) (Robson, 2011)

Moreover, the development of these approaches has followed a historical trajectory. Quantitative methods dominated research in the social sciences from the late 19th century through the mid-20th century. In the latter half of the 20th century, interest in qualitative research grew significantly, leading to the emergence and expansion of mixed methods research (Creswell, 2013). Given this background, it is helpful to consider clear definitions of these three key research approaches.

4.5.1 Quantitative Research

Quantitative research is frequently used in descriptive and causal studies, though it can also serve exploratory purposes. Rooted in the positivist tradition, it emphasizes objectivity, measurable variables, and hypothesis testing based on observable data (Hair et al., 2010). This approach involves gathering numerical data and analysing the relationships among variables through systematic, structured procedures. It relies on hypothesis-driven, deductive reasoning to derive conclusions from empirical evidence. A significant advantage of quantitative research is its capacity to work with large sample sizes, which enables researchers to test for statistical significance and generalize findings to broader populations. This strengthens both the reliability and practical applicability of the results.

4.5.2 Qualitative Research

In contrast, qualitative research focuses on words and meanings rather than numerical data (Bryman & Bell, 2003). It follows an inductive logic and is closely linked to the interpretivist paradigm, although they are not entirely synonymous. Qualitative methods encompass various techniques for collecting and analysing data to explore, generate, or refine theoretical insights (Van Maanen, 1979). The aim is to gain a deep understanding of social phenomena as they occur in natural contexts. One challenge associated with qualitative research is maintaining the credibility and trustworthiness of findings, especially given its typically smaller sample sizes. While it provides rich, contextual insights and helps uncover the reasons behind certain phenomena, it is sometimes criticized for being time-consuming, difficult to analyse, and less generalizable than quantitative approaches. Furthermore, qualitative

research carries the risk of researcher bias influencing the interpretation of data (Snow & Thomas, 1994). Nevertheless, qualitative research plays a crucial role in developing new theories and exploring areas that have not been extensively studied.

4.5.3 Mixed Method Research

Mixed methods research combines both qualitative and quantitative approaches, allowing researchers to gather numerical and textual data either simultaneously or in sequence. The result is a dataset that integrates both types of information. (Creswell et al., 2007 pp. 238) describe mixed methods as:

“A study strategy that incorporates both philosophical assumptions and inquiry methodologies. As a methodology, it implies philosophical assumptions that shape the collection and analysis of data, integrating both qualitative and quantitative data into one study or a series of studies. The fundamental principle of mixed methods research is that combining these two approaches offers a more thorough comprehension of study issues than depending on each method independently.”

The table (4.3) below provides a comparison of the main characteristics associated with quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods approaches.

Table 4-3 Research Methods (Creswell, 2014 pp. 17)

Quantitative Method	Qualitative Method	Mixed Methods Method
• Pre- determined	• Emerging methods	• Bothe predetermined and emerging methods
• Instrument based questions	• Open ended questions	• Bothe open ended and close ended questions
• Performance data, attitude data, observational data and census data	• Interview data, observation data, document data and audiovisual data	• Multiple forms of data drawing on all possibilities
• Statistical analysis	• Text and images analysis	• Statistical and text analysis
• Statistical interpretation	• Themes, patterns interpretation	• Across databases interpretation

4.6 Research Strategy

The term "research strategy" denotes the overarching plan of the researcher for tackling the research questions (Saunders et al., 2009). According to Saunders et al. (2009), a research project's approach should be determined by factors like the researcher's philosophical beliefs, the study questions and objectives, the available time and resources, and the scope of the research. A brief detail of seven different strategies is given below:

Experiments

The researcher analyses the intervention's implementation within the study group and evaluates the resulting outcomes (Williams, 2007).

Action Research

As stated by Marsick and Watkins (1997), action researchers believe that the best way to study complicated social processes is to intervene in them and then assess the results.

Ethnography

In this study, the researcher examines the daily actions of individuals to identify prevailing norms, beliefs, social structures, and other factors that influence the evolution of the group's culture over time (Williams, 2007).

Grounded Theory

“Grounded theory” denotes the researcher's endeavour to develop a general abstract theory regarding a specific process, action, or interaction, grounded in the perspectives of the study participants (Creswell, 2003).

Archival Research

This study involves the examination and selection of material for analysis from existing records and archives (Jackson, 2008). This approach is utilised in situations when there is already existing data (Jackson, 2008) and gathering new data would be inefficient or where ethical or logistical constraints make it impractical to perform an experiment examining the variables of interest (McBurney & White, 2010).

Case Studies

Robson (2002) defines a case study as a research method that involves the empirical analysis of a particular contemporary event within its actual context, utilising multiple sources of information. It is the most appropriate strategy for critical realist paradigm to address the research questions.

Phenomenological Research

Phenomenological research, according to Saunders et al. (2012), is a technique that tends to produce "qualitative data" that is usually highly rich but can also be subjective. Thus, small samples, usually a limited selection of meticulously selected case study businesses and/or individuals is employed to generate such data.

Surveys

Survey research is primarily used to gather data from a specific group of individuals or a certain demographic efficiently (Kotzab, 2005). The deductive approach (Saunders et al., 2007) is commonly connected with it, and it is a traditional methodology tool for supply chain and logistics studies. Oppenheim (1992, p. 100) noted that surveys are frequently conducted with inadequate design and planning, or without any design whatsoever. “The process of ‘fact-gathering’ can be exhilarating and alluring, with a questionnaire providing a rapid and seemingly effortless method; however, the design flaws are often overlooked until the results require interpretation.” In survey-based study, respondents are instructed to provide input in a certain sequence on a pre-set set of questions (Ibeh & Brock, 2004; Bryman & Bell, 2007; Saunders et al., 2009). A variety of survey-based research methodologies are documented in the literature, as summarised in table 4.4 which was adapted from (Bryman & Bell (2015).

Table 4-4 Types of Surveys (Bryman & Bell, 2007, p.231)

Features	Mail questionnaire	Web survey	Telephonic interview	Face to face interview	Drop and collect
Cost	Cheap	Cheapest	Moderate	Expensive	Moderate
Speed	Slowest	Fastest	Fast	Slow to moderate	Fast
Length	Moderate	Moderate	Short	Longest	Long
Response rate	Lowest	Moderate	Moderate	Highest	Highest

Online surveys have grown significantly in popularity during the last few years. Online surveys have emerged as a predominant methodology in marketing research, utilised by 59% of researchers (Hair et al., 2010) and when compared to more traditional means of survey like postal, email, or telephone, this one has some distinctive advantages (Grant & Teller, 2005) . There are pros and cons of both traditional and web-based survey methods as shown in the table 4.5.

Table 4-5 Advantages and Disadvantages of Traditional and Web-based Survey (Grant et al., 2005, p.2)

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Traditional Survey (Self-administered, Postal or Mail Surveys)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Control over the survey process - No clustering of interviewees - Absence of interviewer biases - Low administration costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Low response rate -High non-response rate - Lack of external validity due to non-response -No control over how or when surveys are completed
Modern Survey (Web-based or Online Survey)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quick response time - Low variable expenditures - Easy for researchers and participants - No media gap - High rate of item response 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Low overall questionnaire response rate -High initial fixed cost -Limited control over the sample -Potential for coverage error

Considering the merits and drawbacks of various survey types, the self-administered survey has a better chance of being employed in this study as the investigation and the nature of the problem and researcher aims to comprehend the food and drink manufacturing industries in UK. Therefore, the Google forms was deemed more expedient considering time limitations. Comprehensive explanations and instructions pertaining to each area of the questionnaire will be supplied within the form. In order to achieve a satisfactory response rate, various reminder messages will be sent to the responders, in addition to personal contact attempts.

4.7 Researcher's Paradigm and Philosophical Stance

Burrell & Morgan (1979) underlined the differences between employing positivism and non-positivism paradigms to "conceptualise social science in terms of four sets of assumptions linked to ontology, epistemology, human nature, and methodology," (p.503). Additionally, it is critical for all researchers to be conscious of their own paradigm, which will affect their research and how it is performed, even though there is no such thing as a correct or incorrect paradigm.

The selection of a research paradigm is influenced by the research questions and objectives. (Thomas, 2004). As the core objective of the research is to explore the correlation between BCT, SCR and CEP in UK food manufacturing sector, the positivist philosophical assumption seemed to be the most appropriate fit for this investigation.

Before settling on this approach, the following considerations were considered:

- Positivism denotes the approach of engaging with observable social realities, whereby the resultant research yields law-like generalisations like to those generated by physical and natural sciences” (Remenyi & Williams, 1995, p. 33). The positivist technique separates the facts from values, largely based on quantitative data where propositions are founded on facts and hypothesis are tested against these facts (Robson & McCartan, 2016). Therefore, in this research multiple hypotheses are proposed and will be tested, analysed and quantified.
- This research pertains to social subject wherein the researcher aims to provide a rational explanation of relationship among variables by identifying, measuring, and evaluating them while maintaining a separation from the study's objective (Saunders et al., 2015). Thus, the positivist approach could be defended from objectivist stance of ontology.
- The positivist technique is typically linked to quantitative research that uses a deductive approach (Bryman et al., 2007). This approach will not only help to build and test the established theories but also yields more robust measurements of association between variables. The results will therefore be generalised to a larger population.
- The research objective necessitates a clear conceptual framework that explicitly defines the relationships between constructs and employs precise measurements. The application of quantitative methods, such as statistical approaches, can effectively uncover the connections between different constructs. These connections provide insights into the patterns that arise from the interaction of causal forces (Modell, 2007) and help to develop a comprehensive framework.
- A survey that concurrently examines many factors, assesses various variables, and explores multiple hypotheses is deemed appropriate for gathering responses from a larger population of a specific group of individuals (Kotzab, 2005). Due to its larger sample size and ability to test variables and structures, the survey can be utilized to draw conclusions, thus their inferences can be generalized (Bhattacharjee, 2012; Zikmund, Carr, and Griffin, 2012). Therefore, this study will employ a survey-based approach to gather data from managers of food manufacturing companies in the UK.

Further, table 4.6 provides a detailed design of the study and the justification of selection of each aspect of research design of the current study.

Table 4-6 A brief overview of the research design of the current study

Research Design	Available Research Design Options	Selected Research Design	Justification of the Selected Research Design
Ontology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subjective • Objective 	Objective	This study follows the objectivist stance of ontology. Which postulate that social realities existed independently of social actors (Saunders, 2014). Therefore, this research pertains to social subjects where impact of SC capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability) on SC resilience and CEP, sustainable supply chain performance and moderating role of BCT is assessed and the researcher is detached from the study's goal (Saunders et al., 2007).
Epistemology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positivism • Interpretivism • Critical theory • Critical realism 	Positivism	Positivism refers as “Working with a tangible social reality, the outcome of such research can yield law-like generalizations akin to those generated by physical and natural sciences” (Remenyi et al., 1998). The positivist technique separates the facts from values, largely based on quantitative data where propositions are founded on facts and hypothesis are tested against these facts (Robson and McCartan, 2016). In this research multiple hypotheses are proposed and will be tested, analysed, and measured.
Research Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deductive • Inductive • Abductive 	Deductive	Deductive approach starts with the formulation of a theory that undergoes a rigorous evaluation (Saunders et al., 2007). Therefore, this study used deductive strategy starts from theory and seek to explain the causal relationship between variables (SC capabilities, SC resilience, CE practices, sustainable supply chain performance and BCT).
Research Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative • Quantitative • Mixed methods 	Quantitative	The study is using a quantitative method to testing objective theories by looking at the relationships between different variables.
Quantitative Research Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiments • Surveys 	Surveys	The primary goal of survey research is to efficiently collect data from a targeted group of individuals or a specific demographic (Kotzab et al., 2006). The main aim of this study is to examine the influence of supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability) on supply chain resilience and circular economy practices along with the moderating effect of BCT on sustainable supply chain performance. This necessitates gathering data from a large sample of individuals, especially when employing the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) technique for data analysis
Data Collection Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Custom surveys • Telephonic surveys • Web surveys • Omnibus surveys • Self-administered surveys 	Self-administered surveys	Self-administered surveys are frequently employed in research due to their cost-effectiveness and convenience for collecting data from a large sample (Olsen et al., 2004). Therefore, this study has opted for self-administered surveys as the data collection method.

Sampling Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Probability sampling • Random • Satisfied • Systematic cluster • Non-probability sampling • Convenience • Quota • Purposive • Snowball 	Random	<p>A multistage random sampling technique is utilized since our population is sector-specific, requiring respondents who are either adopting or considering the adoption of Blockchain technology (BCT) and Circular Economy (CE) practices. The unit of analysis for this study is organizations. The target survey participants include supply chain managers (covering operations, logistics, sales, production, purchasing, procurement, and distribution) as well as IT managers. They were selected because they are believed to possess the most in-depth understanding of the companies' supply chains and the relevant innovative technologies.</p>
Data Analysis Technique	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regression • Descriptive statistics • One-way ANOVA • Missing value analysis • Reliability analysis • Factor analysis • Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) 	Descriptive statistics, Factor analysis, Structural Equation Modelling	<p>The construct's validity was evaluated through factor analysis and reliability analysis. The phenomena of interest were analysed descriptively. Lastly, the hypotheses were tested using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM).</p>

4.8 Data Collection Techniques and Analysis

4.8.1 Population and Sampling

A population refers to a full set of items or events that are relevant to a certain topic or experiment (Saunders et al, 2009) and the sample constitutes a subset of the population chosen for research (Bryman, 2008). According to Saunders et al. (2015), the researcher should consider a variety of aspects while designing a sample, including the nature of the research problem, objectives, time, and budget.

Sampling is an essential component of the research process before moving on to data collection. According to Saunders et al. (2015), there are four key issues to consider about when designing a sample: 1) the sample approach (probability or non-probability), 2) sample framing, 3) sample size, and 4) response rate. Sampling techniques can be categorised into two types: probability sampling and non-probability sampling (Saunders et al., 2007).

4.8.1.1 Probability Sampling

Bryman & Bell (2011) characterised the probability sampling approach as one in which the sample is chosen through random selection, guaranteeing that each unit in the population possesses a known and equal likelihood of being chosen. This method is designed to enhance the representativeness of the sample. This indicates that you are capable of addressing research questions and fulfilling objectives that need statistical estimation of population characteristics from a sample (Saunders at al 2007). The table 4.7 shows the probability sampling techniques.

Table 4-7 Probability Sampling Techniques (Easterby-Smith et al. 2012, p.226-227)

Probability sampling techniques	Details	Advantages
Simple random sampling	Every sample entity has an equal chance of being part of the sample	Easy to draw up a list of random numbers as a basis for selecting a sample
Stratified random sampling	Divide the population into small groups and then take a simple random sample within each group	Small (advantage) but important parts of the population are missed altogether (disadvantage)
Systematic random sampling	Generate a list in some form or other of the units in the population that the researcher is interested in	The list is essentially organized randomly, so that bias is not introduced
Cluster sampling	Divide the population into clusters then sample all units from within the selected cluster	The study allows the use of local research staff who are familiar with the language and culture of each country
Multi-stage sampling	Combine together the methods described above in order to achieve higher operational and technical efficiency	To balance the need for representativeness of the sample with the highest possible cost effectiveness

4.8.1.2 Non-Probability Sampling

Non-probability sampling refers to a sample that has not been chosen by a random selection procedure. This indicates that certain units within the population have a higher probability of being picked than others” (Bryman & Bell, 2011, p.176). It is not viable to address research questions or achieve objectives necessitating statistical assessments of the population's characteristics (Saunders at al 2007).

While it is possible to make generalisations about the population from non-probability samples, such conclusions lack statistical validity. The table 4.8 depicted the non-probability sampling techniques.

Table 4-8 Non-Probability Sampling Techniques (Easterby-Smith et al. 2012, p.228-229)

Probability sampling techniques	Details	Advantages
Convenience sampling	Selecting sample units on the basis of how easily accessible they are	Very common and convenient
Quota sampling	Divide the relevant population up into category and then selection continues until a sample of a specific size is achieved within each categories	Sampling can be controlled for certain characteristics
Purposive sampling	The researcher has a clear idea of what sample units are needed, and then approaches potential sample members to check whether they meet eligibility criteria	Reasonable control over sample content
Snowball sampling	A form of convenient sample but with this method, the researcher was able to make initial contact with a small group of people relevant to the research topic and use these to make contact with others	Suitable for samples where individuals vary and it is difficult to identify who belongs to the population

4.9 Justification for Using Multistage Random Sampling

Multistage sampling is a flexible and efficient sampling method that can incorporate two or more sampling strategies at different stages of the sampling plan (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). For example, probability sampling could be used in the initial stages to select clusters, ensuring a broad and representative base. In later stages, non-probability methods could be employed to select specific units within those clusters based on characteristics or research needs. This combination can enhance the flexibility and applicability of the sampling plan to various research contexts.

Multistage random sampling was employed to identify a representative cohort of participants for the current investigation that accurately reflects the characteristics of the broader population under study. The UK food and drink manufacturing sector, the largest manufacturing industry (Food and Drink Report 2022, DBO., 2022), was the focus. Initially, a stratified method was employed, and UK food and drink manufacturers were divided into clusters based on their size: small, medium, and large. Small enterprises are classified as having fewer than 50 workers, those with 50 to 249 workers were defined as medium enterprises, while enterprises having more than 250 employees were categorised as large (Food statistics in your pocket - GOV.UK (www.gov.uk)). The distribution of small, medium, and large enterprises is given in the table below 4.9.

Table 4-9 Population of the Study

Small	Medium	Large
7,530	755	280

The current study excluded small enterprises from the sample, as blockchain technology (BCT) is a recent invention with high associated implementation costs, and the idea of a circular economy is rather

recent. It is anticipated that the number of respondents from small enterprises would be limited due to these factors. In the later stages of the research, proportionate sampling method was employed to calculate the final sample. Various industry reports and government websites were utilized to locate medium and large food and drink manufacturers in the UK as shown in the table 4.10.

Table 4-10 Proportionate Sample

Enterprises Size	Population	Population %	Sample taken
Medium	755	73%	204
Large	280	27%	76
Total	1,035	100%	280

4.10 Unit of Analysis

The unit of analysis of this study was firms. The target survey subjects were supply chain (including operations, logistics, sales, production, purchasing, procurement and distribution) and IT managers. They were approached because it was believed that they would have the most comprehensive knowledge of the inner workings of the companies' supply chains and associated innovative technologies.

Previous studies like Karmaker et al., 2023; Cheng et al., 2022; Egwuonmwu et al., 2022; Nayal et al., 2021; Queiroz et al., 2020 and Duby et al., 2020 considered managerial employees as appropriate respondents for measuring supply chain capabilities, SC resilience, CE practices, BCT and sustainable supply chain performance. Furthermore, due to their hierarchical positions within their respective firms, these individuals possessed the highest level of knowledge and information pertaining to the factors under investigation.

4.11 Sample Size

It is fundamental to specify the sample size within target population. According to Bryman et al., (2007), a large sample size will not assure precision in a study, wasting time and money. There are two broader criteria available for the computation of sample size. The first criteria are determined by the statistical method used and the level of statistical power expected to be needed (Hair et al., 2011; Mitchell, 1993). However, when conducting statistical analyses such as SEM, a small sample size can reduce the accuracy and reliability of the results (Hair et al., 2017). A comprehensive route model, according to Goodboy et al., (2017), should have at least 200 participants. A sample size can range from 50 to 1,000, with 50 being the minimum and 1,000 being the largest, depending on model complexity (Goodboy et al., 2017; Hair et al., 2017). According to Schreiber (2008) a sample size can be computed in terms of the number of respondents per estimated parameter, while also accounting for the model's complexity, which includes the number of constructs and variables. For instance, a sample size of 300 or more is required for a model with six or more components and three indicators in each (Hair et al., 2017). Furthermore, Schreiber (2017) noted that 10 respondents is a frequently recognised figure for every estimated parameter within the model.

The second criteria are based on the method employed by Krejcie and Morgen (1970) was utilised to determine the necessary sample size, considering the size of the population.

$$s = \frac{X^2 \cdot NP(1 - P)}{d^2(N - 1) + X^2P(1 - P)}$$

Where s represents the requisite sample size, X denote the chi-square table value for one degree of freedom at the specified confidence level, N signify the population size, P indicate the population percentage (assumed to be 0.5), and d reflect the degree of precision stated as a proportion of 0.5. A total of 1035 medium and large food and drink enterprises were identified through the utilization of secondary sources. Where X is 1.96 at 5% significance level. Using these values into the given formula:

$$s = \frac{(1.96)^2(1035)0.5(1 - 0.5)}{0.05^2(1035 - 1) + (1.96)^20.5(1 - 0.5)}$$

$$s = 280$$

Based on the above calculation, Krejcie and Morgan (1970) scientific guideline calculated the sample size of this research is 280 food and drink organizations. In the current study, 280 organisations will be surveyed using the multi-respondent strategy.

4.12 Sampling Strategy

The sample for the study was drawn from a national database of UK food and drink manufacturers, which initially contained over 8,000 companies. To focus on medium and large enterprises, filters were applied to exclude small companies with fewer than 50 employees. This resulted in a pool of 1,035 medium and large organizations, with approximately 755 medium-sized (50-249 employees) and 280 large businesses (250+ employees).

Following scientific sampling principles established by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), the final sample size was set at 280 organizations. From these 280 companies, supply chain (including operations, logistics, sales, production, purchasing, procurement and distribution) and IT managers were identified as target respondents due to their knowledge of overall supply chain operations and firm performance. A total of 750 questionnaires were distributed across these 280 enterprises, allowing for multiple respondents per company.

4.13 Research Instrument Development

After establishing the research design and sampling method, the subsequent step in the research design entailed the theoretical and practical determination of how to measure the key variables in the study. The development of questions pertaining to key variables, such as supply chain capabilities, SCRES, CE practices, BCT and sustainable supply chain performance was accomplished by examining existing research studies that have already measured these variables. An established instrument improves data collection, which yields precise results. Therefore, the development of an instrument is crucial for achieving the desired level of success in a research project.

4.13.1 Scale Development

According to DeVellis (2012) scales are measurement instruments that consist of a group of items that are combined into a composite score and are aimed to show levels of theoretical variables that are not easily observed by direct mean. We create scales when we seek to quantify things that we assume exist based on our theoretical understanding of the universe but cannot directly measure. Likert (1932) established five-point rating scale to measure attitude statements. This seven-point Likert scale will be used in online survey to test practitioners' perceptions on the existing role BCT in SCRES and CE practices to acquire a better understanding of the relationship between these variables to improve supply chain sustainable performance. The usage of such a scale result in high levels of reliability and validity.

4.13.2 Survey Instrument

According to Ritchie et al. (2003), to gather the most relevant data from respondents, a survey questionnaire must be designed in such a way that it is simple, valid, and reliable. As stated by (Zikmund, 2003), the two most important criteria of a successful questionnaire are relevance and accuracy. The term "relevance" refers to the idea that only information that is directly related to the study's goals and objectives should be included in the questionnaire. Accuracy refers to how reliable and valid the data is.

The current study employed a self-administered questionnaire that had been previously examined, deemed reliable, and validated for the purpose of data collection. In order to achieve the intended objective, the researcher made modifications to the scales employed in prior investigations. A 7-point Likert scale served as the foundation for the study instrument's data gathering as shown in the below table 4.11.

Table 4-11 Summary of Variable's Measures

Constructs	Source	No. of Items
SC capabilities (SCCs)		(15)
SC Agility (Ag)	Adapted from Li et al., (2022); Baah et al., (2020)	5
SC Collaboration (Col)	Adapted from Baah et al., (2020)	5
SC Traceability (Tr)	Adapted from Cousins et al, (2019)	5
SC resilience (SCRES)	Adapted from Ponomarov., (2012)	7
Circular Economy Practices (CEP)	Adapted from Le, T.T., et al., (2022); (Riggs et al., 2023)	8
Blockchain Technology (BCT)	Adapted from Duby et al., (2020); Zelbst et al., (2019); Dehghani et al., (2021)	5
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)	Adapted from Le, T.T., et al., (2022); Kumar at al., (2019); Bag et al., (2020)	5

4.13.2.1 Scale for SC Capabilities (SCCs)

Capabilities are broken down in the literature into two categories: operational capabilities (ordinary or static capabilities) and higher order capabilities (dynamic capabilities) (Wang and Ahmed, 2007, Danneels, 2016, Teece, 2018). Static capabilities function like established day-to-day procedures within

an organisation, allowing for consistent distribution of products and services and they do not create a long-term competitive advantage as they rarely interact with the environment (Winter, 2003, Wang and Ahmed, 2007, Zahra et al., 2006, Cepeda and Vera, 2007). Dynamic capabilities (DCs) refer to higher-order capabilities that are intentionally developed and possess distinctive qualities in order to construct, integrate, or reconfigure operational capabilities in response to external environment (Teece et al., 1997). SC capabilities refer to an organization's ability to effectively recognise, employ, and integrate both internal and external resources and information in order to enable the entirety of supply chain activities (Bharadwaj, 2000; Collis, 1994). The researcher envisions the SC capabilities as a higher-order construct and considering the following three dimensions of SC capabilities in the model: agility, collaboration and traceability. The study operationalized the constructs of these key SC capabilities based on SC resilience and implementation of CE practices focus criteria to measure the sustainable performance of food supply chains in UK. The scale consists of 15 items, 5 items for each agility, supply chain collaboration and traceability. Previously reported Cronbach's α value for agility was 0.903 (Li et al., 2022), for collaboration Cronbach α was 0.767 (Baah et al., 2020) and for traceability Cronbach α was 0.89 (Cousins et al., 2019). The reliability scores of agility, collaboration and traceability are shown in the table 4.12.

Table 4-12 Reliability Scores of SC capabilities (SCCs)

Constructs	α Score
SC Agility (SCA)	0.903
SC Collaboration (SCCO)	0.767
SC Traceability (SCT)	0.89

4.13.2.2 Scale for SC Resilience (SCRES)

According to Christopher and Peck (2004), the concept of SCRES refers to the capacity of a system to revert to its initial state or transition to a more favourable state following a disruption. The definition of SCRES that is commonly recognised in academic literature is the one proposed by Ponomarov and Holcomb in 2009. As per their assertion, SC resilience (SCRES) can be characterised as the capacity of a supply chain to adapt to unforeseen circumstances, effectively address disruptions, and restore operations to ensure the desired level of interconnectedness and control over its structure and functionality.

In the current study, SC resilience (SCRES) had been studying as the dependent variable. To measure SC resilience 7 items were adopted from Ponomarov (2012). The reliability score of SCRES is given in the below table 4.13.

Table 4-13 Reliability Scores for SC Resilience (SCRES)

Constructs	α Score
SC resilience (SCRES)	0.874

4.13.2.3 Scale for Circular Economy Practices (CEP)

Circular economy (CE) is an approach that seeks to convert traditional linear production and consumption systems into circular models. The implementation of CE is achieved via the execution of certain activities and practises (Schroeder et al., 2019). The concept of these CE practices (CEP) is frequently framed within the context of "R" frameworks, such as the 3R, reduce, reuse and recover (Cui et al., 2021), 4R (reduce, reuse, recycle and recover) (Gebhardt et al., 2022), or even 9R (refuse, rethink, reduce, reuse, repair, refurbish, remanufacturing, repurpose, recycling and recover) (Potting et al., 2017). In this study, CE practices serve as the dependent variable, adapting the approach of Le et al. (2022). Le et al. (2022) developed the Circular Economy Practices (CEP) construct consisting of eight items, drawing from relevant studies by Kuzma et al. (2021), Hazen et al. (2021), and Pizzi et al. (2022). These items represent typical CE practices, encompassing activities such as converting waste into production inputs, sharing resources, saving energy, promoting sourcing from the circular economy, adding value to products and materials, creating valuable inputs for supply chain partners, and enabling responsiveness to market fluctuations. The reliability score for circular economy practices is given in the below table 4.14.

Table 4-14 Reliability Scores for Circular Economy Practices (CEP)

Construct	α Score
Circular Economy Practices (CEP)	0.925

4.13.2.4 Scale for Blockchain Technology (BCT)

Supply chains that utilise Blockchain technology will own a distributed ledger system. Every transaction conducted by participants of the supply chain is recorded and organised into a block. The transactions within the supply chain members are interconnected and grouped into blocks, resulting in a chain of interconnected and immutable entries. If any alterations are made to the Information, it will become apparent to the participants of the supply chain that the information has been compromised. It could be used as a potential means of trade protection. Various industries, including finance (Treleaven et al., 2017), healthcare (Zhang et al., 2018), and retail (Karamitsos et al., 2018), have already directed their efforts towards exploring and using this technology (Dehghani et al., 2020). BCT has recently found its way into the food supply chains as well (Mao et al., 2018; Dehghani et al., 2021). The rise of this system can be attributed to the development of programmes that can function without the need for a central server or other trustworthy third party. Therefore, it is expected that blockchain will be employed in markets for products with relatively high information costs, such as those with a short life cycle, such as agricultural products (Tian, 2016) or high-value commodities (Tian, 2016).

In this study, the focus of analysis pertains to food and drink manufacturers, encompassing both medium-sized and large organisations that have implemented blockchain technology. The study included a construct item pertaining to the adoption of BCT, as outlined by Duby et al., (2020); Zelbst et al., (2019); Dehghani et al., (2021), The reliability of this construct was assessed using Cronbach's α , yielding a value of 0.93 is given in table 4.15.

Table 4-15 Reliability Scores for Blockchain Technology (BCT)

Constructs	α Score
Blockchain Technology (BCT)	0.93

4.13.2.5 Scale for Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)

The idea of sustainability lacks inherent quantifiable metrics, but it is contingent upon other operational orientations, including the economic, social, and environmental dimensions, with which it is interconnected (Kumar et al., 2019). It is important to understand that these three dimensions are separate facets that cannot be substituted by any alternative dimension. For instance, it is important to note that social outcomes cannot be replaced by environmental outcomes, just as economic outcomes cannot be substituted for environmental outcomes. All three dimensions each have their unique and essential roles in bringing significant value to the performance of organisations; therefore, all three are indispensable. These attributes in conjunction with recommendations provided in the scholarly literature (Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001; Petter et al., 2007; Henseler et al., 2009; Kumar et al., 2019; Le et al., 2022). In line with Le et al. (2022), this study adapts their approach to develop a construct for sustainable supply chain performance. By leveraging the methodology established by Le et al., the research aims to create a comprehensive framework that effectively captures the essential elements of sustainability within supply chain. The table 4.16 presents the reliability values of the items.

Table 4-16 Reliability Scores for Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)

Constructs	α Score
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)	0.949

4.14 Questionnaire Design

According to Ritchie et al. (2003), to gather the most relevant data from respondents, a survey questionnaire must be designed in such a way that it is simple, valid, and reliable. As stated by (Zikmund, 2003), the two most important criteria of a successful questionnaire are relevance and accuracy. The term "relevance" refers to the idea that only information that is directly related to the study's goals and objectives should be included in the questionnaire. Accuracy refers to how reliable and valid the data is.

The survey questionnaire will be pre-tested by 2 specialists from UK's food industries before it was examined in its final stage. Questions relating to measure demographic Information, SC capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability), SC resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance constituted the main elements of the survey.

To get information about the respondent's demographics, simple categorical scales is used and to get information about the respondent's perceptions, 7-point Likert scales will be used. According to (Bryman & Bell, 2007), this type of Likert scale is commonly employed in survey research to convey people's perceptions in terms of ordinal level categories. Although Likert scales are technically ordinal, there is strong empirical evidence supporting their treatment as interval scales (Murray, 2013; Carifio & Perla, 2008; Preston & Colman, 2000). When multiple Likert items are summed or averaged to create

a composite score, the resulting data are often considered approximately continuous and suitable for parametric analysis (Koo and Yang, 2025). Carifio and Perla (2008) address the long-standing “ordinal vs interval” debate and conclude that Likert scales (collections of items) are essentially interval in nature and thus can be analyzed parametrically with all the associated benefits and power. Preston and Colman (2000) found that a 7-point response scale offers optimal reliability and validity, with minimal gains beyond that. The difference in data quality between a 7-point scale and a continuous scale is negligible, indicating that aggregated 7-point Likert items can effectively approximate interval-level data. Consequently, the 7-point scales employed in this study have been regarded as continuous (quasi-interval) data, as they are widely shown to approximate interval properties adequately and are supported by empirical research (H. Wu & Leung, 2017) . All the questions will be mixed, and questions on the same concept will not place next to each other, to avoid the respondent's common answer bias, i.e., identical questions appearing sequentially.

Questionnaire development:

A scale developed in Chapter 3 is used to evaluate the data's reliability and validity. The questionnaire was meticulously constructed according to Churchill's nine-step approach, (1979). The following are the nine steps that composed the strategy:

1. Development of questionnaire protocols: Protocols for the questionnaires were established following a rigorous literature study. A 7-point Likert scale will be used to evaluate whether participant agreed or disagreed with a statement by marking a tick next to it (strongly disagree, disagree, slightly disagree, neutral, somewhat agree, agree, and strongly agree). This size was created to address concerns about attenuation caused by range restrictions (Schreiber, 2017; Kwak et al., 2018). The questions were phrased in such a way as to encourage responders to complete the survey without becoming confused. Move rover, this scale is useful for this research since it gives an interval or ratio base (Likert, 1932), which is a well-known statistical analysis scale (Hair et al., 2010).
2. Revision and modification of survey questionnaire: After the questionnaire was drafted, there were a few revisions to be made. The researcher and her supervisors will go over the new questionnaire together to examine for any errors. This procedure also assisted in anticipating any future issues. At this stage, errors and ambiguity should be reduced or removed.
3. Survey Pre-test: The questionnaire will be distributed to participants for a pre-testing. Feedback and suggestions will be given to the researcher within three weeks for evaluation and amendment of the questionnaire before the main survey is distributed. Cronbach's alpha will be used to determine the reliability of pre-test data.
4. Finalization of the questionnaire protocols: After pre-testing final questionnaire will be developed and ready for on-line survey.
5. Questionnaire distribution: The respondents will be from the food and drink industry and the questionnaire will be receiving by email. On-line surveys or Microsoft Word documents will

be used by respondents to fill out and return the questionnaire. In addition to the questionnaire, the responder consent form will be included in the email.

6. Follow-up and reminder: Respondents will receive an email two weeks before the deadline reminding them that their questionnaires are due. Respondents who needed more time will be given an extra amount of time to increase the response rate.
7. Questionnaire collection and coding: After receiving back the questionnaire, the data will be entered, coded, and prepared for analysis.
8. Data analysis: The results of the questionnaire will be analysed using statistical analysis such as means, standard deviation, factor analysis, and AMOS by SPSS 20.

4.14.1 Advantages and Disadvantages of a 7-Point Scale

A 7-point scale offers several advantages in research contexts. It provides greater sensitivity than shorter scales, enabling respondents to express finer distinctions in their attitudes or perceptions (Ibrahim, 2025). Studies have shown that scales with more points up to around seven can enhance measurement reliability and better capture variability compared to 5-point scales (Pallant, 2007). Moreover, the presence of a balanced midpoint allows respondents to choose a neutral option when they have no strong opinion, which helps reduce forced choices and potential response bias (Schaeffer & Presser, 2003). However, there are also disadvantages associated with using a 7-point scale. It can impose a higher cognitive load on respondents, making it slightly more demanding to use, especially in telephone or verbal surveys, which may result in confusion or inconsistent answers (Pallant, 2010). Additionally, there is a risk of central tendency bias, where some participants default to the midpoint or middle categories to avoid expressing extreme views, potentially masking true attitudes (Preston & Colman, 2000). Cultural differences also play a role, as respondents in certain cultures might avoid using the extreme points on the scale, thus reducing the effective range of responses and limiting the scale's discriminative power (Harzing, 2006).

4.15 Pretest

Before initiating large-scale data collection for this study, the research instrument underwent a two-step validation process. The first step involved pretesting, a crucial phase in developing a robust questionnaire. As emphasized by Dillman (1991) and Iacobucci and Churchill (2009), pretesting is an essential precursor to pilot testing, ensuring the foundation of a well-constructed survey instrument. This initial validation step helps identify and address potential issues in the questionnaire design, enhancing its effectiveness and reliability before proceeding to the subsequent stages of the research. Initially, the research instrument was presented to experts, including Ph.D. qualified academicians from the relevant field, a language expert, and a manager from the food and drink industry, to obtain their feedback on the wording of the items and ensure face and content validity. Based on their recommendations, the questionnaire was revised accordingly. Given that the variables in this study pertain to supply chain capabilities, resilience, CE, sustainability and blockchain, the content of the questionnaire was validated by experts in these specific areas.

4.16 Pilot Testing

A pilot study serves as a valuable tool for assessing the internal consistency, identifying flaws, omissions, and biases in the items of an instrument (Creswell, 2013). Sekaran (2006) asserts that conducting a pilot study can effectively conserve both time and resources. Furthermore, the act of assessing the reliability of a questionnaire helps in enhancing the quality of its items (Nor, 2005). Ghazali (2011) posits that reliability pertains to the extent to which a scale demonstrates consistency in measuring a latent variable.

Cronbach's alpha (1951) values will be used in the current investigation. Cronbach's alpha is considered acceptable when it approaches a value of 1. Conversely, if the value is less than 0.50, it is considered unacceptable as shown in the table 4.17.

Table 4-17 Cronbach's Alpha Values

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.90$	Excellent
$0.90 > \alpha \geq 0.80$	Good
$0.80 > \alpha \geq 0.70$	Acceptable
$0.70 > \alpha \geq 0.60$	Questionable
$0.60 > \alpha \geq 0.50$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.50$	Unacceptable

Source: (George, 2003)

4.16.1 Results of Pilot Testing

The pilot study results led to several improvements in the questionnaire. Items exhibiting low reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values below the threshold of 0.60, were identified and addressed. A sample of 30 managers from the population was used in the pilot study to assess the instrument's reliability. The reliability analysis was conducted using SPSS, and table 4.18 presents the reliability scores for the questionnaire items in the pilot study.

Table 4-18 Pilot Testing Results

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha
SC Agility (Ag)	0.84
SC Collaboration (Col)	0.89
SC Traceability (Tr)	0.76
Blockchain Technology (BCT)	0.75
SC resilience (SCRES)	0.71
Circular Economy Practices (CEP)	0.89
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)	0.81

4.17 Data Analysis

Analysis of data conducted with the goal of answering the research questions given in the introductory chapter. In this section, all hypotheses were tested using statistical analysis. As this study employs a quantitative research approach, hence SPSS 20 and AMOS is used for statistical analysis. Many social

science researchers rely on and make considerable use of this statistical tool. This study examined the relationship between independent, mediating, and dependent variables based on causal relationships among variables. The study employed a cross-sectional research design, wherein data will be collected within a specific time frame.

4.18 Non-Parametric Tests

4.18.1 Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test

The Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test is a non-parametric statistical procedure that serves as an alternative to the paired-samples t-test. It is particularly suitable when the assumption of normality is violated, or when dealing with ordinal data. This test is used to compare two related samples, matched samples, or repeated measurements on a single group in order to determine whether there is a statistically significant difference in their population mean ranks (Field, 2024).

The procedure involves calculating the difference between pairs of observations, discarding pairs with no difference, and ranking the absolute values of the differences. Positive and negative signs are then assigned based on the direction of the difference. The test statistic is obtained from the smaller of the sums of the positive and negative ranks, which is then compared to critical values or converted to a Z-score in larger samples. A significance value of less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) indicates that there is a statistically significant difference between the two related groups, whereas a significance value greater than 0.05 suggests no meaningful difference.

4.18.2 Friedman Test

The Friedman Test is a non-parametric alternative to the repeated-measures ANOVA and is used when analysing more than two related samples (Friedman, 1937). It is appropriate in cases where the same subjects are measured under different conditions or over multiple time points. This test evaluates whether there are statistically significant differences between the distributions of the related groups.

The procedure involves ranking the scores for each subject across all conditions, then summing the ranks for each condition. The test statistic is based on the differences in these rank sums across groups. A statistically significant result ($p < 0.05$) suggests that at least one of the related groups differs significantly from the others, although the Friedman Test does not specify where the differences lie. Post-hoc analyses, such as the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test with Bonferroni correction, are often applied to identify the specific pairs of groups that differ significantly.

The Friedman Test is commonly applied in research where multiple related measures are collected, such as comparing participants' responses to different treatments, interventions, or time intervals.

4.18.3 Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation

Correlation analysis is employed to examine and gain a preliminary understanding of the relationships between the variables of interest. It provides an indication of whether the association between variables is strong or weak and whether the relationship follows a consistent pattern. In this study, Spearman's

rank-order coefficient (Spearman's ρ) is used to evaluate the strength and direction of monotonic associations between supply chain capabilities (Agility, Collaboration, Traceability) and supply chain outcomes (SC Resilience, Circular Economy Practices, Sustainable Supply Chain Performance). Unlike Pearson's correlation, Spearman's rank correlation is a non-parametric test that does not assume normality of the data (DeCoster and Claypool, 2004). It focuses on medians rather than means (Bryman and Cramer, 2002; Jamieson, 2004), making it particularly suitable for ordinal and non-normally distributed data, such as that collected from British AEC professionals. The Spearman coefficient is derived based on the Pearson product-moment correlation formula but applied to ranked data.

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Where;

d_i = represents the difference between the ranks assigned to the two variables for each paired observation,

n = denotes the number of paired ranks

r_s = refers to the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

The value of r_s ranges from +1 to -1, where a positive coefficient signifies a direct (positive) association between variables, while a negative coefficient indicates an inverse (negative) relationship. Values close to zero suggest little to no association between the variables. Statistical significance is determined using the p -value, with results considered significant when $p < 0.05$. In this study, significance levels of $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$ were adopted to interpret the strength of the correlations.

4.19 Data Screening

The process of data screening holds significance as it ensures the quality of the data obtained during a field survey, enabling its suitability for further analyses and tests required to address the hypotheses formulated for the study. The following stages are covered by data screening.

4.19.1 Missing Value Analysis

Various methodologies can be employed to address the issue of missing values within a dataset. According to Johnson and McClure (2004), statistical experts have recommended the utilisation of the listwise deletion method as the best suitable approach for handling missing values. Nevertheless, the presence of missing data amounting to less than 10% does not pose a significant concern and can be addressed using mean imputation (Hair et al., 2006). The present study employed the median imputation method to compute missing values.

4.20 Collinearity Assessment

Collinearity or multicollinearity represents the occurrence of strong correlations between independent variables (Hair et al., 2006). Pallant (2005) posits that the presence of collinearity is observed when

there is a significant degree of correlation ($r= 0.9$ and above) among the independent variables. One of the problems with structural equation modelling is that it cannot account for the presence of collinearity. To examine the likelihood of multicollinearity SPSS carries out "collinearity diagnostics" by comparing the Tolerance values and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values to the threshold values. The tolerance value quantifies the extent to which the observed fluctuation in the given independent variable is not explained by the other independent variables in the model. According to Field (2005), a tolerance value below 0.10 indicates the presence of collinearity. Meanwhile, VIF can be thought of as the opposite of tolerance value. Collinearity would be present if the VIF value was greater than 5, as stated by Pallant (2005).

4.21 Common Method Bias

Leiter et al. (2007) and Laschinger and Fida (2013), among others, have emphasised the problem of common Method biases that typically arise when respondents self-report the survey. Common method bias, in the context of research, pertains to the variability in data that may be ascribed to the measuring technique employed, rather than being a reflection of the underlying construct being investigated (Buckley et al., 1990; Bagozzi and Yi, 1991; Lindell and Whitney, 2001). The present study employed the Harman single factor approach to investigate the presence of common method biases.

In the Harman one-factor test, all variables in the study were subjected to exploratory factor analysis, and the unrotated factor solution was analysed to assess variation attributed to a single component. A common variance of less than 50% signifies the absence of common technique bias in the data (Hair et al., 2006).

4.22 Structural Equation Modelling

Structural equation modelling (SEM) is "a multivariate technique that integrates elements of factor analysis and multiple regression, allowing researchers to simultaneously explore a series of interconnected dependency relationships among observed variables and latent constructs, as well as among multiple latent constructs" (Hair et al., 2010, p.634). Spearman developed this method in 1904, and it has since been applied in a variety of fields of study. In contrast to conventional linear models, in which variables may only be represented by a single measure and measurement error is not modelled, SEM permits the researcher to utilise multiple measurements to represent constructs and solves the problem of measure-specific error (Hox, 1999; Weston, 2006). The significance of SEM rests in its capacity to test hypotheses that are difficult to assess using other analytical approaches (Schreiber et al., 2010). This is due to the fact that SEM employs a framework that incorporates many common statistical approaches. For example, integrating factor analysis with structural equation modelling allows a researcher to examine complicated interrelated dependence of variables (Weston, 2006; Schreiber et al., 2010). Additionally, various statistical software are accessible, making SEM simple to specify and estimate (Pallant, 2005).

There are two analytical techniques in structural equation modelling (SEM); 1) covariance based structural equation modelling (CB-SEM) (Joreskog, 1971; Joreskog & Sorbom, 1996) and 2) partial

least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) (Wold, 1973, 1974, 1975). CB-SEM represents a common factor-based SEM method that views constructs as common factors responsible for explaining the covariation among their associated indicators. (Falk & Miller, 1992). On the other hand, PLS-SEM operates on the assumption that concepts of interest can be measured as composites (Joreskog, 1982). This approach has led to PLS being classified as a composite-based SEM method (Hwang et al., 2019.)

4.22.1 Rationale for Choosing of CB-SEM

The fundamental philosophical distinction between Covariance-Based SEM (CB-SEM) and Partial Least Squares SEM (PLS-SEM) lies in their underlying research objectives. While CB-SEM is primarily designed for theory testing and validation, PLS-SEM is more appropriate for theory development and prediction (Dash & Paul, 2021; Usakli & Rasoolimanesh, 2023). This study adopts CB-SEM due to its alignment with the aim of confirming theoretical relationships derived from established conceptual frameworks (Dash & Paul, 2021). CB-SEM is particularly suitable for analysing complex models involving multiple latent constructs, a common characteristic of management and organisational research, where relationships are often intricate and multidimensional (Mia et al., 2019). Additionally, CB-SEM is especially well-suited for reflective measurement models, which are frequently employed in organisational studies (Hair et al., 2017). Although CB-SEM typically assumes multivariate normality, robust estimation methods are available to manage moderate deviations from this assumption, enhancing the model's reliability and interpretability (Hair et al., 2006).

Both covariance-based SEM (CB-SEM) and partial least squares SEM (PLS-SEM) have limitations that researchers must consider. CB-SEM requires large sample sizes, assumes multivariate normality, and is better suited for reflective rather than formative constructs (Hair et al., 2019; Kline, 2016). It also focuses on model fit rather than predictive accuracy, which may not align with exploratory or prediction-focused studies (Hair et al., 2017). Conversely, PLS-SEM is more robust with small samples and formative models but lacks global goodness-of-fit measures and can produce biased estimates, such as overestimated loadings and underestimated path coefficients, particularly in small or complex models (Rigdon et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2016). Therefore, the choice between CB-SEM and PLS-SEM should align with the research objectives, data characteristics, and the theoretical or predictive focus of the study.

4.22.2 Stages of Structural Equation Modelling

Hair et al. (2015) describe SEM as a six-stage process that provides a comprehensive framework for model development and validation as illustrated in figure 4.2. The process begins with defining the constructs, followed by creating the measurement model. The third step involves designing a study to generate empirical data, which is then used in the fourth stage to evaluate the validity of the measurement model. The fifth stage focuses on specifying the structural model, and the final step involves measuring the validity of this structural model. The first four stages typically focus on the measurement model, while the last two address the structural model. This systematic approach ensures

a thorough examination of both the measurement and structural aspects of the proposed model, allowing researchers to draw robust conclusions about the relationships between variables and the overall fit of their theoretical framework to the observed data.

Figure 4.2 Six Stages for SEM

(Source: Hair et al., 2017)

4.23 Ethical Consideration

Ethical considerations are important for every study but are especially important for those that examine the social behaviour of their participants (Mittelstadt, 2017). In general, research ethics are considered prior to the data collection process. The survey participants' willingness to disclose personal information is a prerequisite for their participation. No one should be forced into taking the survey. Hence, if respondents decided to take part, they have a responsibility to be accurate and honest in their comments, based on their best judgement, without any deception or false information (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010).

According to UWS guidelines for ethical considerations when collecting data, a consent form will be sent to all participants, outlining their right to discontinued from the study at any point of time, without any consequences or need for explanation. The fact that participation was voluntary, and the assurances that confidentiality and anonymity would be maintained throughout the research process. This study also addresses other ethical issues, such as the researcher's responsibility after the data collection method, particularly during the data processing stage. A participant information letter will also be provided to everyone. This letter detailed the study's title, goals, and expected outcomes, the questionnaire's length and timing, the researcher's, and supervisor's contact information in case any questions raised, and the UWS ethical committee's email address in case any concerns were raised about the study's ethical aspect. Appendix B contains a copy of the consent form for the participant and the participant information sheet. Prior to data collection phase ethical approval from the Department of Business and Creative Industries will be obtained.

4.24 Summary

The primary objective of this chapter was to present and rationalise the philosophical perspectives, methodologies, processes, and statistical methods employed in this study to accomplish the research objectives. This investigation employed a quantitative strategy (Chapter 4) to explore and validate the conceptual framework. The best suitable survey approach for this study was determined to be based on the positivist paradigm. In order to gather data, a questionnaire will be employed, and a comprehensive examination of the many phases of questionnaire design, including design, development, scaling, and pilot research, was presented. Prior to finalising the questionnaire, two-stage pilot research will be conducted. A comprehensive account of the sample size and other sampling techniques was additionally included, along with a rationale for employing the probability sampling technique. Moreover, this chapter encompasses the discussion of both scale construction and data analysis procedures. Additionally, the structural equation modelling (SEM) technique was discussed to examine the postulated linkages within the framework, including direct, mediating, and moderating effects.

CHAPTER 5 : DATA ANALYSIS

Preliminary Data Analysis

5.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the preliminary analysis and statistical findings derived from the survey data. The preliminary analysis involved data screening, reliability analysis, and exploratory factor analysis (EFA). All analyses were conducted using SPSS version 29.0. Before applying Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), it is essential to conduct a rigorous preliminary data analysis to ensure that the data meet the key assumptions required for valid results. In this study, the preliminary analysis began by screening the dataset for missing values, as missing data can lead to biased parameter estimates and reduced statistical power if not handled appropriately (Allison, 2002). Then identified and addressed both univariate and multivariate outliers, which can distort statistical relationships and affect model fit in SEM (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). SEM is somewhat robust to minor deviations from normality, especially with larger samples, substantial non-normality can impact estimation accuracy (Kline, 2016). Multicollinearity among predictor variables was also assessed, as high intercorrelations can inflate standard errors and distort path coefficients (Hair et al., 2019). Common method bias was examined to ensure that variance was not primarily attributable to the measurement method rather than the constructs themselves (Podsakoff et al., 2003). In addition, conducted reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha to confirm the internal consistency of the constructs (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Finally, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was used to verify construct validity and the underlying structure of the measurement model, which is a critical step before conducting SEM (Fabrigar et al., 1999). These procedures collectively helped establish that the data were suitable for parametric tests and the application of SEM.

5.2 Data Screening

The first step of data analysis entails preparing the survey data for analysis. Data preparations encompass crucial operations, including data entry, editing, and coding, that are required for transforming raw data into a suitable format for analysis. Data screening assured that all collected data was devoid of errors before proceeding with data analysis. To ensure the accuracy of the scale, the researcher assessed both its construct validity and content validity. This assessment allows us to thoroughly examine each item in the scale and make any required adjustments to address any discrepancies.

Prior to data entry, every question in this survey was examined for any missing information. Moreover, an analysis of descriptive statistics was conducted to ascertain the precision of the data. In this instance, the responses that produced values beyond the acceptable range were compared with the original questionnaires to improve accuracy.

5.3 Missing Data

Missing data is a major problem when evaluating data that could affect the aims and objectives of the research (Hair et al., 2017). Missing data includes three types of incomplete responses; first, it includes cases where the respondent does not provide any answers to the survey questions, except for demographic questions. Second, it includes cases where some of the data is missing, meaning that the respondent does not provide answers to one or more of the survey questions. Third, it includes cases where the respondent gives the same response to all the questions, which is known as unengaged responses. An example of unengaged response is when the respondent chooses to answer 4 from the Likert Scale for all the questions. When using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) in conjunction with AMOS, the consequences of missing data are considerably more important. Chi-Square and other fit measures, such as the Goodness-of-Fit-Index and modification indices (will discuss in Chapter next), cannot be calculated if there are any missing data in the sample.

Data with up to 5% missing is considered acceptable (Schreiber, 2017). As a result of preliminary screening in SPSS 29.0, it was determined that all missing data was distributed randomly and below the threshold of 5%. The proportion of missing data was 0.63 percent. Given its low magnitude, this value can be considered acceptable. Consequently, the researcher employed the 'mean substitution' technique to replace missing data for categorical variables, as suggested by numerous experts, such as (Bell & Bryman, 2007) and (Pallant, 2007). However, 2 cases had only demographic data and 2 responses showed unengaged responses (the respondent provided the identical response for each item) and were deleted from the data set.

5.4 Outliers

An outlier is defined as observations that possess a particular combination of characteristics that sets them apart from the other observations (Hair et al., 2017). Recognising and managing outliers is essential because they can distort the results of statistical tests (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). To identify the outliers, the researcher employed the univariate and multivariate detection process outlined by (Hair et al., 2006). To find the univariate outliers in the dataset, the researcher calculated the z-scores frequency distributions following the recommendation of (Goodboy & Kline, 2017). Although there are no specific criteria for determining extreme values in the existing literature, a value of 3.29 can be considered acceptable for a large sample size exceeding 80. Therefore, the analysis of the univariate outliers indicates that the data set contain 16 responses that deviated significantly from the norm (Z-score $+_{3.29}$) and deleted from the data set.

The process of identifying multivariate outliers entails the observation and analysis of several statistical outcomes of variables simultaneously. The Mahalanobis D2 metric was employed to detect multivariate outliers (Goodboy & Kline, 2017; Hair et al., 2017). Mahalanobis D2 is a measure that quantifies the distance between the centroid of a specific example and the centroid of all the other cases. Any records with a p1 value below 0.05 (particularly significant on one side) are regarded as influential outliers and the correlation between the variables for these responses is notably distinct or abnormal in comparison

to the remaining data (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). In the given sample, there were two instances of multivariate outliers that had the highest Mahalanobis D values. Nevertheless, the researcher chose to retain the outliers in the sample as they were deemed insignificant in relation to the overall dataset and so justified for further examination (Hair et al., 2017).

The results of data screening after weeding out the unengaged, missing data and outliers the total number of responses that were selected for study was 299 as shown in the table 5.1.

Table 5-1 Summary of Questionnaire Processed

Survey	Frequency	Percentage %
Total Distributed Questionnaire	750	100
Returned	317	42.27
Defective and Unengaged Responses	2	0.63
Useable and Non-Defective Responses	315	42
Univariate outliers (Z Score is +_3.29)	16	5.08
Total useable Responses (after outliers)	299	39.87

5.5 Non-Parametric Tests

5.5.1 Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was applied to assess whether the median construct scores differed significantly from the neutral point of 4 on a seven-point Likert scale. This non-parametric approach was chosen as the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test confirmed that most variables did not meet the normality assumption (Pallant, 2020; Field, 2024). The results showed that agility scores were significantly higher than neutral ($Z = -14.120, p < .001$), with the majority of respondents ranking above the test median. This suggests that firms are perceived as agile, able to detect and adapt to change quickly, reflecting agility’s established role as a crucial capability in dynamic supply chain environments (Christopher & Holweg, 2011). Similarly, collaboration demonstrated a strong deviation from neutrality ($Z = -14.874, p < .001$), with almost all respondents ranking positively. This indicates that supply chain partners within the sample actively share information engage in joint planning, and distribute risks and benefits, reinforcing prior work that identifies collaboration as a central driver of supply chain performance (Simatupang & Sridharan, 2008).

Traceability also showed a statistically significant result ($Z = -2.056, p = 0.040$); however, the balance between positive and negative ranks suggests more variation across firms. While some demonstrate high levels of traceability, others remain in earlier stages of adoption, a pattern consistent with the uneven uptake of traceability systems reported in the literature (Tsolakis et al., 2021). Supply chain resilience, on the other hand, was markedly higher than neutral ($Z = -14.374, p < .001$), with most respondents indicating strong preparedness to cope with disruptions, aligning with the growing emphasis on resilience as a strategic supply chain capability (Ivanov & Dolgui, 2019). Circular

economy practices also exceeded neutrality ($Z = -6.351, p < .001$), though with noticeable variability in responses. This suggests that while firms are increasingly engaging in recycling, energy efficiency, and resource-sharing initiatives, the transition to circular models is still uneven across the sample (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017).

Blockchain adoption, however, did not significantly differ from the neutral point ($Z = -1.295, p = 0.195$), indicating no strong trend toward adoption in the firms studied. This is likely due to the early stage of blockchain deployment in supply chains, with barriers such as cost, interoperability, and technical complexity persisting (Sabeti et al., 2019). Finally, sustainable supply chain performance scores were significantly higher than neutral ($Z = -8.691, p < .001$), with most firms reporting improvements in profitability, market share, environmental impact, and stakeholder well-being. This result suggests that sustainability initiatives are yielding tangible benefits, reinforcing the link between sustainability practices and improved business outcomes (Pagell & Shevchenko, 2014). Table 5.2 presents the Wilcoxon signed-rank test results for all constructs.

Table 5-2 Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Results

Construct	Z	p (2-tailed)	r	Effect Size Interpretation	Median Direction
Agility	-14.120	< .001	0.84	Large	Median > 4 (Higher than neutral)
Collaboration	-14.874	< .001	0.87	Large	Median > 4 (Higher than neutral)
Traceability	-2.056	.040	0.15	Small	Median < 4 (Slightly lower than neutral)
Supply Chain Resilience	-14.374	< .001	0.85	Large	Median > 4 (Higher than neutral)
Circular Economy Practices	-6.351	< .001	0.40	Medium–Large	Median > 4 (Higher than neutral)
Blockchain	-1.295	.195	0.09	Trivial / Not Significant	No significant difference
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance	-8.691	< .001	0.57	Large	Median > 4 (Higher than neutral)

5.5.2 Friedman Test

The Friedman test was conducted to examine whether there were statistically significant differences in the median scores across the seven constructs under investigation. The results indicated a highly significant difference among the constructs, $\chi^2(6) = 1064.087, p < .001$, suggesting that participants did not evaluate all dimensions equally (Conover, 1999; Siegel and Castellan, 1988). Instead, some constructs were consistently rated higher or lower than others. An examination of the mean ranks provides further insights into these differences. Traceability (Mean Rank = 5.91) emerged as the highest-ranked construct, closely followed by blockchain adoption (Mean Rank = 5.59) and circular economy practices (Mean Rank = 4.90). This pattern suggests that respondents perceive firms to be more advanced in implementing digital tracking systems, blockchain-enabled transparency, and environmentally focused practices. Sustainable supply chain performance was also rated relatively high

(Mean Rank = 4.41), implying that sustainability initiatives are beginning to yield visible outcomes in terms of operational and strategic benefits (Seuring and Müller, 2008; Ahi and Searcy, 2013).

By contrast, collaboration (Mean Rank = 1.57) received the lowest ranking among all constructs, while agility (Mean Rank = 2.92) and supply chain resilience (Mean Rank = 2.69) also occupied lower positions. These results suggest that although firms may have invested in digital and technological enablers of supply chain improvement, collaborative practices such as joint planning, information sharing, and shared risk management remain less developed (Simatupang and Sridharan, 2005). Furthermore, while agility and resilience are recognised as critical capabilities in the literature, the relatively lower rankings may indicate that firms are still building these competencies in practice (Christopher, 2000; Ivanov and Dolgui, 2020). Overall, the findings highlight a divergence in supply chain priorities, with respondents emphasising traceability, blockchain, and circular economy practices more strongly than collaboration, agility, and resilience. This divergence underlines the need for firms to balance technological adoption with relational and process-oriented capabilities to achieve holistic and sustainable supply chain performance (Dubey et al., 2019; Queiroz et al., 2020). The Table 5.3 presents the summary of Friedman mean rank test results for all constructs.

Table 5-3 Friedman Mean Rank Test Results

Construct	Mean Rank
Collaboration	1.57
Agility	2.92
Supply Chain Resilience	2.69
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance	4.41
Circular Economy Practices	4.90
Blockchain	5.59
Traceability	5.91

5.5.3 Spearman Correlation Matrix

Spearman's rank-order correlation analysis was conducted to examine the associations between supply chain capabilities (Agility, Collaboration, and Traceability) and supply chain outcomes (Supply Chain Resilience, Circular Economy Practices, and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance). The results revealed several statistically significant positive correlations. Agility demonstrated moderate positive correlations with Supply Chain Resilience ($\rho = 0.460, p < .001$), Circular Economy Practices ($\rho = 0.263, p < .001$), and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance ($\rho = 0.423, p < .001$), indicating that firms with greater agility tend to adapt more effectively to disruptions, embrace circular practices, and achieve better sustainability outcomes. Collaboration was also positively associated with Supply Chain Resilience ($\rho = 0.383, p < .001$), Circular Economy Practices ($\rho = 0.169, p < .01$), and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance ($\rho = 0.210, p < .001$), though the effect sizes were relatively weaker compared to agility, suggesting that while collaborative practices support resilience and sustainability, their impact may vary across firms. Traceability showed moderate to strong positive correlations with

Supply Chain Resilience ($\rho = 0.267, p < .001$), Circular Economy Practices ($\rho = 0.488, p < .001$), and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance ($\rho = 0.414, p < .001$). This finding highlights the growing importance of traceability as a critical capability that enhances transparency, accountability, and sustainable outcomes across supply chains. Collectively, these results suggest that supply chain capabilities particularly agility and traceability play a pivotal role in enabling firms to achieve resilience, integrate circular economy principles, and enhance sustainable supply chain performance (Garcia-Torres et al., 2024). Table 5.4 demonstrates the results for Spearman's rank-order correlation analysis.

Table 5-4 Spearman's Rank-order Correlation Analysis Results

Variable	Agility	Collaboration	Traceability	SC Resilience	Circular Economy Practices	Sustainable SC Performance
Agility	—	0.410**	0.298**	0.460**	0.263**	0.423**
Collaboration	0.410**	—	0.159**	0.383**	0.169**	0.210**
Traceability	0.298**	0.159**	—	0.267**	0.488**	0.414**
SC Resilience	0.460**	0.383**	0.267**	—	0.300**	0.459**
Circular Economy Practices	0.263**	0.169**	0.488**	0.300**	—	0.415**
Sustainable SC Performance	0.423**	0.210**	0.414**	0.459**	0.415**	—

Note: N = 299. ρ (Spearman's rho). ** $p < .01$ (2-tailed)

5.6 Multi - Collinearity

Multicollinearity implies to the occurrence of significant correlations among two or more independent variables in a multiple regression model (Hair et al., 2006). (Pallant, 2005, p.150) defines multicollinearity as the presence of strong correlation ($r = 0.9$ and higher) among independent variables. Prior to using multivariate analysis, multi-collinearity is another significant issue that must be resolved. To assess the presence of multicollinearity, SPSS conducts "collinearity diagnostics" by comparing Tolerance values and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values with predefined threshold values.

The tolerance value shows the extent to which the other independent variables in the model do not account for the variability of the given independent variable. A tolerance value below 0.10 indicates the presence of multicollinearity (Field, 2005). Conversely, the VIF is the inverse of the tolerance value. The VIF assesses the strength of the linear regression relationship between two predictors. Multicollinearity is absent when the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value is equal to or below the recommended threshold of 10 (Hair et al., 2010). All the independent variables' tolerance and VIF

values are shown in table 5.5. All of the requirements were satisfied by the data used for tolerance and variance inflation factor (VIF); thus, the researcher concluded that the multi-co-linearity assumption is not violated.

Table 5-5 Multicollinearity Statistics among Independent Variables

Constructs	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
SC Capabilities (SSCs)		
Agility	0.67	1.49
Collaboration	0.78	1.28
Traceability	0.66	1.52
SC Resilience (SCRES)	0.71	1.40
Circular Economy Practices (CEP)	0.50	2.02
Blockchain Technology (BCT)	0.51	1.97

5.7 Common Method Bias (CMB)

Common Method Bias (CMB) is a major risk for the validity of results for the relationship between variables (Podsakoff et al., 2003). A variety of factors can contribute to CMB, including the common rate effect, consistency theme, social desirability, acquiescence biases, common scale format, item social desirability, and scale length. Common Method Variance (CMV) one-factor method was employed to determine the presence of common method bias in the data, and the variance assessed was related to the method of data collecting rather than the constructs included in the investigation. CMV was regarded a severe concern linked with data analysis in several studies, notably those that used surveys, questionnaires, or interviews (Richardson et al., 2009). The one-factor technique of CMV is one of the most extensively used statistical procedures for testing the presence of common method bias in data. In exploratory factor analysis, the loadings of all measurement items are aggregated into a single factor, and the un-rotated component matrix is assessed to identify the variation attributed to that factor. The data for this study was collected from managers in the food and drink industry using a questionnaire. The survey instrument was created based on the literature of different authors, with some items being adopted and others being adapted. Therefore, a common method bias could be an issue. In this study, the researcher used CMV to examine the question items across all constructs and extracted one component to examine the items' effects on the variation within a particular construct. Based on the findings of the factor analysis, it was found that one factor account for 29.19% of the total variance, which is below 50% (Podsakoff & Organ, 1986). Therefore, there is no common method bias in the data as shown in table 5.6.

Table 5-6 Total Variance Explained Using Single Factor Method

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	11.087	30.798	30.798	10.508	29.188	29.188
2	4.498	12.494	43.293			
3	2.906	8.072	51.365			
4	2.188	6.078	57.443			
5	1.854	5.150	62.594			
6	1.644	4.568	67.162			
7	1.148	3.188	70.349			

40	.001	.0028	100.000			

5.8 Reliability

Reliable scales and an acceptable alpha value are characteristics of high-quality research (Hair et al., 2010). There are following two commonly used methods for determining the final factor solutions' internal reliability:

- Test-retest
- Internal consistency

"Test-retest involves conducting research with the same respondents at two separate points in time" (Hair et al., 2010, p.125). Therefore, test-retest could not be implemented in this study due to various factors. These include time constraints caused by the large sample size, participant fatigue from having to complete the same survey twice, potential financial implications from having to compensate participants for taking the survey twice, response pattern bias from survey participants becoming too familiar with the questions and developing response pattern bias, and attrition from participants leaving the study halfway, which can lead to an incomplete data set and potentially biased results.

The internal consistency method, which is the most basic form of reliability assessment, is widely regarded as the most practicable approach. (Green & Tull, 1970, p.314) provided a definition of internal consistency as the "reliability within single testing occasions". Cronbach's alpha is widely recognised as a reliable measure of internal consistency and, hence, reliability. The Cronbach's coefficient alpha is the recommended indicator of a set of items' internal consistency (Churchill, 1979; Nunnally, 1978; Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The threshold level of Cronbach's coefficient alpha varies depending on the type of research. For new and exploratory-type research, a lower level of 0.60 (Nunnally, 1978) may be acceptable, however the widely recognised lower limit is 0.70.

The proposed study model incorporates several items for each construct, so the internal consistency can be assess using Cronbach's alpha measure for each construct. These scales include "Agility (Ag)", "Collaboration (Col)", "Traceability (Tr)", "SC resilience (SCRES)", "Circular Economy Practices (CEP)", "Blockchain Technology (BCT)" and "Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)". An

analysis of the reliability tests conducted for this study was carried out with SPSS.29, as can be shown in table 5.7. The results indicate that the constructs displayed with a score range of 0.77 to 0.933. This proves that the chosen scales have a high level of reliability, as all the construct's alpha coefficients are over the acceptable threshold and demonstrate strong internal consistency.

Table 5-7 Cronbach's alpha for each item

Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Agility (Ag)	0.770
Collaboration (Col)	0.921
Traceability (Tr)	0.933
SC Resilience (SCRES)	0.904
Circular Economy Practices (CEP)	0.896
Blockchain Technology (BCT)	0.826
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)	0.913

5.9 Sample Characteristics

Following the completion of data cleaning, the researcher initiated an investigation into the characteristics of the variables. This section will provide an overview of the characteristics of the firms and respondents who participated in the study.

5.9.1 Firm Profile

The analysis of 299 responses from food and drink manufacturing firms' is shown in table 5.8. The participants are only from food and drink manufacturing firms that offer comprehensive and integrated manufacturing services, including logistics, processing, assembly, material handling, storage and purchasing, quality control as well as IT services.

Table 5-8 Firm Profile

Size of the organization	No.	Percent
Medium firm (50 to 249 employees)	188	62.8%
Large firm (more than 250 employees)	111	37.1%
Grand Total	299	100%
Annual Revenue	No.	Percent
50-100 million £	131	44%
100-250 million £	100	33%
250-500 million £	63	21%
More than 500 million £	5	2%
Grand Total	299	100%

5.9.1.1 Size of the Firm

The distribution of firms based on organisation size is as follows: 62.8% were medium firms with between 50 to 249 employees and 37.1% were large firms with more than 250 employees as shown in table 5.5. This presentation of medium and large firms in the sample reflects the targeted focus on significant players within the UK food and drink manufacturing sector, where firms of larger scale are more prevalent and better positioned to implement advanced supply chain capabilities and technologies

(Morgan et al., 2003). Thus, the size distribution in the sample aligns with the research objective of investigating capabilities and practices typically found in more resource-intensive enterprises.

5.9.1.2 Annual Revenue

Table 5.5 illustrates that the majority of companies, approximately 77%, has annual revenue ranging from £50 million to £250 million. Meanwhile, 21% have sales between £250 million and £500 million, and only 2% have annual revenue more than £500 million.

This revenue distribution suggests that most firms in the sample operate at the medium-to-large scale within the food and drink manufacturing sector. Approximately 98.6% businesses in the UK food and drink manufacturing industry were small and medium enterprises (SMEs), generating a combined turnover of just under £22 billion. By contrast, less than 3% were large firms, yet these accounted for a significantly higher turnover of £76 billion (Food statistics in your pocket - GOV.UK). Compared to this national picture, the sample in this research is heavily weighted toward larger businesses with higher revenue levels. This focus is intentional and aligns with the study’s objectives, as medium and larger firms are more likely to possess the resources and capabilities to implement advanced supply chain practices and sustainability initiatives.

5.9.2 Respondent Profile

The profile of the respondents is presented in table 5.9.

Table 5-9 Respondents Profile

Respondent Profile	No.	Percent
Designation		
Supply Chain Manager	72	24%
Distribution/Warehouse Manager	59	20%
Logistics/Transport/Freight Manager	47	16%
IT Manager	33	11%
Purchase Manager	26	9%
Project/Production Manager	28	9%
CEO/Director/President	22	7%
Owner/Partner	12	4%
Years in the Company		
1-5	59	20%
6-8	67	22%
9-10	32	11%
More than 10	141	47%
Gender		
Male	240	80%
Female	59	20%

5.9.2.1 Designation

The respondents' designations reflect their expertise and roles across the supply chain, ensuring a broad range of perspectives. Specifically, 24% were Supply Chain Managers, 20% Distribution/Warehouse Managers, 16% Logistics/Transport/Freight Managers, and 11% IT Managers. This diversity captures strategic, operational, and technological viewpoints, enhancing the comprehensiveness of the findings.

5.9.2.2 Years in Company

20% have worked for 1-5 years. Whereas 22% have worked for 6-8 years, 11% have worked for 9-10 years, and 47% have been employed in the company for more than 10 years. The data indicates that half of the respondents have substantial tenure in their organisations, which may reflect significant experience and familiarity with company operations.

5.9.2.3 Gender

Participants in the sample include both male and female respondents. A significant majority of the respondents, 80% were males. This gender distribution reflects the known gender imbalance commonly observed in the manufacturing sector, particularly in food and beverage industries. According to Food Navigator (2025), women represent around 36% of the workforce in the UK food and beverage industry, which contextualizes the male dominance observed in this study's sample. While the 80% male proportion is slightly higher than industry averages, it remains plausible given the sector's demographics.

5.10 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Exploratory Factor Analysis is a statistical method used to decrease the number of variables by identifying the number of latent constructs and the factor structure within a set of variables (Hair et al., 2010). The objective of EFA is to summarize and reduction of data by applying a specific factors logic, with the purpose of establishing a suitable arrangement of research variables. Furthermore, data reduction in exploratory factor analysis (EFA) enables the deletion of all uncorrelated items, leading to a decreased number of items inside each variable (Field, 2005). (Hair et al., 2017) identified two potential issues that could impact the results of exploratory factor analysis (EFA): the number of items inside each component and the size of the sample. In order to address these issues, several suggestions can be found in the literature. According to (Hair et al., 2010), it is proposed to include a minimum of three or more components in a factor to address the initial issue. Whereas, in addressing the second issue, (Hair et al., 2017) advised that the number of observations should exceed the number of study variables, and the sample size should be a minimum of 150 or more, depending on the number of variables being considered.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) facilitates the comprehension of the arrangement of a set of variables (latent variables) and the drop of data while preserving as much original information as possible (Memon et al., 2017). EFA use reflective latent variables (multi-indicator) instead of formative, demographic or categorical variables such as gender, age, and other similar factors. All the constructs in this study are subjected to factor analysis in order to obtain the fundamental information on their

content and construct validity. This encompasses the 40 items utilised to evaluate the influence of SC capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability), SC resilience, CE practices and BCT on sustainable supply performance (SSCP) of a firm. Factor analysis is a statistical method used to identify natural groupings of variables that measure similar concepts. It involves analysing a large correlation matrix and expressing the results as dimensions or factors (Memon et al., 2017).

5.10.1 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) Requirements

Conduct a correlation analysis of the variables, if there is no or a very weak correlation among the variables, then the suitability of factor analysis will be seriously questioned. In factor analysis, a researcher anticipates that some variables will exhibit strong correlations with each other, thereby forming a factor. The EFA was executed by implementing the subsequent procedures.

5.10.2 Data Adequacy

(a). Meyer Kaiser -Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's tests of sphericity

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity measures are the most commonly used methods to assess the factorability of data (Baumgartner & Homburg, 1996; Costello & Osborne, 2005; Kline, 1998).

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) approach is employed to ascertain the adequacy of the sample size for conducting factor analysis (Lowry & Gaskin, 2014). The KMO index ranges from 0 to 1, where a value of 0.6 indicates a poor level and a value of 0.9 indicates excellent for executing EFA. Table 5.10 displays the KMO data, which range from low to excellent suggested by (Hair et al., 2017) and (Lowry & Gaskin, 2014).

Table 5-10 KMO Statistics

Data range	KMO values
Excellent	0.9
Meritorious	0.8
Moderate	0.7
Average	0.6
Miserable	0.5
Unacceptable	<0.3

The Bartlett's test for Sphericity assesses the similarity between correlation matrix (a matrix of Pearson correlations) and the identity matrix. Simply put, it verifies whether there is any redundant information between variables that can be summarised using certain factors. The existence of identity matrix puts the correctness of the factor analysis under suspicion. According to (Hair et al., 2010), Bartlett's test of sphericity should yield a statistically significant result, with a p-value less than 0.05.

The KMO and Bartlett's tests of sphericity were employed to evaluate the adequacy of the data for this study. The KMO measure of sample adequacy is generally regarded as a more sophisticated test compared to Bartlett. (Hair et al., 2010) proposed that a threshold of 0.6 or greater is necessary to determine the appropriateness of a factor analysis. The KMO results for both the initial and revised

EFA (after removing the cross-loaded components) are displayed in table 5.11. The KMO value of 0.91 is clearly indicating that the matrix is not an identity matrix and that the variables have a strong enough relationship to carry out a meaningful EFA.

Table 5-11 Sampling Adequacy Measure

		Initial	Revised
KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.916	0.914
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	8315.666	7404.735
	df	780	630
	Sig.	0.000	0.000

5.11 Factor Analysis

When doing factor analysis, principal components analysis is by far the most used method (Abdi & Williams, 2010). Below, you will find the details of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

5.11.1 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a statistical technique used to reduce the complexity of a large dataset containing several variables per observation (Costello & Osborne, 2005). It transforms the data into a smaller collection of summary indices. These indices preserve the majority of the information from the original set of variables. These newly identified values are commonly referred to as principal components by researchers. The principal components are a collection of new, uncorrelated variables that are formed by combining the original variables in a linear manner. PCA's simplification facilitates the visualisation, analysis, and identification of patterns in your data with greater ease. This approach is especially advantageous when there is a high number of variables compared to the number of observations, or when the variables exhibit strong correlation.

The alternative principal axis factoring method is better suitable when there is less previous knowledge about the dataset and when the assumption of clearly derived structures is less certain (Stewart, 1981). When conducting principal components analysis, three procedural decisions are required to be made (a) the number of components derived (factor extraction) (b) simplify and clarify the data structure (factor rotation) and (c) loadings and cross loadings of items. The subsequent steps are discussed below.

5.11.2 Factor Extraction

(Pallant, 2005) stated that the primary purpose of the extraction approach in factor analysis is to identify the smallest feasible number of factors that accurately describe the variations and interrelationships within the data. (Costello & Osborne, 2005) proposed several factor extraction techniques that depend on the software package employed for study. Among these methods are principal component analysis (PCA), maximum likelihood (ML), unweighted least squares, image factoring, principal axis factoring and generalised least squares method (GLS).

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is the extraction approach that is most commonly used and accepted. SPSS 29.0 offers many tests for Principal Component Analysis (PCA), such as eigenvalue analysis, scree plot, and fixed factor etc. In eigen-value analysis, the cut-off point of eigen-values should

be set at a value greater than 1 in order to determine the components (Kaiser, 1958). While Catell's scree plot provides a visual depiction of the components that have been derived. The inflexion points of this curve, where the slope of the line experiences a significant rise, should be identified as the cut-off point for selecting factors (Latan & Noonan, 2017). In this study, the researcher used Kaiser's criterion and kept all factors whose eigenvalues were 1 or higher.

Figure 5.1 Scree Plot

5.11.3 Factor Rotation

As stated by (Costello & Osborne, 2005), the purpose of the rotation approach is to simplify and clarify the data structure. However, it does not have the ability to enhance fundamental aspects of analysis, such as the amount of variance retrieved from the items. The rotation of factors is also required because the original factor model might be right mathematically but hard to interpret. If various factors have a high loading on the same variable, then the interpretation will be extremely difficult. This type of interpretation challenge is resolved through rotation. Producing a relatively basic structure with a high factor loading on one factor and a low factor loading on all other factors is the primary goal of rotation. (Pallant, 2005), outlined the two categories of rotation method: orthogonal and oblique. The most popular orthogonal rotation method is varimax (is also adopted in this study), followed by equamax and quartimax. Whereas oblique rotation methods include promax, direct oblimin, and quartimin (Costello & Osborne, 2005).

5.11.4 Factor Loadings and Cross Loading

A sufficient sample size is required to identify statistically significant factor loadings. Moreover, (Hair et al., 2010) also asserted that the moderation factor loading should be a minimum of 0.60, with higher cut-off points indicating strong item to total correlations. (Kerlinger, 1986) proposed that “cross-loadings of 0.40 or less are regarded as too low to hold significant importance”. He further stated that the higher the item-to-total loading, the greater the validity of the factor r . In consequence, this study has included only those items that have a minimum loading of 0.6 on the hypothesized component and

a maximum loading of 0.40 on other components. Following the factor analysis, the subsequent step involves labelling of the derived factors. At this step, the researcher ought to have a comprehensive understanding of the study's nature and the specific components that have been extracted throughout the factor analysis. Conducting a reliability assessment subsequent to factor analysis is also very important. This is done by eliminating poor-loading items and proceeding with the presentation of the factors that were extracted during the analysis.

From initial results, it can be seen that some items were found to be cross loaded on other factors (in this case its (Ag2), suggests that the variables being assessed in the EFA had strong inter-correlations. The initial rotated factor matrix, without any entries removed, is displayed below (table 5.12).

Table 5-12 Initial Rotated Factor Matrix

Rotated Factor Matrix ^a							
	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Agility (Ag)							
Ag1							.718
Ag2			.761				
Ag3							.774
Ag4							.773
Ag5							.720
Collaboration (Col)							
Col1					.770		
Col2					.846		
Col3					.878		
Col4					.853		
Col5					.861		
Traceability (Tr)							
Tr1				.820			
Tr2				.792			
Tr3				.824			
Tr4				.836			
Tr5				.796			
SC resilience (SCRES)							
SCRES1		.681					
SCRES2		.825					
SCRES3		.713					
SCRES4		.725					
SCRES5		.825					
SCRES6		.825					
SCRES7		.629					
Circular Economy Practices (CEP)							
CEP1	.629						
CEP2	.804						
CEP3	.846						
CEP4	.770						
CEP5	.766						
CEP6	.523						
CEP7	.666						
CEP8	.582						
Blockchain (BC)							
BC1						.723	
BC2						.694	
BC3						.662	
BC4						.641	
BC5						.576	
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)							
SSCP1			.716				
SSCP2			.830				
SSCP3			.796				
SSCP4			.821				
SSCP5			.801				
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.							

The revised Rotated Factor Matix after removing the low or cross loading factor (Ag2) is given below (table 5.13). From the perspective of the outcome of the factor loadings, there were no more modifications made to the collaboration, traceability, supply cain resilience, circular economy practices, blockchain and sustainable supply chain performance's items. To ensure internal consistency, reassessed the reliability of the remaining components by recalculating Cronbach's alpha values.

Table 5-13 Revised Rotated Factor Matrix

Rotated Factor Matrix ^a							
	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Agility (Ag)							
Ag1	.717						
Ag3	.773						
Ag4	.774						
Ag5	.722						
Collaboration (Col)							
Col1		.770					
Col2		.846					
Col3		.878					
Col4		.853					
Col5		.861					
Traceability (Tr)							
Tr1			.819				
Tr2			.793				
Tr3			.825				
Tr4			.837				
Tr5			.798				
SC resilience (SCRES)							
SCRES1				.678			
SCRES2				.826			
SCRES3				.714			
SCRES4				.729			
SCRES5				.829			
SCRES6				.831			
SCRES7				.634			
Circular Economy Practices (CEP)							
CEP1					.628		
CEP2					.803		
CEP3					.845		
CEP4					.773		
CEP5					.769		
CEP7					.667		
CEP8					.587		
Blockchain Technology (BCT)							
BC1						.727	
BC2						.696	
BC3						.668	
BC4						.642	
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)							
SSCP1							.731
SSCP2							.830
SSCP3							.804
SSCP4							.820
SSCP5							.779

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
 a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

The first factor/component derived after performing EFA is Supply Chain Agility (Ag) with total variance accounted as 20%. All four items of Supply Chain Agility (Ag) were loaded on component 1 on its underlying factor with values $Ag1 = .717$, $Ag3 = .773$, $Ag4 = .774$ and $Ag5 = .722$ respectively and were retained. Supply Chain Collaboration (Col) is the second factor/component determined, with total variance accounting 12.45%. All five items of Supply Chain Collaboration (Col) heavily loaded on component 2 on its underlying factor with values $Col1 = .770$, $Col2 = .846$, $Col3 = .878$, $Col4 = .853$ and $Col5 = .861$ respectively. Supply Chain Traceability (Tr), with a total variance of 8.072 %, was the third factor/component derived. All five items of Supply Chain Traceability (Tr) were loaded on component 3 on its underlying factor with values $Tr1 = .819$, $Tr2 = .793$, $Tr3 = .825$, $Tr4 = .837$ and $Tr5 = .798$. SC resilience (SCRES), with a total variance of 6.08 %, was the fourth factor/component derived following the execution of EFA. All seven items of SC resilience (SCRES) were loaded on component 4 on its underlying factor with values $SCRES1 = .678$, $SCRES2 = .826$, $SCRES3 = .714$, $SCRES4 = .729$, $SCRES5 = .8292$, $SCRES6 = .831$ and $SCRES7 = .634$ respectively. The fifth factor/component derived from EFA was circular economy practices (CEP) with total variance 5.15%. All eight items of Circular Economy Practices (CEP) were loaded on their underlying factor 5 with values $CEP1 = .628$, $CEP2 = .803$, $CEP3 = .845$, $CEP4 = .773$, $CEP5 = .769$, $CEP7 = .667$ and $CEP8 = .587$ respectively. The sixth factor/component derived after performing EFA was Blockchain technology (BCT) with total variance 4.6%. All five items of Blockchain technology (BCT) were loaded on their underlying factor 6 with values $BC1 = .727$, $BC2 = .696$, $BC3 = .668$, and $BC4 = .642$ respectively. The seventh and last factor/component derived from EFA was Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP) with total variance of 3.18%. All five items of Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP) were loaded on their underlying factor 7 with value $SSCP1 = .731$, $SSCP2 = .830$, $SSCP3 = .804$, $SSCP4 = .820$ and $SSCP5 = .779$ respectively.

All seven factors explain 63.5% of variance in the factor analysis, which shows the strength of the data and analysis. Therefore, no further internal consistency assessment was conducted.

5.12 Summary

This chapter provides a concise overview of the findings obtained from the initial analysis conducted using SPSS 29. This chapter also covered several topics like missing data, unengaged responses, outliers, evaluating the normal distribution of the data through skewness and kurtosis, multicollinearity, and common method bias. The results demonstrated that the sample followed a normal distribution with the less than 5% missing data. Moreover, both the skewness and kurtosis values in each case fell within the range of 1, which is acceptable since there were no issues with the normality of the data. Lastly, the values of the VIF and tolerance suggested that there were no worries with multicollinearity in the sample.

This chapter also provided details regarding the company's demographics and respondent profiles, encompassing factors such as employee count, annual revenues, respondent designation, and tenure at the company. According to the data, most of the firms were large had a workforce of more than 250

individuals and had sales ranging from £50m to £250m. Moreover, most of the participants were managers or executives who held positions of authority and had accumulated 5-8 years of professional experience inside their respective companies.

This chapter further presented the outcomes of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), encompassing KMO statistics and principal component analysis. This facilitated the researcher in verifying the convergent and discriminant validity of the dataset, as well as in preparing the data for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The chapter concluded with a distinct rotated factor matrix that displayed distinct loadings of constructs on their respective factors.

CHAPTER 6 : STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELLING (SEM)

6.1 Introduction

This chapter will provide a detailed analysis of the relationships between the constructs included in the proposed research model for applying Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). The analysis will be carried out in two steps: The first step involves assessing the measurement model using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). This will help determine the model's fit, as well as the reliability and validity of the constructs. The second step is to assess the structural model. This will involve examining the hypothesized relationships between the variables using a series of multiple regression equations. The analysis will be conducted using IBM AMOS version 29.

6.2 Model Fit Measurements

In Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), one of the most crucial tasks is to determine if a given model "fits" the data. Therefore, it is imperative for researchers to understand the model fit indices and their acceptance levels to tackle underlying possible misspecifications within the model. The most widely respected and reported fit indices are Absolute fit indices and Incremental fit indices. Absolute fit indices assess the degree to which a pre-established model aligns with the data collected from the sample (McDonald & Ho, 2002) and determines which proposed model exhibits the best fit. These measurements offer the most basic indicator of the compatibility between the proposed theory and the data. Moreover, these indices are not calculated based on comparison with a baseline model but rather indicates how well the model fits compared to having no model at all (Jöreskog and Sörbom, 1993). This category includes the Chi-Squared test, RMSEA, GFI, AGFI, RMR, and SRMR. Incremental fit indices, sometimes referred to as comparative (Shevlin & Miles, 1998) or relative fit indices (McDonald and Ho, 2002), are a set of metrics that assess model fit by comparing the chi-square value to a baseline model. The null hypothesis for these models is that all variables are uncorrelated (McDonald and Ho, 2002). All the model fit indices and their acceptable threshold values are given in the table 6.1 below.

Table 6-1 Fit indices and their acceptable thresholds (Copied from Hooper et al., 2008.)

Indices	Index Name	Acceptance Rule
Absolute Fit		
	Chi-Square χ^2	Low χ^2 relative to degrees of freedom with an insignificant p value ($p > 0.05$)
	RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	RMSEA < 0.08
	GFI (Goodness of Fit)	GFI > 0.95
	RMR (Root mean square residual)	Smaller the better, 0 indicates perfect fit
	SRMR (Standardised RMR)	SRMR \leq 0.08
Incremental fit		
	NFI (Normed-fit index)	IFI \geq 0.95
	CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	CFI \geq 0.95

6.3 Measurement Model Assessment

For measurement model assessment, the researcher performed Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The details of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) are discussed below.

6.3.1 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

CFA is a multivariate technique used to verify if a theoretical latent variable can be inferred from the observed variables (Phakiti et al., 2018). A total of seven constructs, including three independent, three dependent, and a moderator, were used for CFA. The process included estimating and re-estimating the model to examine the loadings of each item on its construct. In Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) goodness of fit was examined followed by model's reliability and validity.

In Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), distinguishing between endogenous and exogenous constructs is not necessary, yet it becomes essential during the model evaluation phase (Hair et al., 2017). The construct items (measured variables) are represented as rectangular forms in figure 6.1, where all variables are connected. Single-headed arrows are commonly used to represent a causal relationship from a construct to an indicator, but double-headed arrows are typically used to represent covariance.

6.3.1.1 Goodness of Fit

(a). Initial Model

An initial measurement model was conducted in AMOS 29 using the refined dataset to evaluate the overall fit of measurements. Initial runs of the CFA model, carried out before any model refinements, yielded fit statistics that were marginally acceptable. The model fit indices were $\chi^2 = 820.87$ at $df = 570$, $\chi^2/df = 1.44$; CFI = 0.87; IFI = 0.87; RMSEA 0.056; RMR = 0.03 and SRMR = 0.04. This model was thoroughly assessed for statistical fit and theoretical justification, considering all possible modifications.

The initial modification indices (MI) indicated that some degree of improvement in model fit was needed. The following measures are recommended for a good model fit:

- The standardised residual covariance should be equal to or less than 2.58 (Bryman et al., 2007)
- Factor loading (Standardised regression weight) should go above 0.5 and preferably be above 0.7 (Bryman et al., 2007).

However, in initial model the model fit indices marginally met the criteria where the standardised factor loading values for CEP6 (0.53), CEP8 (0.54), BC4 (0.42) and BC5 (0.49) were less than 0.6. After elimination of CEP6, CEP8, BC4 and BC5 in accordance with the criteria, the researcher reran the model to increase the modification indices (fig 6.1).

Figure 6.1 CFA Measurement Model

Figure 6.1 presents the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) measurement model used in this study to assess the validity and reliability of the proposed constructs. The model includes seven latent variables: CEP (Circular Economy Practices), SCRES (Supply Chain Resilience), Tr (Traceability), Col (Collaboration), SSCP (Sustainable Supply Chain Performance), Ag (Agility), BC (Blockchain Technology Adoption). Each latent construct is measured by multiple observed indicators, represented by rectangles in the diagram (e.g., CEP1, SCRES1, Tr1, etc.). The numbers on the arrows from each latent variable to its observed indicators denote standardized factor loadings, indicating how strongly each indicator is associated with its underlying factor. For example, the factor loadings for CEP indicators range from 0.72 to 0.84, suggesting good convergent validity.

The curved double-headed arrows between latent variables represent the correlations among the constructs, with the corresponding correlation coefficients shown on the paths. These values range from 0.17 to 0.65, reflecting varying degrees of association between the constructs in the model. For instance, SCRES and SSCP are positively correlated (0.65), suggesting a strong relationship between supply chain resilience and sustainable supply chain performance. Error terms for each observed indicator are depicted as small circles (e.g., e1, e2, etc.), with corresponding values indicating the measurement error associated with each indicator. Overall, the CFA results demonstrate an adequate measurement model, confirming that the observed variables reliably measure their intended constructs and that the constructs are distinct yet interrelated.

The revised values of final model fit indices demonstrated better fit statistics with $\chi^2 = 743.8$ at $df = 535$, $\chi^2/df = 1.396$; CFI = 0.96; IFI = 0.96; RMSEA 0.036; RMR = 0.03 and SRMR = 0.04. The findings demonstrate that the model is well-fitting based on the Fit indices and standardised loading values are above their acceptable thresholds 0.6. Therefore, no further improvements were made, and model was finalized. The summary of the model fit indices is given below.

Table 6-2 Summary of fit indices for measurement model

Indices	Estimated value	Interpretation
χ^2/df	1.396	Excellent
CFI	0.96	Excellent
IFI	0.96	Excellent
RMR	0.03	Excellent
RMSEA	0.036	Excellent
SRMR	0.044	Excellent

6.3.1.2 Construct Reliability and Validity

It is essential to conduct a thorough assessment of the measurements' validity and reliability prior to testing the hypotheses in the proposed conceptual model (Hair et al., 2017). Otherwise, the results and the study's overall purpose could be compromised. Although these two tests are separate in nature, they are intrinsically connected (Gummesson, 2000). A measure may possess high reliability (consistency);

but lack of validity (accuracy) conversely, a measure may possess high validity (accuracy) but lack of reliability (consistency) (Holmbeck, 1997). The details of these two measures are given below.

(a). Reliability

The researcher calculated the reliabilities of the variables by computing Composite Reliability (CR). Composite reliability, often referred to as construct reliability, is a measure that assesses the internal consistency of scale components, like Cronbach's alpha coefficients (Hair et al., 2017). However, Cronbach's alpha coefficient values tend to underestimate reliability, presents various limitations, and may lead to inaccuracies (Malhotra et al., 2006; Garver and Mentzer, 1999).

The composite reliability has a threshold value of 0.70 or higher (Rasli, 2006; Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Table 6.3 demonstrates that all the constructs have acceptable reliability, with values ranging from 0.801 to 0.927. Composite reliability for Agility (Ag) = 0.812, Collaboration (Col) = 0.924, Traceability (Tr) = 0.927, SC Resilience (SCRES) = 0.901, Circular Economy Practices (CEP) = 0.898, Blockchain Technology (BCT) = 0.801, and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP) = 0.916. This proves that convergent validity can be established with acceptable composite reliability values.

Table 6-3 Composite Reliability

Construct	Composite Reliability
Agility (Ag)	0.812
Collaboration (Col)	0.924
Traceability (Tr)	0.927
SC resilience (SCRES)	0.901
Circular Economy Practices (CEP)	0.898
Blockchain Technology (BCT)	0.801
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)	0.916

(b). Convergent Validity

Convergent validity implies to the extent to which multiple measures of a construct that are theoretically expected to be related, are indeed found to be related in practice (Gefeb, Straub & Boudreau, 2000). In other words, convergent validity assesses whether the different indicators or measures used to assess the same underlying concept or construct are converging to measure that construct. The key idea is that if the measures are truly capturing the same underlying phenomenon, they should be strongly correlated with each other. The assessment of convergent validity is important because it helps establish the construct validity of a measurement approach. If the multiple indicators meant to measure the same construct are not strongly related, it suggests that they may not be accurately reflecting the intended underlying concept. By demonstrating convergent validity, researchers can have more confidence that their measurement approach is valid and that the different indicators are indeed tapping into the same theoretical construct as intended. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) should be greater than 0.5 to demonstrate acceptable convergent validity. This indicates that the latent construct explains at least 50% of the variance in its indicators. The results of the AVE are displayed in Table 6.4.

The AVE can be calculated using the following formula, according to Fornell C & Larcker F D, (1981):
 $AVE = \frac{(\text{summation of squared factor loadings})}{(\text{summation of squared factor loadings}) + (\text{summation of error variances})}$

$$AVE = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2)}{n}$$

Where “λ” represents factor loadings (standardised regression weights) and “i” represents the total number of items.

Table 6-4 Convergent Validity

Constructs	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Agility	0.519
Collaboration	0.710
Traceability	0.718
SC resilience	0.566
Circular Economy Practices	0.595
Blockchain	0.574
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance	0.686

(c). Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity measures the extent to which a construct is empirically distinct from other constructs in the structural model (Hair et al., 2013). A research study contains several measurements; therefore, each construct must have its unique identity and not overlap. Discriminant validity statistically determines the individuality of the constructs. It indicates that each component in the model is unique and represents its own set of principles. To demonstrate discriminant validity, the square root of the average variance extraction must be greater than the value of the inter-construct correlations. The constructs' discriminant validity was tested in this study using two criteria. These were the Fornell-Larcker criterion and Heterotrait-Monotrait. The Fornell-Larcker criterion is a measure that compares the square root of the average variance extraction (AVE) of each latent construct to the latent inter-construct correlation with other latent variables in the model (Hair et al., 2013). Table 6.5 demonstrates The Fornell-Lacker criterion that the square root of the average variance extraction for each latent construct is higher than the correlation between latent constructs in the model.

Table 6-5 Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Constructs	Ag	CEP	SCRES	Tr	Col	SSCP	BCT
Ag	0.72						
CEP	0.20	0.77					
SCRES	0.46	0.29	0.75				
Tr	0.26	0.59	0.31	0.85			
Col	0.47	0.19	0.39	0.17	0.84		
SSCP	0.38	0.42	0.51	0.46	0.24	0.83	
BCT	0.31	0.65	0.35	0.54	0.19	0.49	0.76

Although the Fornell-Larcker criterion has been widely used to evaluate discriminant validity by assessing shared variance, but recent research has raised concerns about the sensitivity of this test in detecting discriminant validity difficulties between constructs. A modern approach to assess discriminant validity is Heterotrait - Monotrait Ratio of correlations (HTMT). Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt (2012) proposed an approach based on the multi trait-multimethod matrix, to assess the discriminant validity called the Heterotrait - Monotrait Ratio of correlations (HTMT). The HTMT method assesses the ratio between inter-construct correlations and intra-construct correlations for two constructs. In simpler terms, it evaluates the correlations among indicators across different constructs relative to the correlations among indicators within the same construct. Discriminant validity between two reflective constructs is demonstrated when the HTMT score is less than 0.90. Table 6.6 reveals that there are no Discriminant validity issues in the model. Therefore, the measurement model was concluded to be finalised to test the hypothesis, as there were no issues with validity or reliability.

Table 6-6 Heterotrait - Monotrait Ratio of correlations (HTMT)

	BCT	Ag	SSCP	Col	Tr	SCRES	CEP
BCT							
Ag	0.31						
SSCP	0.49	0.38					
Col	0.19	0.47	0.24				
Tr	0.53	0.26	0.45	0.17			
SCRES	0.34	0.45	0.51	0.39	0.30		
CEP	0.65	0.20	0.41	0.19	0.57	0.28	

6.4 Structural Model

The second step in performing Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) is assessment of structural model to test the hypothesis. The relationship between the constructs was assessed by examining the paths in the structural model. The forthcoming sections will present the outcomes of the structural model testing.

6.4.1 Structural Model Assessment

To test the relationships between constructs a structural model was generated through AMOS 29. A good fitting model is accepted if the value of the CMIN/df is <5, the goodness of fit (GFI) indices; the Tucker and Lewis Index (TLI) and the Confirmatory fit index (CFI) is > 0.90 (Hair et al., 2010). In addition, an adequate- fitting model was accepted if the AMOS computed value of the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) is <0.05 and root mean square error approximation (RMSEA) is between 0.05 and 0.08 (Hair et al., 2010). The fit indices for the model shown in the table 6.7 fell within the acceptable range CMIN/df=3.34, goodness of fit (GFI)= 0.99, TLI=0.93, CFI=0.99, SRMR=0.02, RMSEA= 0.06.

Table 6-7 Model Fit Indices for structural model

Indices	Estimated values	Interpretation
CMIN/df	3.34	Acceptable
GFI	0.99	Excellent
CFI	0.99	Excellent
TLI	0.93	Excellent
SRMR	0.02	Excellent
RMSEA	0.06	Excellent

6.4.2 Hypothesis Testing

The value of the standardised coefficients in the model (See fig 6.2) reveals the strength of theoretical relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), SC resilience, circular economy practices and sustainable supply chain performance. The figure shows that agility has the strongest positive effect on SCRES ($b = 0.35$) but does not contribute to CEP ($b = 0.00$), while traceability strongly drives CEP ($b = 0.60$) and modest effect on SCRES ($b = 0.19$). Collaboration has a modest effect on SCRES ($b = 0.20$) and a marginal effect on CEP ($b = 0.09$). Both SCRES ($b = 0.36$) and CEP ($b = 0.17$) positively impact SSCP, mediating the effects of capabilities on performance. This demonstrates the interconnected roles of capabilities, resilience, and circularity in achieving sustainability. Further explanation of the below model is provided in subsequent sections.

Figure 6.2 Structural Model

6.4.2.1 Direct Effect

The current study proposed five main hypotheses to test the direct relationship between variables. The hypothesis **H1** stated “**SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) have a direct and positive impact on SC resilience**”, this hypothesis was further subdivided into three hypotheses H1a, H1b, H1c. The table 6.8 shows that for H1a (Ag→SCRES) the standardised coefficient value was $b=0.347$, $t\text{-value} = 6.01$ and $p<0.001$. Therefore, study assessed that the hypothesis H1a is supported, indicating that supply chain agility has strong positive impact on SC resilience.

The standardised coefficient value for H1b (Col→SCRES) was $b=0.196$, $t\text{-value} = 3.48$, and $p<0.001$. The empirical findings of this study confirm the acceptance of hypothesis H1b, demonstrating that supply chain collaboration has a positive and significant impact on SC resilience.

The standardised coefficient value for H1c (Tr→SCRES) was $b=0.187$, with a $t\text{-value}$ of 3.73 and $p\text{-value} <0.001$. The empirical results of this study supported hypothesis H1c, illustrating that supply chain traceability has a positive and significant impact on SC resilience.

Hypothesis H2 stated that **“SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) have a direct and positive impact on CE Practices”**, this hypothesis was further subdivided into three hypotheses H2a, H2b, H2c. Table 6.8 shows that the standardised coefficient value for H2a (Ag→CEP) was $b=-0.002$, with a $t\text{-value}$ of -0.04 and $p\text{-value} =0.97$. The empirical results of this study not supported hypothesis H2a, illustrating that supply chain agility has a negative and insignificant impact on CE practices.

The standardised coefficient value for H2b (Col→CEP) was $b=0.094$, with a $t\text{-value}$ of 1.77 and a $p\text{-value}$ of <0.01 . The study's empirical results supported hypothesis H2b, showing that supply chain collaboration has a positive impact on CE practices. Similarly, the standardised coefficient value for H2c (Tr→CEP) in Table 6.8 is $b=0.604$, with a $t\text{-value}$ of 12.82 and a $p\text{-value}$ of <0.001 . The study's empirical findings supported hypothesis H2c, demonstrating that supply chain traceability has a strong positive impact on CE practices.

Hypothesis H3 stated that **“SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) have a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance”**, this hypothesis was further subdivided into three hypotheses H3a, H3b and H3c. Table 6.8 shows that the standardised coefficient value for H3a (Ag→SSCP) was $b=0.161$, with a $t\text{-value}$ of 2.87 and $p\text{-value} <0.001$. The empirical results of this study supported hypothesis H3a, illustrating that supply chain has a positive and significant impact on sustainable supply chain performance.

The standardised coefficient value for H3b (Col→SSCP) was $b=-0.056$, with a $t\text{-value}$ of -1.06 and $p\text{-value} =0.29$. The empirical results of this study not supported hypothesis H3b, illustrating that supply chain collaboration has a negative and insignificant impact on sustainable supply chain performance.

The standardised coefficient value for H3c (Tr→SSCP) was $b=0.225$, with a $t\text{-value}$ of 3.89 and $p\text{-value}<0.001$. The empirical results of this study supported hypothesis H3c, illustrating that traceability has a strong positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance.

Hypothesis H4 postulated that **“SC resilience has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance”**. Based on the data in table 6.8, the standardised coefficient value for H4 (SCRES→SSCP) was $b=0.361$, with a $t\text{-value}$ of 6.79 and a $p\text{-value}$ of <0.001 . The empirical findings of the study supported hypothesis H4, demonstrating the strong positive relationship between SC resilience and sustainable supply chain performance.

Hypothesis H5 implied that **“CE Practices has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance”**. The standardised coefficient value for H5 (CEP→SSCP) was $b=0.172$, with a $t\text{-value}$ of 1.77 and a $p\text{-value}$ of >0.05 . The empirical results of this study not supported hypothesis H5, illustrating that CE practices has a negative and insignificant impact on sustainable supply chain performance.

value of 3.04 and a p-value of <0.001. The empirical findings of the study supported hypothesis H5, demonstrating the CE Practices has a positive and significant impact on sustainable supply chain performance.

Table 6-8 Direct Effect

Relationship	Standardised Co-efficient	t-Value	p-Value	Result
H1a: Ag→ SCRES	0.347	6.01	***	Supported
H1b: Col→ SCRES	0.196	3.48	***	Supported
H1c: Tr→ SCRES	0.187	3.73	***	Supported
H2a: Ag→ CEP	-0.002	-0.04	0.97	Not Supported
H2b: Col→ CEP	0.094	1.77	**	Supported
H2c: Tr→ CEP	0.604	12.82	***	Supported
H3a: Ag→ SSCP	0.161	2.87	***	Supported
H3b: Col→ SSCP	-0.056	-1.06	0.29	Not Supported
H3c: Tr→ SSCP	0.225	3.89	***	Supported
H4: SCRES→SSCP	0.361	6.79	***	Supported
H5: CEP →SSCP	0.172	3.04	***	Supported

Notes: *p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.001

6.4.2.2 Mediation Effect

Mediation can be understood as a causal chain wherein one variable influences a second variable, which in turn impacts a third variable. The initial variable is termed the independent variable X, while the second variable acts as the mediator M, and the third variable represents the dependent variable Y as shown in figure 6.3. The relationship between the independent variable, X, and the mediating variable, M, is depicted by path a, while the influence of the mediating variable, M, on the dependent variable, Y, is represented by path b. In mediation analysis, direct, indirect, and total effects delineate the pathways through which independent variables influence dependent variables. A direct effect signifies a direct relationship between an independent variable and a dependent variable, considering the presence of a mediator (c'). Conversely, an indirect effect denotes the pathway from an independent variable to a mediator and subsequently to a dependent variable (a*b). The total effect captures both the direct effect between two constructs and the indirect effect that flows through the mediator ($c = c' + a*b$), reflecting the combined influence of both pathways on the dependent variable as shown in figure 6.3. Mediation is observed when the influence of the independent variable X on the dependent variable Y is either partially or wholly transmitted through the mediator M.

Figure 6.3 Direct and indirect effects in mediation analysis

The bootstrapping approach developed by Hayes et al. (2013) is employed to examine whether mediator M, mediates the relationship between the independent variable, X, and the dependent variable, Y. This method, which is non-parametric, avoids violating normality assumptions, making it suitable even for small sample sizes. Bootstrapping involves repeatedly selecting samples from the dataset to compute the desired statistical outcomes. In this study, Hayes' SPSS process macros were employed to assess indirect, total, and direct effects.

Hypothesis H6 stated that **"SC resilience mediates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance."** This hypothesis was further disaggregated into three sub-hypotheses 6a, 6b and 6c. Analysis detailed in table 6.9 demonstrated that the indirect path coefficient value of $Ag \rightarrow SCRES \rightarrow SSCP$ was 0.263, with a t-value of 3.39 at $p < 0.001$. Thus, hypothesis 6a is supported, indicating that Supply Chain Agility has a positive and significant indirect impact on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance.

The indirect path coefficient value of $Col \rightarrow SCRES \rightarrow SSCP$ was $b=0.243$, with a t-value of 0.597 at $p = 0.55$. Consequently, hypothesis 6b is not supported, suggesting that while Supply Chain Collaboration has a positive effect, it is statistically insignificant in its indirect impact on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance.

Similarly, the indirect path coefficient value of $Tr \rightarrow SCRES \rightarrow SSCP$ was $b= 0.148$, with a t-value of 9.05 at $p < 0.001$. This indicates strong statistical significance, supporting hypothesis 6c. In other words, Supply Chain Traceability has a positive and significant indirect impact on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance, mediated by SC resilience. Figures 6.4, 6.5 and 6.6 illustrated the outcomes of this mediation analysis.

Figure 6.4 Mediation Analysis (Ag→SCRES→SSCP)

Figure 6.5 Mediation Analysis (Col→SCRES→SSCP)

Figure 6.6 Mediation Analysis (Tr→SCRES→SSCP)

Hypothesis H7 stated that "CE Practices mediates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance." This hypothesis was further divided into three sub-hypotheses 7a, 7b and 7c. Table 6.9 reveals that the indirect path coefficient value of Ag→CEP→SSCP was 0.093, with a t-value of 6.67 at $p < 0.001$. This result indicates a statistically significant indirect effect, supporting hypothesis 7a. In essence, it suggests that CE practices play a crucial role in mediating the relationship between Supply Chain Agility and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance.

The indirect path coefficient value of Supply Chain Collaboration $Col \rightarrow CEP \rightarrow SSCP$ is $b=0.030$, with a t -value= 7.81 at $p < 0.001$. This indicates a statistically significant indirect effect, supporting hypothesis 7b. Therefore, it suggested that Supply Chain Collaboration has a positive and significant indirect impact on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance through the mediation of CE Practices.

Table 6.9 indicates that the indirect path coefficient value of $Tr \rightarrow CEP \rightarrow SSCP$ is $b=0.241$, with a t -value of 3.67 at $p < 0.001$. The result indicates the significance indirect effect, supporting hypothesis 7c. Therefore, it suggests that Supply Chain Traceability has a positive and significant indirect impact on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance through the mediation of CE Practices. Figures 6.7, 6.8 and 6.9 depicts the outcomes of this mediation analysis.

Figure 6.7 Mediation Analysis ($Ag \rightarrow CEP \rightarrow SSCP$)

Figure 6.8 Mediation Analysis ($Col \rightarrow CEP \rightarrow SSCP$)

Figure 6.9 Mediation Analysis ($Tr \rightarrow CEP \rightarrow SSCP$)

Table 6-9 Summary of Mediation Effect

Relationship	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Confidence Interval		P-Value	t-Value	Decision
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
H6a: Ag→SCRES→SSCP	0.222	0.263	0.189	0.357	***	3.39	Supported
H6b: Col→SCRES→SSCP	0.036	0.243	0.169	0.334	0.55	0.59	Not Supported
H6c: Tr→SCRES→SSCP	0.504	0.148	0.104	0.261	***	9.05	Supported
H7a: Ag→CEP→SSCP	0.39	0.093	0.045	0.153	***	6.67	Supported
H7b: Col→CEP→SSCP	0.56	0.030	0.041	0.148	***	7.81	Supported
H7c: Tr→CEP→SSCP	0.319	0.241	0.083	0.302	***	3.67	Supported

Notes: *p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.001

6.4.2.3 Moderation Effect

Moderation effect refers to the influence of a third variable on the strength or direction of the relationship between two other variables (González-Romá et al., 2017). Moderation is typically assessed through interaction effects, where the effect of one variable (the moderator) on the relationship between two other variables (the predictor and the outcome) is examined. This moderation effect indicates that the relationship between the predictor and the outcome variable changes depending on the level of the moderator. A moderator variable can influence the strength and even the direction (positive or negative) of the relationship between an independent variable and a dependent variable (Williams et al., 2009)

Hypothesis H8, H9 and H10 is related to moderation effect. To find out the moderator 's effect a two-stage approach for interaction modelling was employed using interaction method. Initially, the variables of interest, namely Ag, Col, Tr and BC, were standardised through mean centring using IBM SPSS, leading to the creation of three new standardised variables. During the second stage, these standardised variables were multiplied to obtain product term of the independent variable and the moderator to test the combined effect of them on dependent variable. The product terms obtained through this stage were Ag x BC, Col x BC and Tr x BC. The significance of the interaction term's impact on the variance of the dependent variable, after controlling for main effects, signalled the presence of moderating effects. Hypothesis H8 stated that **“BCT moderates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and SC resilience.”** This hypothesis was further broken down into three sub-hypotheses H8a, H8b and H8c. The results in Table 6.10 reveals that the product term Ag x BC and SCRES are positively linked at standardized coefficient (β) of 0.057 and p-value <0.05. Similarly, the product term Col x BC and SCRES are positively linked at standardized coefficient (β) of 0.195 and p<0.05. Whereas the moderator BC influence the negative relationship between Tr and SCRES, indicating BC's significant role in weakening the strength of the Tr-SCRES association with standardized coefficient (β) of -0.094 and p=0.40. Figures 6.10, 6.11 and 6.12 present the moderating slopes graphically.

Figure 6.10 BC strengthens the positive relationship between Ag and SCRES

Figure 6.11 BC strengthens the positive relationship between Col and SCRES

Figure 6.12 BC dampens the positive relationship between Tr and SCRES

Hypothesis H9 stated that “BCT moderates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and CE practices.” This hypothesis was further broken down into three sub-hypotheses H9a, H9b and H9c. The results in table 6.10 reveals that BCT weakens the negative relationship between Ag and CEP, suggesting BCT's significant role in influencing the strength of the Ag-CEP relationship with standardized coefficient (β) = 0.069 and p-value = 0.31. However, a positive association between collaboration and CE practices and traceability and CE practices exist by the influence of BCT at standardized coefficient values of (β)= 0.008 and (β)= 0.023 respectively at p-value<0.01 for both. Figures 6.13, 6.14 and 6.15 present the moderating slopes graphically.

Figure 6.13 BC dampens the negative relationship between Ag and CEP

Figure 6.14 BC strengthens the positive relationship between Col and CEP

Figure 6.15 BC strengthens the positive relationship between Tr and CEP

Hypothesis H10 stated that “**BCT moderates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance.**” This hypothesis was further broken down into three sub-hypotheses 10a 10b and 10c. The results in table 6.10 reveals that the product term Ag x BC and SSCP are positively linked at standardized coefficient (β) of 0.024 and p-value<0.01.

The results also reveals that the product term Col x BC and SSCP are positively linked at standardized coefficient (β) of 0.023 and p-value<0.01. Whereas the moderator BCT reduces the positive relationship between Tr and SSCP, indicating BCT 's significant influence on the strength of the Tr-SSCP relationship with standardized coefficient (β) of -0.061 and p value= 0.60. Figures 6.16, 6.17 and 6.18 present the moderating slopes graphically.

Figure 6.16 BC strengthens the positive relationship between Ag and SSCP

Figure 6.17 BC strengthens the positive relationship between Col and SSCP

Figure 6.18 BC dampens the positive relationship between Tr and SSCP

Table 6-10 Summary of Moderating Effect

Relationship	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
H8a: SCRES <--- Ag x BC	0.057	0.096	0.592	*
H8b: SCRES <--- Col x BC	0.195	0.102	1.913	*
H8c: SCRES <--- Tr x BC	-0.094	0.111	-0.84	0.40
H9a: CEP <--- Ag x BC	0.069	0.068	1.016	0.31
H9b: CEP <--- Col x BC	0.008	0.07	0.108	**
H9c: CEP <--- Tr x BC	0.023	0.068	0.342	**
H10a: SSCP <--- Ag x BC	0.024	0.108	0.219	**
H10b: SSCP <--- Col x BC	0.023	0.116	0.196	**
H10c: SSCP <--- Tr x BC	-0.061	0.117	-0.522	0.60

Notes: *p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.001

6.5 Summary

The SEM analysis provided empirical support for the hypothesized relationships in the study. The results suggest that enhancing agility, collaboration, and traceability can directly contribute to building SC resilience. However, agility and collaboration did not demonstrate a significant positive impact on circular economy practices and sustainable supply chain performance, respectively. Therefore, the findings indicate that improving SC resilience and implementing circular economy practices can positively influence the overall sustainable performance of the supply chain. These insights can inform managerial decision-making and guide supply chain strategies aimed at enhancing sustainability and resilience.

For mediation analysis the results suggest that SC resilience plays an important mediating role in translating the benefits of agility and traceability into improved sustainable supply chain performance. However, the impact of collaboration on sustainable performance was not found to be mediated by SC resilience.

Interestingly, the findings indicate that the implementation of CE practices can help amplify the positive effects of agility, collaboration, and traceability on sustainable supply chain performance. This highlights the importance of integrating circular economy principles to enhance the sustainability outcomes of supply chain initiatives. Overall, the mediation analysis provides valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms through which different SC capabilities and practices influence sustainable supply chain performance.

The findings of moderation analysis suggest that the integration of Blockchain technology plays a crucial moderating role in the supply chain management context. Specifically: Blockchain technology enhances the synergistic effects between agility and collaboration on building SC resilience but dampens the positive impact of traceability on SC resilience. Therefore, Blockchain technology strengthens the positive relationships between collaboration and traceability on circular economy practices, while also mitigating the negative effect of agility on CE practices. Interestingly, Blockchain technology strengthens the positive influence of agility and collaboration on sustainable supply chain performance but dampens the positive effect of traceability in this regard.

CHAPTER 7 : DISCUSSION, IMPLICATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

This chapter primarily focuses on the discussions and conclusions derived from the analysis of the collected data. The chapter started with a summary of the research directions. This study compares its findings to previous research. This comparison tries to clarify data-supported links and those that contradict earlier conclusions. Comparing current research to existing literature improves comprehension of the phenomena under study. This chapter wraps up the thesis by presenting the conclusions, major theoretical and practical contributions of the study, outlining its limitations, and offering recommendations for further research.

7.1 Recapping the Key Findings

The integration of SC resilience (SCRES) and Circular Economy (CE) concept to drive sustainable supply chain performance remains relatively limited in the existing literature. Existing scholarly works tend to approach these domains as separate and distinct subjects, resulting in a fragmented understanding of their potential combined impact. Furthermore, there is a scarcity of comprehensive studies that holistically examine the interplay of SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Blockchain technology between SC resilience and circular economy practices to catalyse the achievement of sustainable performance. This study fills a gap in the literature by bridging these complementary concepts, thereby unlocking their collective potential to foster sustainability in supply chain performance.

Following up on the previous chapter's discussion, table 7.1, summarises the study's aims, research questions, and objectives. Furthermore, table 7.2 provides a quick overview of the study's findings, the key outcomes that merged as a reference for further discussion on the research findings and figure 7.1 and 7.2 shows the proposed and evolving conceptual frameworks respectively.

Table 7-1 Research Directions

Aim	Research Questions	Objectives
<p>The primary aim of this study is to investigate the impact of supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability), supply chain resilience, CE practices and Blockchain technology on sustainable supply chain performance.</p>	<p>RQ1. <i>What is the impact of SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on SC resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance?</i></p> <p>RQ2. <i>What is the impact of SC resilience and CE practices on sustainable supply chain performance?</i></p> <p>RQ3. <i>Do SC resilience and CE practices play a mediating role between SC capabilities and sustainable supply chain performance?</i></p> <p>RQ4. <i>Does Blockchain technology moderate the influence of SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on SC resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance?</i></p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) To investigate the impact of SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on SC resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance 2) To investigate the impact of SC resilience and CE practices on sustainable supply chain performance. 3) To examine the mediating role of SC resilience and CE practices between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance. 4) To examine the moderating role of Blockchain technology on supply chain capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), SC resilience and CE practices. 5) To develop a comprehensive framework of SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), SC resilience, CE practices and Blockchain technology in achieving sustainable supply chain performance in food and drink manufacturing industry UK.

Table 7-2 Key Research Findings

Hypothesis	Independent Variable	Dependant variable	Results
<i>H1: SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) have a direct and positive impact on SC resilience</i>			
• H1a: Agility has a direct and positive impact on SC resilience	Agility	SC resilience	Supported
• H1b: Collaboration has a direct and positive impact on SC resilience	Collaboration	SC resilience	Supported
• H1c: Traceability has a direct and positive impact on SC resilience	Traceability	SC resilience	Supported
<i>H2: SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) have a direct and positive impact on CE Practices</i>			
• H2a: Agility has a direct and positive impact on CE Practices	Agility	CE Practices	Not Supported
• H2b: Collaboration has a direct and positive impact on CE Practices	Collaboration	CE Practices	Supported
• H2c: Traceability has a direct and positive impact on CE Practices	Traceability	CE Practices	Supported
<i>H3: SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) have a direct and positive impact on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance</i>			
• H3a: Agility has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance	Agility	Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
• H3b: Collaboration has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance	Collaboration	Sustainable supply chain performance	Not Supported
• H3c: Traceability has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance	Traceability	Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
<i>H4: SC resilience has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance</i>	SC resilience	Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
<i>H5: CE Practices has a direct and positive impact on m sustainable supply chain performance</i>	CE Practices	Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
<i>H6: SC resilience mediates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance</i>			
• H6a: SC resilience mediates the relationship between agility, and sustainable supply chain performance	Agility	Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
• H6b: SC resilience mediates the relationship between collaboration, and sustainable supply chain performance	Collaboration	Sustainable supply chain performance	Not supported
• H6c: SC resilience mediates the relationship between traceability, and sustainable supply chain performance	Traceability	Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
<i>H7: CE Practices mediates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance</i>			

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H7a: CE Practices mediates the relationship between agility and sustainable supply chain performance 	Agility	Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H7b: CE Practices mediates the relationship between collaboration and sustainable supply chain performance 	Collaboration	Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H7c: CE Practices mediates the relationship between traceability and sustainable supply chain performance 	Traceability	Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
<i>H8: BCT moderates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and SC resilience.</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H8a: BCT moderates the relationship between agility and SC resilience 	BCT	Agility, SC resilience	Supported
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H8b: BCT moderates the relationship between collaboration and SC resilience 	BCT	Collaboration, SC resilience	Supported
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H8c: BCT moderates the relationship between traceability and SC resilience 	BCT	Traceability, SC resilience	Not supported
<i>H9: BCT moderates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and CE practices</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H9a: BCT moderates the relationship between agility and CE practices 	BCT	Agility, CE practices	Not supported
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H9b: BCT moderates the relationship between collaboration and CE practices 	BCT	Collaboration, CE practices	Supported
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H9c: BCT moderates the relationship between traceability and CE practices 	BCT	Traceability, CE practices	Supported
<i>H10: BCT moderates the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H10a: BCT moderates the relationship between agility and sustainable supply chain performance 	BCT	Agility, Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H10b: BCT moderates the relationship between collaboration and sustainable supply chain performance 	BCT	Collaboration, Sustainable supply chain performance	Supported
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H10c: BCT moderates the relationship between traceability and sustainable supply chain performance 	BCT	Traceability, Sustainable supply chain performance	Not supported

Figure 7.1 Proposed Conceptual Framework

To comprehensively address the first research question, a series of hypotheses H1a, H1b, H1c, H2a, H2b, H2c, and H3a, H3b, H3c were formulated and rigorously tested. The findings revealed that SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) have significant positive relationship with SC resilience (SCRES). Notably, while agility did not exhibit a significant association with circular economy practices (CEP), and collaboration did not significantly influence sustainable supply chain performance (SSCP), the other relationships yielded statistically significant results.

Through the comprehensive empirical examination, 2 out of the 9 hypothesized relationships were found to be statistically insignificant. These findings provided substantial support in addressing the *first research question*, shedding light on the complex interplay between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), SC resilience, circular economy practices, and sustainable performance within the context of food supply chain management as shown in the figure 7.2.

To address *research question 2*, the study tested hypotheses 4 and 5. The findings revealed that both SC resilience and circular economy (CE) practices had a statistically significant positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance (see figure 7.2).

To investigate *research question 3* a mediation analysis was performed and a series of hypothesis 6a, 6b, 6c and 7a, 7b and 7c were tested. The mediation analysis yielded that SC resilience mediates a positive and significant relationship between agility, traceability, and sustainable supply chain performance. However, the impact of collaboration on sustainable performance was not found to be mediated by SC resilience. The study findings further revealed that CE practices mediate a positive and significant relationship between agility, collaboration, traceability, and sustainable supply chain performance. About abovementioned six hypotheses, five have been found to be empirically supported and one has not (H6b) (figure 7.2). This result provided substantial empirical support in addressing the third research question by unveiling the mediating roles played by SC resilience and CE practices, on the relationships between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and sustainable performance. The results of mediation analysis can be seen in figure 7.2.

To address the *research question 4*, a moderation analysis was performed. This involved testing a set of hypotheses, specifically 8a, 8b, 8c, 9a, 9b, 9c, 10a, 10b, and 10c. The statistical results supported 6 out of nine hypothesis 8a,8b, 9b, 9c and 10a,10b and revealed that Blockchain technology provided partial moderation effect to all the relationships in hypotheses 8,9 and 10 (figure 7.2). The findings of moderation analysis suggested that Blockchain technology plays a crucial moderating role between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), SC resilience, circular economy practices, and sustainable performance.

The following section presents the findings from the surveys and includes a discussion on these results. The hypotheses in this study are examined considering the rationale behind earlier research and theories. Insignificant and contradicting findings are analysed alongside potential explanations and justifications.

Figure 7.2 Evolving Conceptual Framework

7.2 Discussion of the Findings

The outcomes of this study are explained in accordance with the sequence of research questions, research objectives, and hypotheses. The initial discussion focused on the impact of supply chain capabilities, such as agility, collaboration, and traceability, on SC resilience, CE practices, and sustainable supply chain performance. This is followed by the discussion on the effect of SC resilience, CE practices, on sustainable supply chain performance. After that the discussion focused on the role of SC resilience and circular economy (CE) practices as a mediating factor between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance. Lastly, the study discussed the potential moderating role of Blockchain technology in the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and key variables SC resilience, circular economy practices, and sustainable supply chain performance. The analysis aimed to shed light on how the adoption and implementation of Blockchain technology might amplify or alter the effects of these SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on achieving SC resilience, promoting CE practices, and enhancing overall sustainable performance of food supply chain.

Notwithstanding statistical significance and model fit are essential considerations in academic research, they should not be regarded as the ultimate objectives. The primary goal of a researcher to investigate the numerical data lies in the pursuit of uncovering novel relationships and gaining deeper insights into the subject matter under investigation. The true essence of scholarly inquiry resides in the exploration of uncharted territories, challenging existing paradigms, and contributing to the development of knowledge within the field of study.

The subsequent sections will provide a comprehensive discussion on the empirical findings derived from the surveys presented in the previous chapter.

7.2.1 Effect of SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on SC Resilience, CE Practices and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (RQ1)

The first objective of this study is to investigate the impact of SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on SC resilience (SCRES), CE practices (CEP) and sustainable supply chain performance (SSCP). This objective was achieved by answering RQ1.

(a). Effect of SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on SC Resilience

From the vast and multifaceted literature on supply chain capabilities, the researcher conducted a rigorous literature review to identify the key SC capabilities that integrate SC resilience (SCRES) and circular economy practices (CEP) to achieve sustainable supply chain performance (SSCP). Through a meticulous examination of the intricate and fragmented body of knowledge, three fundamental capabilities emerged as critical enablers: agility, collaboration, and traceability. The comprehensive analysis was facilitated through a survey conducted among UK food and drink manufacturers. This survey provided the empirical insights into the interplay between these key SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and the desired outcomes of resilience, circularity, and sustainability of food supply chains.

The results of the research revealed that agility has a positive and significant ($b=0.347$, $p<0.001$) impact on SC resilience (SCRES). This result supported the first hypothesis H1a and provided empirical evidence that agility, which refers to the ability to quickly adapt to changes and disruptions, has a significant positive influence on enhancing the resilience of supply chains. This outcome aligns with the assertions of (I. Kazancoglu et al., 2022), who claimed that agility exerts a tangible effect on SC resilience. The results are also resonating with the (Nandi et al., 2021a) that agility equips organization's supply chains with the capability to effectively combat unforeseen adversities. It empowers them to withstand and overcome threats that may arise in the dynamic market landscape. By embracing the inherent variations and fluctuations in the business environment, agile supply chains can competently adapt and turn these challenges into strategic advantages, ultimately enhancing their resilience. Studies of Aslam et al. (2020) and Scala and Lindsay (2021) also support the findings that agility plays an important role in SC resilience.

Several researchers have also explored the complementary mediating role of agility in fostering SC resilience. By acting as a mediator, agility facilitates the translation of capabilities such as flexibility (I. Kazancoglu et al., 2022), visibility and velocity (Nguyen Thi et al., 2023), supply chain ambidexterity (H. Aslam, Khan, et al., 2020) innovation (Sabahi & Parast, 2020) into improved resilience outcomes, enabling supply chains to better withstand and recover from disruptions.

The convergence of findings from this research and numerous other studies substantiates the pivotal role of agility in fostering SC resilience. Agility empowers organizations to swiftly adapt to changes, mitigate disruptions, and capitalize on opportunities, thereby enhancing their ability to withstand and recover from challenges within the dynamic supply chain landscape.

The research unveiled another pivotal finding: supply chain collaboration exerts a positive and statistically significant influence ($b=0.196$, $p<0.001$) on SC resilience (SCRES), thereby lending support to hypothesis H1b. This outcome resonates with the conclusions drawn by Scholten & Schilder (2015), whose findings highlight the critical role that supply chain collaboration in achieving SC resilience. The study further elucidates that mechanism of collaborative activities among organizations facilitate the information sharing capability which enhances supply chain visibility and transparency. Consequently, this collaborative approach ensures a more effective response to disruptions, both upstream and downstream within the supply chain ecosystem. The findings of this study are further substantiated by the research conducted by Gani et al. (2023), who asserted that collaboration, information technology, and leadership are essential capabilities for organizations to prepare for and navigate uncertainties effectively. Additionally, Y. Liu et al. (2024) lends credence to the argument that supply chain collaboration fosters both resilience and robustness within supply networks, proposing that collaboration mediates the role of digitization in increasing SC resilience. Lusiantoro & Pradiptyo (2022) demonstrated the importance of collaboration as a crucial element in fostering SC resilience, especially during times of disruption.

Moreover, a multitude of scholarly works, including (A. A. Ali et al., 2024; Scala & Lindsay, 2021; Song et al., 2022; Umar & Wilson, 2021; J. Zhou et al., 2024) and (A. A. Ali et al., 2024), consistently identify collaboration as a pivotal factor in fostering SC resilience. These findings from various researchers and current research can help industry experts in lending substantial credibility to the notion that supply chain collaboration is a critical enabler of SC resilience.

One interesting finding is that supply chain traceability has a positive and significant impact ($b=0.187$, $p<0.001$) on SC resilience and supported H1c hypothesis. This result pointed out an interesting fact regarding the role of traceability in achieving SC resilience (SCRES) which has received relatively less attention in research (Razak et al., 2023). This result provided empirical evidence to support the findings of (Razak et al., 2023) and (Zhao et al., 2022). Supply chain traceability enable end-to-end visibility and tracking of products, materials, and components throughout the supply chain, facilitating early detection of deviations, anomalies, or disruptions (Kelepouris et al., 2007; Timmer & Kaufmann, 2017). The unique contribution of this study lies in quantitatively assessing the impact of traceability on SC resilience, particularly within the context of the agri-food supply chain. By empirically demonstrating this relationship, this research highlights the importance of traceability as a critical enabler of resilience, complementing existing literature on other resilience factors such as agility and collaboration.

(b). Effect of SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on CE Practices

The result of this research shows that there is a negative and insignificant association between agility and the adoption or implementation of circular economy practices ($b=-0.002$, $p=0.97$), not supported H2a. This result is somewhat counterintuitive. Therefore, several studies highlight the complementary role of agility in facilitating and enabling the transition towards a circular economy model. Nandi et al. (2021a) emphasizes the importance of localization, agility, and digitization as key enablers for the successful implementation of circular economy (CE) practices. Specifically, they highlight the crucial role of agility in facilitating the identification, manufacturing, and delivery of byproducts (former wastes) for new applications and customers within the circular economy model. Bag (2023) highlighted the role of agility in facilitating remanufacturing operations, which are a crucial component of circular economy practices. Javeed & Akram (2024) suggests that organizational agility acts as a critical enabler, allowing firms to proactively respond to institutional pressures and effectively translate those pressures into tangible actions and initiatives that advance their circular economy adoption. Agility empowers organizations to navigate the uncertainties and complexities inherent in the transition towards a circular model, ultimately enhancing their ability to meet stakeholder expectations and regulatory requirements while achieving sustainable growth and competitive advantage. M.-L. Tseng et al. (2024) also highlights the importance of agility as an enabler of CE practise in supply chain management.

Although this study did not find a significant direct association between agility and the adoption of circular economy (CE) practices, this result contrasts with existing literature, which suggests that agility

plays a complementary role in facilitating the transition toward a circular economy model. (Salandri et al., 2022) noted that agility can create challenges for operations such as recycling, recovery, and reuse, particularly when rapid adjustments and modifications are required. These processes often necessitate changes to production systems to accommodate new and atypical phases, redesign products to incorporate recycled materials, implement new sorting operations to differentiate reusable and recyclable materials, and manage inventories that integrate virgin and recycled raw materials alongside new and recycled goods.

The results of this study indicated a significant positive correlation between collaboration and the implementation of circular economy (CE) practices ($b=0.094$, $p<0.01$). This aligns with previous research that highlighting the crucial role of collaboration among supply chain stakeholders in enabling and continuously improving CE practices. Calicchio Berardi & Peregrino de Brito (2021) asserted that supply chain collaboration is a key element for adopting CE practices, emphasizing its importance not only for initial implementation but also for ongoing enhancement. Similarly, Bloise (2020) identified collaboration as a prominent foundational theme for operating within a CE framework, particularly in the context of food supply chains where CE principles can be readily applied given the industry's nature. Leising et al. (2018) sought to conceptualize the organizational aspects of supply chain collaboration specifically for CE in the building sector. Furthermore, the study explores the emerging topic of circular value chain collaboration by integrating the fields of sustainable supply chain management and the circular economy. The research findings align with and reinforce the existing literature, that supply chain collaboration is essential to transitioning towards circular economy (Baah et al., 2023; Bag, 2023; Bimpizas-Pinis et al., 2022; Ciccullo et al., 2018; De Angelis et al., 2018; Hennemann Hilario da Silva & Sehnem, 2024; Herczeg et al., 2018; Tosi et al., 2024).

This study not only verifies the results of previous research but also provides empirical evidence that supply chain collaboration is an indispensable SC capability for adopting and implementing CE practices. It serves as a unifying force, bringing together all supply chain partners, from farmers to food manufacturers, to collectively embrace and operationalize circular principles and practices. Effective collaboration among supply chain stakeholders facilitates the implementation of CE strategies, such as resource recovery, product life extension, and closed-loop systems, by fostering information sharing, joint decision-making, and shared responsibility. This holistic approach complements managerial understanding and enhances the sustainability outcomes of circular supply chains, encompassing environmental, economic, and social dimensions.

In essence, the findings underscore the significance of collaboration among supply chain stakeholders in facilitating the adoption and continuous improvement of circular economy practices in food and drink manufacturing industry.

In this study traceability has shown positive relationship with CE practices $b=0.361$, $p <0.001$). This results also resonates with the Anastasiadis et al. (2022). Anastasiadis et al. (2022) work confirms that traceability is indeed play a crucial role for shift towards CE-oriented food SCs. It also revealing an

association between traceability and sustainability-driven CE practices in reduction of food waste. Traceability systems allow the tracking and monitoring of materials, components, and products throughout their entire life cycle. This information is essential for facilitating closed-loop systems, enabling reuse, remanufacturing, and recycling processes (Santana and Ribeiro, 2022, Davari et al., 2023). Traceability provides transparency across supply chains, allowing stakeholders to access information about the origin, composition, and journey of materials and products. This transparency is vital for identifying opportunities for circularity and making informed decisions (Centobelli et al., 2022, Rejeb et al., 2022). The finding of the study supports that traceability plays a crucial role in enabling circular economy practices by providing transparency and accountability throughout the entire product lifecycle. Traceability allows for tracking and monitoring of materials, components, and products from their sourcing to end-of-life management, facilitating the closed-loop circulation of resources (Santana & Ribeiro, 2022).

(c). Effect of SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

This study found that agility is positively associated with sustainable supply chain performance ($b=0.161$, $p < 0.001$). Geyi et al. (2020) research in the oil and gas industry, demonstrate that agile SC capabilities significantly boost both sustainability performance and operational performance. These findings show that companies with agile supply chains can better integrate sustainable practices, leading to improved social and environmental outcomes. The study emphasizes that agility helps in implementing green supply chain practices effectively, thereby enhancing sustainability performance. Alfalla-Luque et al. (2023) conducted meta-analysis of supply chain agility (SCA) and performance relationships and highlighted that agility leads to superior performance outcomes by enabling quick responses to market changes, thus improving overall efficiency and effectiveness. This adaptability not only enhances operational performance but also supports sustainable practices by reducing environmental impact and improving resource utilization. (Blome et al., 2013) highlighted supply chain agility from dynamic capabilities perspective and confirmed its positive influence on firm performance, including sustainability. (Suifan et al., 2020) and Dubey & Gunasekaran (2016) supported the role of agility in sustainable supply chain performance, particularly in humanitarian supply chains. M. Wang & Wang (2024) also highlighted how supply chain agility contributes to sustainability. Nath & Agrawal (2020) identified agility and lean practices as significant factors for social sustainability performance in firms.

The ability of agile supply chains to swiftly adapt to changes, optimize operations, and effectively implement sustainable practices underpins this relationship. Empirical evidence from various industries indicates that agility enhances both operational and sustainability outcomes, making it a crucial factor for achieving long-term sustainability goals in supply chain management. While numerous studies have explored the positive impact of supply chain agility on sustainable performance across different sectors, few have specifically examined this relationship within the food supply chain. This research

distinguishes itself by providing the empirical evidence that agility specifically enhances sustainable supply chain performance in the food supply chain context.

The current study found that supply chain collaboration (SCC) has a negative and insignificant impact on sustainable supply chain performance (SSCP) with a coefficient ($b=-0.056$) and a p-value of 0.29 suggest that there is no statistically significant relationship between these variables. However, the finding of the study is somewhat counterintuitive, as one might expect collaboration in the supply chain to enhance sustainability performance. Collaboration is not automatically beneficial as Cao and Zhang (2011) highlight, it is resource-intensive, requiring significant investments of time, finances, and managerial effort. When these costs outweigh immediate gains, firms may not see a positive impact on sustainability performance, particularly in sectors like food manufacturing, where margins are often tight. Additionally, Vachon and Klassen (2008) note that collaboration introduces coordination complexities and potential conflicts, as partners may have differing goals, levels of commitment, or standards for sustainability practices. These challenges can dilute the potential benefits of collaboration, making its direct effect on sustainability less apparent. Moreover, the benefits of collaboration may be indirect; while SCC did not directly influence SSCP in this study, it may enhance other factors, such as circular economy practices or supply chain resilience, which in turn improve sustainability outcomes, as suggested by the significant mediation effects observed in the analysis. It is also possible that in contexts where sustainability is still emerging as a strategic priority, collaborative efforts remain superficial and thus fail to translate into measurable performance improvements. Further supporting this interpretation, recent research by (Fawcett et al., 2015) explores why collaboration strategies often fail, despite the theoretical benefits promised by the relational view. The study highlights the role of “relational resisters” sociological and structural barriers that interact and reinforce each other to undermine collaborative behaviour. These include trust deficits, fear of opportunism, and a lack of relational routines or skills. This helps explain why, in the current study, collaboration may not have directly improved sustainability performance.

Another important finding is that traceability has a positive and significant impact on sustainable supply chain performance (SSCP), as evidenced by the result ($b=0.225$, $p<0.001$). Traceability in supply chains refers to the ability to track the journey of products and materials from origin to the end consumer. This capability can enhance transparency, accountability, and efficiency within the supply chain, leading to better sustainability outcomes. Several recent studies support this finding: Ma et al. (2023) examined digital transformation's impact on sustainable performance in pharmaceutical supply chains. The study found that digital transformation significantly improves sustainable supply chain performance (SSCP), with traceability playing a crucial mediating role. X. Zhou et al. (2022) investigated the effect of traceability practices on sustainability performance, mediated by dynamic capabilities and moderated by environmental dynamism. Their results showed traceability practices significantly and positively influence firm sustainability performance, partially mediated by dynamic capabilities. Marconi et al. (2017) emphasized the importance of comprehensive traceability in

achieving sustainable supply chain management. Nasyiah et al. (2024) found that traceability systems positively influence halal supply chain management (HSCM) and indirectly affect sustainable performance by identifying and mitigating unsafe products. Koberg & Longoni (2019) stated that higher traceability makes it easier for buyers to rely on first-tier suppliers for managing sub-supplier sustainability outcomes. Garcia-Torres et al. (2019) provided evidence through a literature review that traceability can contribute to supply chain management and triple bottom line sustainability within and beyond supply chain boundaries.

The research findings are consistent with the other studies that a positive and significant relationship between traceability and sustainable supply chain performance. Traceability systems provide end-to-end visibility into the supply chain, enabling companies to track products, materials, and processes from source to consumption. This transparency allows firms to monitor sustainability practices, identify issues, and take corrective actions.

7.2.2 Effect of SC Resilience and CE Practices on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (RQ2)

(a). Effect of SC Resilience on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

The study reveals that SC resilience has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance ($b=0.361$, $p<0.001$). The COVID-19 pandemic exposed the vulnerability of supply chains, prompting the researcher to postulate that for a supply chain to perform sustainably, it must be resilient. However, upon investigating this idea, the literature was found to be dispersed, SC resilience and sustainable supply chain performance have often been discussed separately in the literature, with limited studies exploring their correlation (Fahimnia & Jabbarzadeh, 2016; Ivanov & Dolgui, 2019; Negri et al., 2021; Shishodia et al., 2023). Moreover, with studies consistently pointing to an indirect or mediating relationship between SC resilience and sustainable supply chain performance, rather than a direct positive impact (Piprani et al., 2023; Rahman et al., 2023; X. Zhu & Wu, 2022).

The unique contribution of this research lies in providing empirical evidence of a strong positive relationship between SC resilience and sustainable supply chain performance. The study results provide evidence that SC resilience and sustainable supply chain performance are a "match made in heaven" in the food supply chain context. This implies that for a food supply chain to be truly sustainable, it must first be resilient – able to withstand disruptions and maintain its sustainable practices.

The COVID-19 pandemic served as a catalyst for this research, highlighting the vulnerabilities of supply chains and the need for resilience to ensure sustainability. While previous literature treated resilience and sustainability as separate concepts or explored their relationship indirectly, this study offers empirical evidence of a direct and strong positive correlation between the two.

In essence, the research findings suggest that SC resilience is not merely a complementary factor but a fundamental prerequisite for achieving sustainable supply chain performance, particularly in the food supply chain context. Resilience and sustainability are inextricably linked, and organizations must prioritize building resilient supply chains to ensure long-term sustainability.

(b). Effect of CE Practices on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

The most obvious finding to emerge from the analysis is that CE Practices has a direct and positive impact on sustainable supply chain performance ($b=0.172$, $p<0.001$), supporting H5. The findings of the study are supported by Gunjan Malhotra (2023), who demonstrated a positive impact of circular economy practices on sustainable supply chain performance in manufacturing firms. Additionally, the relationship between supply chain managers and retailers improves with the presence of SC capabilities and flexibility, further strengthened by supply chain integration as a moderating variable. Karmaker et al. (2023) discussed the influence of Industry 4.0 technology on sustainable supply chain performance, particularly within the Bangladeshi ready-made garment sector, utilising green supply chain management and circular economy principles. Similarly, Y. M. Tang et al. (2022) highlighted how circular economy practices enhance production efficiency by reducing economic and environmental costs. S. A. R. Khan et al. (2021) investigated circular economy practices in Pakistani and Taiwanese firms, finding a positive correlation between circular supply chain operations, profitability, and environmental performance. Mora-Contreras et al. (2023) analysed the effect of circular economy practices on companies' sustainability performance, including the internal and external drivers influencing these outcomes. (Arsawan et al., 2024) emphasized that circular economy practices offer opportunities and encourage global cooperation among countries, industries, and businesses to maintain sustainability and protect the environment. The review article by Shekarian et al. (2022) cites multiple studies that demonstrate the positive relationship between adopting sustainable supply chain management practices, which include CE practices, and improved sustainability performance.

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted global supply chains, including those in the food industry, exposing the vulnerabilities and unsustainability of traditional linear supply chain models. This disruption prompted researchers to rethink and explore ways to make food supply chains more sustainable and resilient. Consequently, the collective findings from various studies across industries, along with current research specifically focused on the food and drink manufacturing industry, suggest that implementing circular economy (CE) practices can significantly enhance the sustainability performance of these supply chains in economic, environmental, and social aspects. This study provides empirical evidence and contributes to the growing body of knowledge supporting the adoption of CE practices as a viable and effective approach to achieving sustainable food supply chains. The findings reinforce the idea that embracing CE practices positively impacts the sustainable performance of food supply chains.

7.2.3 Mediating Effect (RQ3)

In general, a variable can be considered a mediator if it explains the relationship between the predictor and the criterion Baron & Kenny (1986). This study assesses the significance of the mediating effects of SC resilience and circular economy (CE) practices between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance. To investigate this, the researcher proposed two main hypotheses, which were further divided into sub-hypotheses to test each dimension. The details are given below:

(a). Mediating Effect of SC Resilience between SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

The results suggested that SC resilience plays an important mediating role in translating the benefits of agility ($b=0.263$, $p < 0.001$) and traceability ($b=0.148$, $p < 0.001$) into improving sustainable supply chain performance, supported 6a and 6c. The existing literature provides strong evidence for the mediating role of SC resilience (SCRES) in the relationship between various capabilities and sustainable supply chain performance. According to Christopher and Peck (2004), agility and resilience are critical for effective supply chain management, especially under volatile market conditions. Resilient supply chains are better at leveraging agility to respond to disruptions. X. Wang et al. (2009) highlighted that traceability systems enhance SC resilience by providing critical information that supports decision-making during disruptions. This enhanced visibility and transparency help mitigate risks and recover faster. Dubey & Gunasekaran (2016) demonstrated that SC resilience significantly impacts sustainable supply chain performance by enabling better resource utilization and reducing the adverse effects of disruptions.

Therefore the mediating role of SC resilience for firm performance also highlighted in various studies; Bahrami & Shokouhyar (2022) demonstrated that SC resilience partially mediates the effect of big data analytics (BDA) capabilities on firm performance. (Haq & Aslam, 2023) stated that SCRES positively mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership capability and supply chain performance. Piprani et al. (2023) proposed that SCRES mediates the association between supply chain integration and supply chain performance. Rezaei et al. (2022) examined how SC resilience and organizational flexibility mediate the link between data analytics capabilities and competitive advantage. Salam & Bajaba (2023) indicated that SC resilience significantly mediates the relationship between the alignment of marketing and supply chain management (MRKT–SCM) and firm performance.

The results of this study align with other studies provide evidence that SC resilience translates the benefits of agility and traceability into improved sustainability performance of supply chain. By establishing this mediating role of resilience, the study contributes a valuable insight to the existing literature on sustainable supply chain management, agility, traceability, and resilience.

The study found that supply chain (SC) resilience does not mediate the relationship between collaboration and sustainable supply chain performance as hypothesis 6b was not supported. These finding challenges assumption that resilience is always a necessary link between collaborative efforts and sustainability gains (Christopher and Peck, 2004; Wieland and Wallenburg, 2013). It may indicate that collaborative relationships, by themselves, are strong enough to foster sustainability initiatives without necessarily needing to first improve the firm's capacity to handle disruptions (Vachon and Klassen, 2008; Cao and Zhang, 2011). Alternatively, it could reflect the possibility that resilience and collaboration operate as parallel mechanisms rather than sequential ones, each contributing to sustainability in different ways (Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015; Scholten and Schilder, 2015). This result provides important insight into the complex dynamics of sustainable supply chains, suggesting that

managers should not automatically assume that building resilience is the only pathway for translating collaboration into sustainability benefits (Jüttner and Maklan, 2011).

(b). Mediating Effect of CE Practices between SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

The mediation analysis in the study indicates that CE practices significantly mediate the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance, supported 7a ($b=0.093$, $p < 0.001$), 7b ($b=0.030$, $p < 0.001$), and 7c ($b=0.241$, $p < 0.001$). Genovese et al. (2017) found that CE practices like recycling and modular product design enhance supply chain agility by allowing quicker adaptation to resource scarcity and market demands. This supports the finding that CE practices mediate the impact of agility on sustainability. Franco (2017) highlights that CE practices necessitate collaboration among supply chain partners to achieve shared sustainability goals, such as reducing waste and improving resource efficiency. This supports the mediation effect of CE practices observed between collaboration and sustainable supply chain performance. Govindan & Hasanagic (2018) indicate that CE practices require robust traceability systems to ensure proper recycling and reuse of materials. This supports the mediation effect between traceability and sustainable supply chain performance. (Riggs et al., 2023) offers theoretical insight that reveals supply chain management capabilities (SCMC) are linked with CE practices, and both constructs sequentially mediate the relationship between Big Data Analytics Capabilities (BDAC) and sustainable performance (SP). Edwin Cheng et al. (2022) provide empirical evidence supporting the mediating function of Circular Economy (CE) practices and Supply Chain (SC) flexibility within the sustainable Big Data Analytics (BDA) capabilities framework. Laguir et al. (2024) found that the impact of eco-control systems, as mediated by CE practices, varies depending on the nature of the company's performance.

The mediation of CE practices in this study indicates that merely having SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) is not sufficient for achieving sustainable performance; it is the integration of these capabilities with CE practices that amplifies their impact. This mediation underscores the importance of embedding CE principles within food supply chain strategies to enhance sustainability outcomes effectively.

7.2.4 Moderating Effect (RQ4)

The last objective of the current study was to test the moderating effect of Blockchain technology (BCT) on SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), SC resilience, CE practices and sustainable supply chain performance. The result of the study reveals that Blockchain technology (BCT) plays a complex role in boosting some positive effects while dampening others in the food supply chain context.

(a). BCT Moderates the Relationship between SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), and SC Resilience

Blockchain technology (BCT) amplifies the positive impact of agility and collaboration on building SC resilience. The result of the study is supported by resource-based view (RBV), (Barney, 1991) resource

dependant theory (RDT) (Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003) and dynamic capabilities view developed by (Teece et al., 1997). RBV suggests that valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources can provide a competitive advantage (Bain, 1968). BCT enables sharing of capacity information and resource sharing through smart contracts, which are valuable and rare capabilities that enhance agility and collaboration (Lohmer et al., 2020). The Blockchain technology-enabled capabilities are difficult to imitate or substitute, conferring competitive advantage in building resilient supply chains. RDT suggested that organizations reduce environmental uncertainties by acquiring control over critical resources from external sources (Selznick, 1980). BCT facilitates communication, cooperation, and integration among supply chain partners, reducing dependence on any single entity. This distributed control over resources through collaboration enhances agility and resilience against disruptions (Nandi et al., 2021a) . Dynamic capabilities involve adapting, integrating, and reconfiguring internal and external resources to match changing environments (Teece et al., 1997). Blockchain technology enables easy addition of new partners, capacity sharing, and early risk mitigation, exhibiting dynamic capabilities. These capabilities allow supply chains to sense disruptions, seize opportunities through agility and collaboration, and reconfigure for resilience (Y. Liu et al., 2024; Pattanayak et al., 2023). Prior research has consistently highlighted the significant role of Blockchain technology (BCT) in enhancing traceability within supply chains. Studies by Dutta et al. (2020), Fosso Wamba et al. (2020), Kshetri (2018), Queiroz et al. (2021), and Shahzad et al. (2024) emphasize that BCT provides a secure, immutable ledger that captures real-time data across supply chain nodes, thereby increasing visibility and transparency. However, the current study's finding that Blockchain reduces the positive effect of traceability on supply chain resilience contradicts this established view. One possible explanation for this contradiction is that, while Blockchain certainly improves data accuracy and transparency, it may simultaneously introduce technological and operational complexities that hinder rapid response (J. Xu et al., 2021; S. Xu et al., 2020). Implementing Blockchain requires significant changes in systems integration, data governance, and stakeholder alignment, which can initially slow down processes rather than accelerate them (Kouhizadeh et al., 2021). Moreover, the sheer volume and granularity of Blockchain-based data can create challenges in filtering critical information during disruptions, potentially leading to analysis paralysis rather than swift action (De Rossi & Abbatemarco, 2023) .

(a). BCT Moderates the Relationship between SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), and CE Practices

The findings reveal that Blockchain technology strengthens the positive relationships between collaboration, traceability, and adopting circular economy practices. Blockchain technology enables secure and transparent sharing of data and resources among supply chain partners, fostering collaboration and reducing information asymmetry. RBV suggested that an organization's internal resources and capabilities are key to achieving and maintaining competitive advantage (Barney, 1991; Newbert, 2008). Blockchain technology, as a valuable resource, enhances both collaboration and traceability by providing a secure and transparent platform for data exchange. This improved data

exchange supports circular economy practices by ensuring that all partners can access reliable information about materials and processes, facilitating recycling and resource efficiency (Chaudhuri et al., 2022; Nandi et al., 2021a; Samadhiya et al., 2023). RDT emphasizes the importance of external relationships and resources, suggesting that organizations are dependent on other entities for critical resources (Bode et al., 2011; Tashman, 2021). Blockchain technology reduces the uncertainty and dependency in these relationships by ensuring transparent and immutable records of transactions. This fosters trust and collaboration among supply chain partners, supporting circular economy practices by enabling better tracking and management of resources throughout their lifecycle (Nandi et al., 2021a). The relationship between agility and the circular economy (CE) is typically seen as positive, with agility being an enabler for the implementation of CE practices (Cherrafi et al., 2022; Edwin Cheng et al., 2022; Lotfi et al., 2024). However, the findings of the current study revealed that Blockchain technology lessens the negative impact of agility on circular economy adoption. This finding highlights an important question: do agility and CE have a negative relationship? Perhaps the explanation lies in the fact that agility focuses on the ability to respond quickly to market changes and demands, often involving short-term planning and frequent adjustments to operations. On the other hand, CE requires long-term planning and stable processes to effectively implement recycling, reuse, and sustainable resource management (Weigend Rodríguez et al., 2020). The long-term nature of circular economy practices can be hindered by the constant changes and short-term focus needed for agility. While agility and CE practices may have conflicting impacts due to their different time horizons and operational focuses, Blockchain technology can serve as a bridge by fostering transparency, collaboration, efficient resource management, and dynamic capabilities (Meier et al., 2023; Quayson et al., 2023). By leveraging Blockchain technology, organizations can potentially mitigate the negative impact of agility on circular economy adoption and achieve a harmonious balance between the two.

(c). BCT Moderates the Relationship between SC Capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), and Sustainable Supply Chain Performance

Another important finding of this study is that Blockchain technology enhances the positive influence of agility and collaboration on sustainable supply chain performance. This result is backed by (Sheel and Nath, 2019, Di Vaio and Varriale, 2020, Paul et al., 2021, Yousefi and Mohamadpour Tosarkani, 2022). This research supports the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Resource Dependence Theory (RDT), suggesting organizations gain sustainable competitive advantage by managing their unique, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources and inter-organizational dependencies effectively. Blockchain technology offers a transparent and immutable ledger that enhances traceability and trust in the supply chain. This transparency can significantly improve agility by allowing firms to respond quickly to changes and disruptions. By facilitating secure and transparent data sharing, Blockchain technology enhances collaboration among supply chain partners. This improved collaboration can lead to better coordination, reducing inefficiencies and enhancing sustainability. The finding of the study also support. Dynamic capabilities view (DCV), such as sensing, seizing, and reconfiguring, allow firms

to adapt to rapidly changing environments and create competitive advantage. Blockchain technology's ability to provide real-time data sharing and traceability can enhance these dynamic capabilities, supporting agility and collaboration in the supply chain (Coreynen et al., 2020; Zahoor et al., 2022). Surprisingly, the current study findings shows that Blockchain technology diminishes the positive effect of traceability on sustainable supply chain performance. In fact, most of the sources suggest the opposite and consistently highlight how Blockchain technology, by enabling secure, transparent and immutable traceability, can positively contribute to sustainable supply chain performance (Centobelli et al., 2022; Feng et al., 2020; George et al., 2019; Razak et al., 2023; Sunny et al., 2020). However, the results of the present research suggest a more complex reality. A possible explanation may lie in the fact that implementing traceability systems particularly digital or blockchain-based solutions can entail significant costs, complex technology integration, and resource-intensive data management, all of which can diminish the anticipated benefits of traceability for sustainable performance (Kouhizadeh, 2022). Blockchain platforms can become overwhelming, making it harder for firms to extract actionable sustainability insights efficiently (Schinckus, 2020). Instead of simplifying sustainability reporting and decision-making, Blockchain may create information overload that slows down processes and impedes quick responses to sustainability issues (S. Xu et al., 2020). Despite Blockchain's promise of transparency, some supply chain partners may still hesitate to share sensitive sustainability data on a decentralized ledger, fearing competitive disadvantage or loss of proprietary information (Queiroz et al., 2021). Such reluctance could limit Blockchain's ability to fully translate traceability into sustainability outcomes.

The collective results and insights from this research have enriched the existing understanding of sustainable supply chain performance. The findings add valuable knowledge to the field, expanding the comprehension of the factors influencing and optimizing supply chain operations. The contributions can be broadly categorized into two significant domains: theoretical implications (pertaining to academic implications) and practical implications (relating to managerial applications). From academic viewpoint, the implications derived from this study enrich the existing body of knowledge within this field of study. The findings provide valuable insights into how SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Blockchain technology impact SC resilience and circular economy practices, ultimately affecting sustainable performance in food and drink manufacturing. These results offer crucial guidance for organizations aiming to enhance sustainability through strategic capability development and technology adoption.

7.3 Theoretical Implications

Theoretical implications, also referred to as academic implications, can be viewed through two distinct lenses: empirical implications and conceptual implications. These two aspects will be further elaborated upon in the subsequent sub-sections, providing a comprehensive understanding of the study's theoretical contributions.

7.3.1 Empirical Implications

This study consolidates previous empirical research to develop the conceptual framework on SC capabilities such as agility (Bag & Rahman, 2023; Blome et al., 2013; I. Kazancoglu et al., 2022; Nandi et al., 2021b; Scala & Lindsay, 2021; M.-L. Tseng et al., 2024; M. Wang & Wang, 2024), collaboration (Vachon and Klassen, 2008, Scholten and Schilder, 2015, De Angelis, Howard and Miemczyk, 2018, Leising, Quist and Bocken, 2018, Calicchio Berardi and Peregrino de Brito, 2021, Lusiantoro and Pradiptyo, 2022, Gani, Yoshi and Rahman, 2023, Zhou et al., 2024) , traceability (Timmer and Kaufmann, 2017, Anastasiadis et al., 2022, Cherrafi et al., 2022, Santana and Ribeiro, 2022, Zhao et al., 2022, Zhou, Pullman and Xu, 2022, Davari et al., 2023, Ma, Shi and Kang, 2023, Razak, Hendry and Stevenson, 2023, Nasyiah et al., 2024), SC resilience (A. Ali et al., 2017; Carvalho et al., 2014; M. M. H. Chowdhury et al., 2019; Christopher & Peck, 2004; Gunasekaran et al., 2015; Negri et al., 2021; Pettit et al., 2019; Pires Ribeiro & Barbosa-Povoa, 2018; Soni et al., 2014; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015; X. Zhu & Wu, 2022) , CE practices (Arsawan et al., 2024; Bag, 2023; Bag et al., 2019; Ciccullo et al., 2021; Dossa et al., 2022; Malhotra, 2023; Mora-Contreras et al., 2023; Z. Yu et al., 2022), sustainable supply chain performance (Cao & Zhang, 2011; Edwin Cheng et al., 2022; Fahimnia & Jabbarzadeh, 2016; Fantasy & Tipu, 2024; Geyi et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2018; Hussain & Malik, 2020; Koberg & Longoni, 2019; G. Kumar et al., 2018; A. N. H. Le et al., 2021; Malhotra, 2023; Rahman et al., 2023; B. Zhou et al., 2023) and Blockchain technology (Centobelli et al., 2022; Cherrafi et al., 2022; Di Vaio & Varriale, 2020; Dutta et al., 2020; Feng et al., 2020; Fosso Wamba et al., 2020; Lohmer et al., 2020; Nandi et al., 2021b; Qader et al., 2022; Queiroz et al., 2021; Samadhiya et al., 2023; Shahzad et al., 2024; Sheel & Nath, 2019; Sunny et al., 2020; Yousefi & Mohamadpour Tosarkani, 2022) .

This study has developed a comprehensive measurement model that integrates the supply chain capabilities (such as agility, collaboration, and traceability), Blockchain technology, supply chain resilience, and sustainable supply chain performance altogether. The model examines the interplay between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), Blockchain technology, SC resilience, and CE practices in achieving sustainable supply chain performance. By combining these critical factors, the study offers a holistic perspective on leveraging SC capabilities and emerging technologies to foster resilience, circularity, and sustainability in supply chain performance. Moreover, this empirical study makes a significant contribution to the existing body of knowledge by integrating SC resilience and CE practices as key drivers for achieving sustainable supply chain performance. While previous literature has predominantly addressed these factors individually, the current research combines them, offering a novel perspective on their synergistic impact. Additionally, the study enriches the understanding of key supply chain capabilities, including agility, collaboration, traceability, and the role of Blockchain technology, in integration of SC resilience and CE concepts in the realm of supply chain management. By bridging these elements, the research expands the knowledge base, providing insights

into the interplay between these factors and their collective influence on sustainable supply chain performance.

Within the broader field of study, this research has made a valuable contribution to academic knowledge by providing empirical evidence that reinforces and strengthens the proposed research framework. The findings derived from the empirical investigation lend credibility and support to the conceptual underpinnings of the framework, solidifying its theoretical foundations and enhancing its applicability within the domain of inquiry. Furthermore, this study confirms the path relationships within the proposed model, providing initial evidence of the critical factors that should be considered by future researchers when developing conceptual frameworks encompassing constructs such as supply chain capabilities, Blockchain technology (BCT), SC resilience, circular economy (CE) practices, and supply chain operational performance. The validation of these path relations offers valuable insights and serves as a guiding reference for scholars aiming to build upon or extend conceptual models within this domain. By identifying the significant factors and their interrelationships, the research paves the way for more comprehensive and robust frameworks in subsequent studies.

Additionally, this study explored the mediating influence of SC resilience and circular economy (CE) practices. While previous research often examined these factors independently, this study integrated them by investigating the mediating role of SC resilience in the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance. The current study also examined the moderating role of blockchain technology (BCT) in influencing these capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) to contribute to SC resilience, CE practices, and ultimately, sustainable supply chain performance. The findings confirm the complex role blockchain technology plays in this context. By unpacking these mediating and moderating mechanisms, the study provides valuable insights into the interplay between various factors driving sustainability in supply chain management.

Several recent studies have been conducted across various countries and industries, the empirical evidence presented in this research is derived from the UK food and drink manufacturing sector. Consequently, the research model employed in this study holds the potential for replication and further testing in different geographical contexts and industrial settings. The findings and methodological approach can serve as a foundation for future researchers to validate and extend the model's applicability across diverse national and sectoral landscapes. This transferability of the research model enhances its relevance and contributes to the broader generalizability of the findings, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the interplay between the examined constructs in a multitude of environments.

7.3.2 Conceptual Implications

This research draws upon three prominent theories in supply chain management - the Resource-Based View (RBV), Resource Dependence Theory (RDT), and Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT). The synthesis of these theoretical perspectives highlights the ability of firms to build, integrate, reconfigure,

and leverage relational assets, internal and external competencies, heterogeneous resources, capabilities, and inter-organizational interactions to address quick change market environment and meet the new challenges to gain competitive advantage (Barney, 1991; Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003; Teece et al., 1997).

The RBV stated that a firm's competitive advantage stems from its valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources and capabilities. In the context of this study, the RBV emphasizes the importance of internal resources and capabilities, such as supply chain agility, collaboration, and traceability, in contributing to SC resilience, circular economy (CE) practices, and sustainable supply chain performance.

Resource Dependence Theory (RDT) acknowledges that organizations rely on external resources and underscores the importance of effectively managing dependencies on other entities and the broader external environment (Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003). In relation to implementing circular economy (CE) practices, multiple stakeholders are involved in facilitating the return, reuse, and recycling of materials. This study incorporates RDT by recognizing the crucial role of inter-organizational interactions and collaborations in achieving successful CE practices and, consequently, sustainable performance.

Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT) focuses on a firm's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external resources and competencies to address rapidly changing environments (Teece et al., 1997). This study aligns with this theory by emphasizing the need for firms to develop dynamic capabilities, such as supply chain agility, collaboration, traceability, and the adoption of emerging technologies like Blockchain, to adapt to dynamic supply chain environments and meet new challenges. In this study combining these theories provoke the contemporary thinking of incorporating SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and Blockchain technology as key resources and capabilities that contribute to SC resilience, CE practices, and ultimately, sustainable supply chain performance. This theoretical extension enriches the understanding of how firms can leverage their internal resources and capabilities, as well as external collaborations and technological advancements, to achieve a competitive advantage in dynamic and sustainable supply chain environments.

7.4 Practical Implications

In addition to its theoretical contributions, this study presents various valuable practical implications, known as managerial implications, for food and drink manufacturing industry's practitioners/managers. The practical contribution of the current work is substantial because the adoption of CE practices and SC resilience for achieving sustainable supply chain performance in food and drink manufacturing industry. From a SC perspective, firstly, supply chain managers should consider the integration of SC resilience and CE practices for sustainable supply chain performance. This integration is crucial for creating sustainable supply chain operations in the face of increasing disruptions and resource constraints.

Secondly, indeed, supply chain managers should consider supply chain capabilities including agility, collaboration and traceability while integrating SC resilience and CE practices. The interplay

between these capabilities, resilience, and CE can help food and drink manufacturers navigate challenges, adapt to changing conditions, and contribute to a more sustainable and circular supply chain ecosystem.

Thirdly, to amplify the impact of SC capabilities (agility, collaboration and traceability) on SC resilience and CE practices, leveraging blockchain technology (BCT) as a catalyst is recommended. As an innovative, decentralized, and distributed technology, blockchain ensures confidentiality, integrity, and availability of all transactions and data across all supply chain stakeholders and levels. This transparency can significantly enhance decision-making processes toward achieving resilience and CE in food supply chains.

Lastly, Supply chain managers should be aware of the Blockchain's complex role in influencing SC resilience, CE practices, to achieve sustainable supply chain performance. However, the relationship between Blockchain, SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), SC resilience, CE practices, and sustainable performance is complex and multi-faceted. The impact of Blockchain depends on factors such as the specific supply chain context, the maturity of Blockchain implementation, the degree of integration with other technologies, and the alignment with organizational strategies and processes (Meier et al., 2023; Min, 2019; Nandi et al., 2021a). Supply chain managers must recognize these complexities and develop a nuanced understanding of how Blockchain technology interacts with SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), supply resilience, CE practices, and sustainability goals within their specific supply chain ecosystems. This holistic perspective is essential for crafting tailored strategies that leverage Blockchain's potential while navigating its challenges and limitations effectively.

By embracing these actionable insights, supply chain professionals can strategically harness resilience, CE, key supply chain capabilities, and emerging technologies like Blockchain to drive meaningful sustainability improvements throughout their supply chains.

7.5 Limitations of the Study

While this research offers insightful findings and contributes to both theoretical and practical knowledge, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations that should be addressed. These limitations primarily pertain to the methodology employed and the generalizability of the study's results. Such constraints are commonly encountered due to practical considerations such as time and budgetary restrictions. The key limitations of this study are outlined in the following sections.

7.5.1 Methodological Limitations

A number of limitations need to be noted regarding methodology employed. One potential limitation of this study is its reliance on a survey methodology. The research is limited to medium and large food and drink manufacturing firms in the UK that have been adopting or initiating/planning BCT and CE practices. This research has also encountered the challenge of a low response rate, primarily because blockchain technology and circular economy (CE) concepts have only recently emerged. To mitigate

this issue, the researcher employed a multiple respondent strategy, aiming to gather responses from several informants within each organization rather than relying on a single respondent per firm.

The time horizon is another methodological limitation. This study employed a cross-sectional research design, capturing data at a single point in time. However, aspects related to company SC resilience, circular economy (CE), and sustainable supply chain performance, which are inherently longitudinal processes. These elements unfold over extended periods, making a single-point-in-time analysis insufficient for capturing their full development.

The sample limited to high-level employees such as managers and CEOs etc. but would tend to miss people who were lower-level employees. Their insights on SC resilience, circular economy practices, and blockchain technology implementation could provide a more comprehensive view of organizational dynamics and practical challenges.

7.5.2 Generalizability Limitations

The generalisability of the results is subject to certain limitations. For instance, as outlined in the study's scope, this research was conducted specifically within the food and drink manufacturing industry in the UK. Consequently, generalizing the findings to other industries or sectors may not be feasible, as the dynamics and contexts can vary significantly across different domains.

Furthermore, the applicability of the results to other countries or regions worldwide is limited, as the study was confined to the UK context. Cultural, economic, regulatory, and operational factors can differ substantially across national boundaries, potentially influencing the relationships and phenomena under investigation.

The results primarily capture participants' views on SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), resilience, circular economy practices, sustainable supply chain performance, and Blockchain technology within the specific context of their organizations during the study period. This context-specific nature of the data may limit the generalizability of the findings to other organizations, industries, or time periods.

7.6 Recommendations for Future Study

The limitations acknowledged in the current study pave the way for exciting avenues of future research in the realm of sustainable supply chain performance, SC resilience, and circular economy (CE) practices. These limitations serve as catalysts for further exploration and advancement in this critical domain. Future studies could focus on establishing the interdependent relationships between various SC capabilities beyond agility, collaboration, and traceability, as well as the different circular economy (CE) practices.

The current study treated blockchain technology (BCT) as a moderating variable, examining how it influences the relationships between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), SC resilience, CE practices, and sustainable supply chain performance. However, as highlighted in the search results, Blockchain technology has the potential for direct and transformative impacts across various aspects of supply chain management and sustainability initiatives. By establishing these direct

relationships, future research could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how blockchain technology, as a disruptive and transformative innovation, can directly shape and drive sustainable, circular and resilient supply chain practices.

It would be interesting to expanding the scope across diverse industries and geographical regions, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of the interplay between resilience, CE practices, and sustainable performance in varied contexts. Employing longitudinal or panel study designs to capture the dynamic and evolving nature of these relationships over time, providing insights into their temporal stability and potential shifts. Incorporating perspectives from employees at various organizational levels, including frontline workers and operational staff, to gain a holistic view of how resilience strategies, CE initiatives, and emerging technologies are perceived, adopted, and implemented across different organizational strata.

These future research directions hold the potential to generate actionable knowledge, inform evidence-based decision-making, and contribute to the advancement of theory and practice in the pursuit of resilient, circular, and sustainable supply chains.

CHAPTER 8 : CONCLUSIONS

In today's dynamic business landscape, where sustainability is no longer a mere buzzword but a strategic imperative, this study delves into the intricate interplay of various factors that can propel organizations towards sustainable supply chain performance to achieve competitive advantage. Specifically, this study investigates the synergistic relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability), SC resilience, CE practices, BCT and their impact on sustainable supply chain performance. Furthermore, this study also investigating the mediating role of SC resilience and CE practices between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and sustainable supply chain performance. This study delves deeper into the pivotal role of Blockchain technology (BCT) as a potential game-changer. Specifically, it explores the moderating impact of BCT on the interplay between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and the desired outcomes of SC resilience, CE practices, and sustainable supply chain performance.

This study set out to collect primary data via a self-administered survey from 299 managerial-level employees in the dynamic and essential UK food and drink manufacturing sector. The analysis of this primary data yielded compelling findings. Notably, the empirical evidence revealed that SC capabilities encompassing agility, collaboration, and traceability, exhibited a significant positive relationship with SC resilience (SCRES). This highlighted the pivotal role these capabilities play in bolstering the ability of organizations to withstand and recover from disruptions effectively. While the findings highlighted the importance of collaboration and traceability in fostering circular economy practices (CEP), the data did not reveal a statistically significant association between agility and CEP adoption. Similarly direct influence of collaboration on sustainable supply chain performance (SSCP) did not reach statistically significant in this study.

The present study establishes a quantitative framework for evaluating sustainable supply chain performance. The empirical investigation reveals two pivotal factors driving sustainable supply chain performance in the UK food and drink manufacturing sector: SC resilience and circular economy (CE) practices. Notably, both SC resilience and the adoption of CE practices demonstrated a statistically significant positive impact on the sustainable supply chain performance.

Furthermore, the mediation analysis showed that SC resilience positively and significantly mediates the relationship between agility, traceability, and sustainable supply chain performance. However, collaboration's impact on sustainable performance was not mediated by SC resilience. Additionally, the study found that circular economy practices positively and significantly mediate the relationship between agility, collaboration, traceability, and sustainable supply chain performance.

The findings of moderation analysis suggested that the integration of Blockchain technology plays a complex moderating role. Specifically, Blockchain technology amplifies the synergistic effects of agility and collaboration on SC resilience but not impacted traceability. BCT strengthens the positive relationships between collaboration and traceability on circular economy practices while reducing the

negative effect of agility on these practices. Interestingly, Blockchain technology enhances the positive influence of agility and collaboration on sustainable supply chain performance but diminishes the positive impact of traceability.

From a RBV and RDT perspective, the study highlights how internal and external relationships particularly agility, collaboration and traceability help organizations dependence on internal and external entities (Nandi et al., 2021b; Öztürk & Bağış, 2025). This was evident in the finding that agility, collaboration and traceability significantly influence on supply chain resilience and circular economy practices. Although collaboration did not directly influence sustainable performance, its positive interaction with Blockchain technology in the context of CE practices reflects how external partnerships and information exchange help manage resource dependencies, consistent with RBV and RDT.

Meanwhile, DCT was central in understanding how dynamic nature of supply chain capabilities enable firms to adapt and transform in response to disruptions and sustainability challenges (Joussen et al., 2025; Köhler & Pizzol, 2020). The significant role of agility, collaboration and traceability in enhancing supply chain resilience and the mediating effect of resilience on sustainable performance demonstrates how dynamic capabilities empower firms to sense, respond, and reconfigure operations amid uncertainty. Additionally, the complex moderating role of Blockchain technology supports the DCT view that digital tools can augment firms' adaptive capabilities, especially in turbulent environments.

The present study was the first of its kind to explore the relationship between SC capabilities (agility, collaboration, and traceability) and SC resilience, CE practices, and sustainable supply chain performance, mediating role of SC resilience and CE practices, and moderating role of BCT in the food and drink manufacturing industry of UK. The conceptual framework laid out in this study provides a novel foundation for future research. It encourages scholars to build upon the proposed framework by incorporating SC resilience and CE practices to achieve sustainable performance. Furthermore, investigate the role of various SC capabilities and Industry 4.0 technologies in facilitating this integration within the domain of supply chain management.

Figure 8.1 Final Model

Figure 8.1 Final Model

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APPENDECES

Appendix A – Questionnaire

Towards Sustainability: The Role of Supply Chain Capabilities, Resilience, Circular Economy, and Blockchain Technology in Food Supply Chains

Section A: Company Profile

This section relates to the background of your company. The questions are meant only for analysis purposes, and it will **NOT** be used to identify your responses individually. Please select one from the alternatives provided.

1. Name of your company (optional): _____
2. Size of your organization
 - a. () Medium firm (50 to 249 employees)
 - b. () Large firm (more than 250 employees)
3. Annual revenues of the company
 - a. () 50-100 million £
 - b. () 100-250 million £
 - c. () 250-500 million £
 - d. () More than 500 million £

Section B: Respondent Profile

1. Your Position in the company: _____
2. Your number of years in the company: _____
3. Gender: _____

Section C: Questionnaire

Please choose the following 7-Point Scale to express your opinion on each of the elements listed below:

Constructs		Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Neutral	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Supply Chain Capabilities (SCCs)								
Agility (Ag)								
Ag1	Our firm quickly detect and adapt to changes, threats, and opportunities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Ag2	Our firm frequently modify tactics and operations when needed	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Ag3	Our firm is able to quickly make decisions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Ag4	Our firm is able to implement decisions quickly in response to market changes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Ag5	Our firm can forecast market demand	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Collaboration (Col)								
Col1	Our firm and supply chain partners share benefits and costs (e.g., inventory cost savings and loss on order changes)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Col2	Our firm and supply chain partners jointly plan to achieve supply chain goals	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Col3	Our firm and supply chain partners have agreements on the importance of collaborations in the supply chain	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Col4	Our firm and supply chain partners collaboratively share costs, risks and benefits	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Col5	Our firm collaborate with our SC partners to acquire requisite knowledge/skill	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Traceability (Tr)								
Tr1	Our firm knows the sources of our raw materials	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Tr2	Our firm tracks the processes involved in producing product throughout our complete supply	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Tr3	Our firm traces the origins of our purchases through the entire supply chain	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Tr4	Our firm tracks the environmental performance of our complete supply chain	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Tr5	Our firm knows what chemicals or elements are in our purchased components	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Supply Chain Resilience (SCRES)								
SCRES1	Our firm's supply chain is well prepared to deal with financial outcomes of supply chain disruptions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SCRES2	Our firm's supply chain can maintain a desired level of connectedness among its members at the time of disruption	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SCRES3	Our firm's supply chain can maintain a desired level of control over structure and function at the time of disruption	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SCRES4	Our firm's supply chain can adequately respond to unexpected disruptions by quickly restoring its product flow	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SCRES5	Our firm's supply chain can quickly return to its original state after being disrupted.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SCRES6	Our firm's supply chain can move to a new, more desirable state after being disrupted.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SCRES7	Our firm's supply chain can extract meaning and useful knowledge from disruptions and unexpected events	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Circular Economy Practices (CEP)								
CEP1	Our firm enhanced converting waste into input for production	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CEP2	Our firm is proactive in sharing certain resources to improve collective efficiency	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CEP3	Our firm promotes saving energy consumption	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CEP4	Our firm promotes water recycling	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CEP5	Our firm promotes sourcing from economy instead of ecological reserve	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CEP6	Our firm increased added value for consumer by adding value to products and material	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CEP7	Our firm is proactive in creating valuable inputs for business partners in the supply chain	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CEP8	Our firm is proactive in responding to fluctuations with an appropriate business model in accordance with circular economy practices	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Blockchain Technology (BCT)								
BC1	Our firm uses blockchain technology to share information	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
BC2	Our firm uses blockchain technology as it helps to maintain confidentiality, integrity and availability of the data	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
BC3	Our firm uses blockchain technology to improve transparency in supply chain	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
BC4	Our firm routinely uses blockchain technology as a data platform that traces the origins, use and destination of supplies	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
BC5	Our firm routinely uses blockchain technology to avoid unreliable information to avoid confusion among partners engaged in supply chain operations	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (SSCP)								
SSCP1	Our firm achieved profitable growth over time	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SSCP2	Our firm achieved market share growth over time	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SSCP3	Our firm improved environmental performance over time	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SSCP4	Our firm improved occupational health and safety of employees	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SSCP5	Our firm improved in overall stakeholder welfare or betterment	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Appendix B – Consent Form

Title of the Project **Towards Sustainability: The Role of Supply Chain Capabilities, Resilience, Circular Economy, and Blockchain Technology in Food Supply Chains**

Researcher Details **Name** Amina Mehmood
Purpose of Research PhD Candidate
Email [REDACTED]

Participant's Details **Name**
Email

Please Initial Box (Y/N)

1. I verify that I have thoroughly read and understood the information sheet provided by the researcher dated _____ for the above-mentioned study and also have had the chance to raise questions.
 2. I acknowledge that I am voluntarily participating in the study and that I am free to withdraw my participation at any moment before submission of the survey.
 3. I understand that once I have submitted the survey, I have agreed to be a part of the above-mentioned study.
 4. I confirm that I have agreed to provide personal information that would be used for the only purpose of my partaking in the study.
 5. I agree to the unknown and anonymous use of the scores from my participation achieved by the researcher in journals and scientific reports.
 6. I voluntarily agree to take part in the above-mentioned study.
- Participant Signature Date:
- Researcher Signature: Date:

Appendix C – Participant Information Sheet

Towards Sustainability: The Role of Supply Chain Capabilities, Resilience, Circular Economy, and Blockchain Technology in Food Supply Chains

To the Participant,

Dear Madam/Sir,

Thank you for your interest in participating in this research study. The primary aim of this research is to investigate the impact of supply chain capabilities, supply chain resilience, CE practices and Blockchain technology on sustainable performance in food supply chains. By exploring these interconnections, the study seeks to develop a comprehensive framework that explains how these elements work together to enhance sustainability in the food supply chains. The information provided by you will be an intuitive contributor to my study. Therefore, it is requested to you participate in this study by completing the questionnaire.

Your participation will involve completing a questionnaire about your experiences and perspectives related supply chain capabilities, supply chain resilience, CE practices, blockchain technology, and sustainable supply chain practices. The total time required for this questionnaire is approximately 10-15 minutes and you are invited to participate in this survey willingly and you can withdraw if you are not willing to participate. All information collected will be kept strictly confidential. Your responses will be anonymized and stored securely, with only the research team having access to the raw data. Results will be reported in aggregate form only, ensuring that no individual participants can be identified.

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You are free to withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason and without any consequences. While there are no direct benefits to participants, your input will contribute valuable insights that advance our understanding of sustainable food supply chains. The findings may inform industry practices and policies aimed at improving sustainability in the food sector.

There are no anticipated risks associated with participating in this study beyond those encountered in everyday life. If you have any questions about the research, please feel free to contact the lead investigator (Amina Mehmood, [REDACTED]). By completing and submitting the questionnaire, you are indicating your consent to participate in this study and for your data to be used as described above. Thank you for considering participation in this important research; your insights are invaluable in helping us create more resilient and sustainable food supply chains.

Yours faithfully,

Amina Mehmood
PhD Candidate
Email: [REDACTED]

University of the West of Scotland, School of Business and Creative Industries
Paisley Campus, Paisley
PA1 2BE, Scotland, United Kingdom
Tel.: [REDACTED]

Appendix D – Ethical Approval

23/10/2023

Dear Mrs Amina Mehmood,

Your application 21712: Resilient and Circular Food Supply Chain in Fourth Industrial Revolution , submission 16914, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Appendix E - Data

Descriptive Statistics

Z - Score Frequency Distribution

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Outlier Cases (Z Score + 3.29)
Ag1	315	-1.69947	2.34841	
Ag2	315	-3.14515	1.58383	
Ag3	315	-2.38953	1.84508	
Ag4	315	-1.53803	2.425	
Ag5	315	-1.6623	2.2236	
Col1	315	-1.47755	2.80225	
Col2	315	-1.36617	2.74213	
Col3	315	-1.44861	3.45797	1
Col4	315	-1.38299	3.19067	
Col5	315	-1.46731	3.32236	2
Tr1	315	-2.85179	1.3329	
Tr2	315	-4.21174	1.39205	3
Tr3	315	-4.19408	1.39212	4
Tr4	315	-4.28377	1.42792	5
Tr5	315	-4.37197	1.34243	6
SCRES1	315	-2.05998	2.68513	
SCRES2	315	-2.06734	2.37022	
SCRES3	315	-1.9306	2.55751	
SCRES4	315	-2.27238	2.1123	
SCRES5	315	-2.12512	2.11839	
SCRES6	315	-2.16028	2.08613	
SCRES7	315	-2.1214	2.33354	
CEP1	315	-3.59935	1.63758	7
CEP2	315	-3.7912	1.50471	8
CEP3	315	-3.73803	1.4894	9
CEP4	315	-3.47136	1.60278	10
CEP5	315	-3.72864	1.72158	11
CEP6	315	-3.65545	1.34007	12
CEP7	315	-3.74793	1.5641	13
CEP8	315	-2.42977	1.8944	
BCT1	315	-3.06156	1.53078	
BCT2	315	-2.73376	1.65979	
BCT3	315	-3.45682	1.4555	14
BCT4	315	-4.01968	1.50957	15
BCT5	315	-3.39294	1.62479	16
SSCP1	315	-2.63866	1.64025	
SSCP2	315	-2.66091	1.63198	
SSCP3	315	-2.77509	1.60115	
SSCP4	315	-3.28567	1.55637	
SSCP5	315	-2.52051	1.69148	

Mean and Standard Deviation

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Agility	299	3	0.689
Collaboration	299	2.26	0.743
Traceability	299	4.06	0.585
Supply Chain Resilience	299	2.93	0.70
Circular Economy Practices	299	3.78	0.557
Sustainable Supply Chain Performance	299	3.56	0.76
Black chain Technology	299	3.96	0.481

Distribution of the Data

Skewness and Kurtosis Values

Variable	Skewness	Kurtosis
Ag1	.248	-.818
Ag2	-.512	.026
Ag3	-.425	-.729
Ag4	.417	-.443
Ag5	.282	-.936
Col1	.856	.259
Col2	.687	-.092
Col3	.821	.659
Col4	.679	.097
Col5	.735	.360
Tr1	-.641	1.175
Tr2	-.437	.785
Tr3	-.376	.332
Tr4	-.322	.330
Tr5	-.318	.058
SCRES1	.277	-.550
SCRES2	.091	-.914
SCRES3	.299	-.462
SCRES4	-.286	-.782
SCRES5	-.105	-1.009
SCRES6	-.146	-1.003
SCRES7	.062	-.689
CEP1	-.415	.359
CEP2	-.513	.670
CEP3	-.314	.062
CEP4	-.474	.218
CEP5	-.499	.468
CEP6	-.571	.380
CEP7	-.251	-.021
CEP8	.059	-.608
BCT1	-.656	2.051
BCT2	-.431	.864
BCT3	.219	.297
BCT4	-.500	1.003
BCT5	-.278	-.040
SSCP1	-.326	-.375
SSCP2	-.407	-.226
SSCP3	-.524	.220
SSCP4	-.866	1.088
SSCP5	-.274	-.444